

Subjective Well-Being and Migration: Empirical Insights from Hungary and Austria

Research Report

MIGWELL

Well-being and Migration:
The Hungary – Austria Migration Nexus

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MIGWELL at a glance

The MIGWELL project focuses on the nexus of migration and well-being in Hungary and Austria. Using quantitative and qualitative research methods, it seeks to explore the impacts of migration on subjective well-being in the case of Hungarian immigrants in Austria as well as the effects of subjective well-being differences on emigration potential in Hungary. The approach of this project is innovative not only because it links the concepts of ‘well-being’ and ‘migration’, but also because it interprets their two-way causal relationship within one research framework. Since the Covid-19 pandemic might have a profound impact on both pillars, MIGWELL will also reflect on the rapidly changing socio-economic and well-being related issues that have emerged due to the epidemic throughout the life cycle of the project. The theoretical expansion of these concepts and the empirical findings of the project may contribute to more effective policies in both countries.

1. Introduction

Our first project report provided an overview of the key definitions and some typologies of migration processes in general, followed by a literature-based review of the main theories on migration and well-being (Németh et al., 2022). It was followed by the presentation of the accumulated knowledge of the migration processes in and between Hungary and Austria (Németh et al., 2023a). The third report investigated the subjective well-being patterns in the two countries and the key factors that are responsible for the SWB differences (Németh et al. 2023b).

The main goal of Work Package 3 was to implement the narrative and cognitive interviews, set up the surveys and analyse the newly collected primary data. While the first two qualitative methods functioned as exploratory, pre-test works, the surveys provided new information about the SWB profiles of the concrete target groups. Therefore, this fourth project report aims to provide an in-depth analysis of our primary data, integrated into the previously built MIGWELL database.

The first report set out in detail the logical structure of the MIGWELL project (Figure 1). In the following, we will use this structure as a starting point and follow this logic to explore the connections between SWB and migration. However, it's important to note that certain aspects of the comparative analysis will be given more emphasis than others. This is because we aim to focus on the key issues that, based on our understanding of the literature, extensive secondary analyses, and the available methodological tools, offer the most significant insights.

Figure 1. Logical structure of the project. Source: Németh et. al., 2022: 43.

2. Sources and methods

The MIGWELL project applies a mixed-methods approach including secondary data analyses and the combination of quantitative and qualitative methods: focus groups, interviews, and surveys in both countries. This chapter provides an overview of the diverse methodological toolkit we applied in Work Package 3. The empirical fieldwork consisted of successive steps of different types of data collection, with each step following the sequence listed below. Each stage was designed with a clearly defined objective and sought to broaden the horizon of the research, building always on the experience of the previous stage:

secondary data analysis (WP2)

narrative interviews with actual and potential migrants or stayers

focus groups with stakeholders and experts

cognitive interviews with actual and potential migrants or stayers

surveys in Hungary and Austria

primary data analysis

2.1. Secondary sources

As the previous project report has already highlighted, several potential data sources could have been suitable for the secondary analysis (Németh et al., 2023b: 7-10). Considering all advantages and disadvantages, we finally decided to use the microdata set from the Statistics on Income and Living Conditions (EU-SILC), a representative sample survey of private households in the European Union. Indicators related to subjective well-being were collected in the 2013, 2018 and 2022 ad-hoc modules. Our other important secondary source was the 2016 Hungarian Microcensus with a distinct subjective well-being module.

As a result of our database building process, in Work Package 2 we created an integrated and weighted MIGWELL dataset. (About a detailed description of the process see Németh et al., 2023b: 11-15, 141-167). At the time the previous project report was written, the 2022 EU-SILC data were not yet available. Therefore, our first task in Work Package 3 was to update the

database with the new EU-SILC data for Hungary and Austria, which were published in late 2023. As a result, the dataset expanded to 133,557 observations (i.e., survey respondents) and 96 variables (their answers to selected questions). This updated dataset served as the foundation for integrating our primary survey data (Chapter 2.5).

2.2. Narrative interviews

The secondary sources represent a top-down approach because they define the components of well-being from a particular scientific position. Such lists are integral parts of the multi-dimensional frameworks for comparative reasons (McGregor et al., 2015:3). However, in order to scrutinise the migration-SWB nexus from the people's perspective, we had to understand the way in which potential migrants or stayers in Hungary and Hungarian immigrants in Austria construct their well-being, i.e., the areas of life to which they attach the greatest importance and the extent to which they are satisfied with achieved well-being outcomes. Moreover, we wanted to explore the motivations and their intentions of staying or moving to another country (including the option to return to Hungary) as well as their pre- and post-migration experiences through the prism of subjective well-being.

In general, the narrative interview technique is based on the idea that oral life stories have an identity-giving function. It aims to capture the way in which people interpret, construct and narrate their life events (Riessman 1993; Rosenthal 2004). This method is especially useful in analysing migration stories and related biographies: understanding the way in which migration creates narrative identity and the kinds of discourses that are employed (Kovács & Melegh 2001).

Therefore, 10-10 narrative interviews with immigrants in Austria and potential emigrants/stayers or return migrants in Hungary were conducted to gather information about people's preferences and values in permissive, non-threatening environments (Table 1-2). The typically two-hours-long narrative interviews followed the standardised guidelines, designed specifically for the three main types of our target population (Tóth et al., 2023).¹ Additionally, the semi-structured interviews provided the opportunity to go into more depth on certain topics where there was a need to explore more complex issues.

The translated transcriptions proved particularly valuable for the subsequent research activities, first and foremost the focus groups with stakeholders, as they allowed us to address topics considered highly relevant to SWB. Indirectly, insights gained from the narrative interviews

¹ The narrative interview outlines are available under the project website: https://www.oew.ac.at/fileadmin/Institute/ISR/pdf/Forschung/MIGWELL_WP3_Narrative_interview_outlines.pdf

facilitated the development of additional survey questions as well. For example, it has become evident that the questionnaires should reflect on overqualification or transnational household structures.

In this project report, there is no separate deliverable dedicated to the qualitative analysis of the interviews. Instead, the forthcoming book by Göncz et al. (in print) will incorporate excerpts from these primary sources, addressing specific topics such as life domains and migration plans or experiences. These qualitative insights are invaluable, as they reveal the perspectives "behind" the statistical analysis. By drawing on real-life experiences, they contextualize the quantitative data and contribute to a deeper understanding and explanation of certain social phenomena.

	Gender	Age	Vocation / profession	Address in Austria (NUTS2)	Past or still present address in Hungary (NUTS2)
1	female	34	social worker	Styria	Western Transdanubia
2	male	54	catering (waiter)	Upper Austria	Northern Hungary
3	male	38	researcher	Styria	Southern Great Plain
4	male	55	house caretaker (hotel)	Tyrol	Southern Great Plain
5	female	36	childcare educator in school	Lower Austria	Western Transdanubia
6	male	53	house painter	Tyrol	Central Hungary
7	female	47	hotel, elderly care	Tyrol	Western Transdanubia
8	male	43	shop assistant, fast food worker	Vienna	Budapest
9	female	60	cleaning woman, babysitter	Vienna	Southern Transdanubia
10	female	50	kindergarten teacher, dance group leader	Vienna	Western Transdanubia

Table 1. Basic data on the narrative interview partners in Austria. Source: own table

	Gender	Age	Vocation / profession	Present status
1	female	50	economist	potencial migrant
2	male	56	physician	potencial migrant / stayer
3	female	45	teacher	return migrant
4	female	46	sport marketing expert	return migrant / potencial migrant
5	female	?	teacher	potencial migrant
6	female	32	philosopher - aesthete	potencial migrant
7	female	62	ex-bank branch manager, present elderly carer	commuter in fortnightly or monhly shift
8	male	65	painter, construction contractor	return migrant
9	male	45	painter	return migrant
10	male	33	electrician	potencial migrant

Table 2. Basic data on the narrative interview partners in Hungary. Source: own table

2.3. Focus groups

Focus group is a widely used qualitative research method in social sciences for gathering empirical experiences from key actors in a particular field. A focus group may be an effective research tools because it offers an open platform for participants to interact and build upon each other’s ideas. We brought together a small group of individuals in Vienna and Budapest who have expertise, interest, or influence over the main topics of the MIGWELL project. They were community leaders and practitioners who are in intensive daily contact with a relatively large number of people from our target populations (Table 3-4). As the narrative interviews, the focus groups also followed the structure of a pre-prepared outline.

	Gender	Vocation / profession	Daily contacts with Hungarians at:
1	female	Teacher at the University of Vienna, Hungarian Studies (linguistics)	University, Hungarian associations in Austria, “Svung” Hungarian Theatre in Vienna, cultural events
2	female	NGO leader in Austria	NGO: mentor program, Hungarian associations in Austria, Cultural events
3	female	Teacher at the Austrian Association of Hungarian Teachers	Schools, cultural events
4	male	Researcher at the Technical University of Vienna (engineer)	University, “Napralforgók” Hungarian Folk Dance group in Vienna, cultural events

Table 3. Participants of the focus group discussion in Austria. Source: own table.

	Gender	Vocation / profession	Daily contacts with Hungarians at:
1	male	secondary school teacher, deputy head teacher in a bilingual secondary school	secondary school in Budapest
2	male	head of a recruitment agency, German-Hungarian interpreter	agency office in Szombathely
3	male	political scientist, currently Captain in the Hungarian penitentiary system, has been working for many years in Germany and the Netherlands, in charge of administrative and other matters for Hungarian employees working there	administrative department of firms employing Hungarian workers in the Netherlands and Germany
4	female	engineer, German-Hungarian interpreter and translator	translation firm office

Table 4. Participants of the focus group discussion in Hungary. Source: own table

The moderated discussions encouraged our participants to share their opinions and reactions to the issues we listed, enabling us to better understand some well-being and migration-related phenomena in Hungary and Austria. Engaging stakeholders helped bridge the gap between social theories, preliminary findings from statistical analyses and real-world experiences. The discussions provided additional information to our individual interviews, highlighted some gaps in existing knowledge (e.g., the “invisible” mental health problems of women who arrived to

Austria as accompanied partners of men) and contributed greatly to improving the survey quality. By incorporating stakeholders' views, we could design questionnaires that are grounded in the lived realities of the target population, leading to more realistic outcomes.

As with the narrative interviews, relevant information from the focus groups are presented in the form of quotes in this project report.

2.4. Cognitive interviews

The cognitive interviewing methods were developed in the 1980s for identifying response errors in survey questionnaires. While statistical agencies, such as the Hungarian Central Statistical Office, routinely implement cognitive interviewing today, its use remains less common in social scientific projects. A cognitive interview primarily focuses on the questionnaire itself rather than the answers of the respondents or the entire survey administration process. The key aspect is its emphasis on the cognitive processes people use to answer questions, examining both overt, observable behaviours and covert, hidden thought processes (Willis, 1999).

There are two main protocols of cognitive interviewing techniques (Forsyth & Lessler 1991). During a *think-aloud* interview participants are specifically asked to "think aloud" as they answer the survey questions. In this method, the interviewer reads each question aloud, while the participant narrates their thought process in arriving at an answer. The interviewer listens and takes notes the participant's reasoning, only intervening when necessary.

Due to its several advantages, *verbal probing* has become a favoured technique among cognitive researchers (Willis, 1999). After the interviewer asks the survey question, and the subject answers, the interviewer follows up by asking for additional details related to the question or the specific answer provided. For example: "How did you arrive at that answer?" "I noticed that you hesitated - what you were thinking?" "How sure are you that...?" "How do you remember that...?" "What does the term ... mean to you"? In essence, the interviewer "probes" deeper to explore the reasoning behind the participant's response.

We applied the verbal probing technique and conducted altogether 10-10 interviews in Austria and Hungary. As with the narrative interviews and focus groups, we prepared a draft interview outline again. Additionally, the cognitive interviews required already a draft version of the survey questionnaire, which we systematically went through with the respondents. Quotes from the cognitive interviews do not appear directly in any project deliverables. The most important aim of these interviews was to compile the best possible survey questionnaire by detecting and eliminating possible misunderstandings and minimising errors. It was a key step in testing the Hungarian and Austrian MIGWELL surveys

2.5. Surveys

The MIGWELL surveys were conducted between December 2023 and February 2024 by two independent professional public poll institutes, Triconsult GmbH in Austria and Szociograf Kft. in Hungary. The MIGWELL teams were responsible for the questionnaires, the survey preparation and all further data analysis. Particular attention was paid to the compatibility of our questionnaires with the EU-SILC and the Hungarian Microcensus questionnaires. It was also important that the primary data from Austria and Hungary were directly comparable, so we synchronised the questions and the response options whenever it was possible. The fieldwork itself was carried out by the two partners mentioned above, with whom we were in constant contact and controlled every step of the process. The questionnaires can be found in a previous MIGWELL project report (Tóth et al. 2023).

2.5.1. MIGWELL survey in Hungary

The Hungarian MIGWELL survey was implemented by Szociográf Kft., also known as the Szocio-Gráf Piac- és Közvéleménykutató Intézet, which is a well-known market and public opinion research institute in Hungary. The survey, based on the probability sampling method, is *representative* for the Hungarian adult population. It mirrors the Hungarian population's characteristics by age, gender, education level, regional distribution, and settlement type.

The *sample selection* was done in two stages. For the first step, the settlement structure of the sample of 1000 inhabitants was determined by region and settlement type based on the 2016 Microcensus conducted by the Hungarian Central Statistical Office. All districts of Budapest and the county seats were included on their own weights, while other municipalities were randomly selected in groups according to their legal status. Cities with county rights that are not county seats were also included in the category of other cities. The next step was the selection of smaller municipalities, which was done randomly by generating random numbers.

The second stage of sampling was the random selection of households at selected sampling points. This was done by means of a „random walk” from a random starting point following a defined rule. A maximum of 6 households could be sampled from a single starting point, so more starting points were selected in municipalities with a larger sample size. (As alternative options – in case of an unexpected problem – we have also provided reserve starting points). Only one household could be asked in a single block of flat. In the case of a detached house or terraced house, neighbouring households couldn't be asked. The selection within a household was made using the „last birthday” method. The household member aged 18 years and over whose last birthday was observed was invited to be interviewed. If this person was not at home at least once, the interviewer had to visit the household at a different time on a different day and could only select another person if there was another failure or refusal to answer.

Cell matrix *weighting* was felt to be problematic due to the high number of cells and the relatively small sample size. Instead, we used the RIM weighting methodology. It is a stepwise process that assigns a weight to each member of the sample, calculated by taking into account each target group into which the individual falls. In other words, weighting according to independent distributions of several variables in an iterative procedure, the weighting process is repeated until the sample distribution of all variables that provide representativeness best fits the population distribution. The resulting range of weights is thus between 0.39 (female, aged 50-59, living in a municipality in Northern Hungary, with secondary education) and 2.44 (male, aged 30-39, living in a county seat in Northern Hungary, with primary education).

Before starting the *fieldwork*, we designated the starting points of the random walks by municipalities. All interviewers received a detailed list of instructions. Before the fieldwork, online and offline training sessions were held for the instructors and interviewers. The final sample contains data from 1003 persons based on face-to-face interviews. The rejection rate was 27%. After the survey, the starting points and the routes (87 routes in total) were checked and a telephone check was also carried out.

After the first round of the survey, it was decided that the relatively low number of potential emigrants would make it problematic to draw statistically valid conclusions (only 8% of the respondents had concrete migration plans for the next two years). Therefore, we organised a second round of surveys, specifically focusing on people who would like to leave Hungary. Hereafter this will be referred to as „*boost sample*”. The advantage of this supplementary sample is that it better reveals the socio-economic characteristics of potential emigrants due to the larger sample size (additional 375 respondents). Its disadvantage is that it is no longer representative of the adult Hungarian population, as it was carried out in municipalities where the representative survey indicated high emigration potential.

2.5.2. MIGWELL survey in Austria

The way the Austrian MIGWELL survey was conducted differed in many details from the Hungarian one. First of all, it was implemented by Triconsult GmbH, formally known as Triconsult Wirtschaftsanalytische Forschung GmbH, a full-service market and public opinion research institute firm, based in Vienna. The fieldwork ran in parallel with the Hungarian one between December 2023 and February 2024.

The quantitative study of not easily approachable social groups demands a special approach. Time and space (centre/intercept point) sampling and chain referral (e.g., snowball/respondent-driven) sampling methods are all commonly-used techniques in migration studies and they represent adequate solutions in exploratory research (Salganik & Heckathorn 2004; McKenzie & Mistiaen 2009; Göncz et al., 2012). Due to the lack of an exhaustive and accessible list that

would make it possible to identify Hungarian-born people in Austria, we have chosen the quota-controlled snowball *sampling*.

Among the potential disadvantages we should mention that snowball sampling, in general, may overestimate the role of members that are better embedded in the community. However, a sufficiently large number of *starting points*, and controlling the length of chains, can assure better sample accuracy. Accordingly, we paid attention to ensure a diverse set of starting points by gender, age, occupation and geographical distribution as well. Eventually, the final sample of 310 respondents was reached from more than 30 different starting points.

Another drawback of snowball sampling is that the final sample is *not representative* of the Hungarian population in Austria as a whole. This was not feasible, both due to the relatively low sample size and the absence of some crucial socio-demographic and socio-economic parameters within the target population. However, we have taken into account the gender breakdown and the age structure of the Hungarian-born population, which is available in the database of Statistics Austria.

Two different data collection methods were used during the *fieldwork*: Computer Assisted Personal Interviewing (CAPI) and Computer Assisted Web Interviewing (CAWI).² In case of the MIGWELL survey, 73% of the respondents (N=226) participated in face-to-face interviews, conducted by professional interviewers specially trained for this exercise, while 27% of the respondents (N=84) filled in a pre-programmed online questionnaire through an individual link. After the survey, the starting points and chains were checked for quality control. After comparing our primary data with the 2016 Hungarian Microcensus for Hungarians in Austria we found that the only significant difference in that in our own survey, those with tertiary education were overrepresented.

Respondents could fill in the questionnaire if they met certain criteria. The following *filter questions* were applied in the survey:

- Age: 18+ years
- Country of birth: Hungary
- Address: having a main or temporary address in Austria
- Duration: living at least for one year in Austria

In the Austrian survey we studied people's material resources, social relationships and other objective factors of well-being. Questions about their migration experiences and further migration intentions (including the option to return to Hungary) were also crucial for specifying

² The EU-SILC also applies a diverse set of interview methods. For instance, in 2022 the distribution of the Austrian respondents by interview mode (HB130) was the following: 49% CAPI, 41% CATI, and 10% CAWI.

sub-samples and acquiring knowledge on the time period for which they plan to stay in Austria. The main focus lied on assessing their pre- and post-migration SWB patterns (in interaction with the material and relational dimensions of well-being), meaning that the interviewees were asked from an ex post perspective. (Among the methodological limitations see Chapter 2.7).

2.6. Methods of quantitative data analysis

2.6.1. Models for satisfaction domains and satisfaction with life

Satisfaction was interpreted as a scale variable, and therefore modelled using linear regression. This choice was based on the experience of the study by Ferrer-i Carbonell and Frijters (2004), which analysed the methodology of satisfaction modelling. Satisfaction dimensions and life satisfaction were first analysed on the full sample. This unweighted sample consisted of a total of 1688 (the two surveys in Hungary and the survey of Hungarians in Austria). The formulae of the models and a summary of their fit can be found in the Appendix. In general, the modelling process examined how individual variables (e.g., gender, education, number of friends) are related to satisfaction in the overall sample. However, we also introduced moderating effects in the models, using interactions. The moderating effect is interpreted in terms of the variable called „Hungarian group”. This variable can take three values: Hungarians who want to stay in Hungary, potential migrants from Hungary and Hungarians living in Austria. This was necessary because it is possible that some of the variables may be inversely related to satisfaction for example in the group of Hungarians who want to stay in Hungary and Hungarians in Austria. Separate models were also run for Hungarians in Austria for each dimension. In these models we included variables specific to this group, such as year of migration, reasons for migration, transnational activity. In these models we also included a moderating effect, the satisfaction before migration. It is possible that, for example, the gender variable is associated with satisfaction differently when the respondent was dissatisfied before migration than when she/he was satisfied before migration.

The interpretation of the models was carried out following the guidance of Arel-Brundock and colleagues (2024), using the `marginalEffects` package. We typically begin our discussion of the relationship of satisfaction with each variable by presenting the model estimates. For example, for women and men, we calculate a mean satisfaction estimates with the associated confidence intervals. However, this is not the basis to find out the relationship between the variable and satisfaction. It is possible that the difference in the mean estimate is caused by one or more other variables. To establish the relationship, we use the average marginal effects and their corresponding confidence intervals. These are obtained in a counterfactual analysis. Let us stick to the gender variable and during this method two values are calculated for each respondent. In one case we convert everyone's gender value to female and in the other to male. Of course, all other variables are controlled, left as they were in the original responses. We then average the differences between the two values to get the average marginal effect. To establish the moderating effect, we examine these average marginal effects separately by Hungarian groups. In the interpretation, the level of significance is set at $p < 0.05$, but in some cases relationships below $p < 0.1$ are also indicated.

2.6.2. Causal model for determining the effect of migration on subjective well-being

Causal analyses have become increasingly popular in the social sciences thanks to the proliferation of various causal inference techniques. To investigate the impact of migration on subjective well-being, the perfect method would be a randomised control trial, of which the only example so far in this field is the study by Stillman and colleagues (2015). Migration experiments raise ethical issues in addition to the obvious financial and material difficulties of implementation. In the absence of RCTs, researchers rely on observational data, longitudinal surveys if available, and cross-sectional surveys as a last resort. Studies looking for causal effects rely mainly on propensity score matching (PSM) in addition to fixed effects and instrumental variables approaches. One of the most important assumptions (exchangeability) for valid causal procedures is that the treated (migrated) and control (stay-at-home) samples are as similar as possible for certain variables. These are the so-called confounder variables, which in this case affect both the intention to migrate and subjective well-being. Such variables could include for example year of birth, gender or education. Pairing on the basis of time-independent variables is preferred, and the inclusion of a variable that reflects post-migration conditions introduces a bias. In this respect, education is an issue, as it could have changed after migration, but since most of the relevant literature includes this variable in the PSM procedure, we have also added it. In addition to the three variables described above (year of birth, gender, education), Erlinghagen (2021) includes retrospective variables that examine marital status and labour market situation before emigration (and matches it with their recently measured counterparts among the stayers). These variables are not available in our own survey, but a retrospective assessment of satisfaction with these objective indicators is. By including them, we argue that unmeasurable objective variables become measurable through these subjective domains. An important assumption is that there should be a relationship between objective variables and domain satisfactions, and therefore we conducted some tests on a sample of Hungarians living in Austria. We found significant relationships between current objective variables and current domain satisfaction, so there is reason to believe that these relationships existed in the past, between pre-migration objective factors and pre-migration subjective domain satisfaction. However, measurement error can also occur for these retrospective subjective variables, as we mentioned in the previous section on the drawbacks of retrospective questions³. Our formulation of the cause-and-effect relationship is illustrated in the following directed acyclic graph (Figure 2).

³ The problem of measurement error may also arise for retrospective objective variables

Figure 2. Causal pathways between “exposure” (green), outcome (blue), measured confounders (grey) and unmeasured confounders (white). In the case of the “treated” migrants some variables refer to their pre-migration measurements.

The PSM procedure and the evaluation of the results were carried out in R using the packages MatchIt⁴, cobalt⁵ and margineffects⁶. For this part of the analysis, we used data from the Hungarian representative and the Austrian snowball survey. We thus tried to match the „treated” individuals in the Austrian survey with control individuals from the Hungarian survey, who does not possess migration intention. The Austrian survey was restricted to those who emigrated after 2017 in the causal modelling, in order to reduce time-induced bias and achieve more robust results.

In the PSM procedure, the „treatment” migration variable was modelled using a logit model, and then paired with the propensity scores of each individual. In the process, individuals who were very similar in terms of variables affecting both migration and subjective well-being were matched into subgroups. Matching was performed using the nearest-neighbours-method, proceeding in random order. Five controls were assigned to a treated person, and control persons could belong to more than one treated person at a time. Pairing could only be performed if the distance between matched individuals was below 0.37⁷ (caliper). Persons excluded from joint support were removed from the analysis. The final data table contained 413 observations, of which 277 were unique observations.

⁴ Ho D, Imai K, King G, Stuart E (2011). “MatchIt: Nonparametric Preprocessing for Parametric Causal Inference.” *Journal of Statistical Software*, 42(8), 1–28. doi:10.18637/jss.v042.i08

⁵ <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/cobalt/index.html>

⁶ <https://marginaleffects.com>

⁷ 0.2 of the standard deviation of the logit of the PS (Austin, 2011)

As Figure 3 shows, the balancing was successful, the variables were previously unbalanced in the original data table, but in the remaining data table the Standardized Mean Differences for all variables except satisfaction with job (0.1012) are all below the conservative limit of 0.1. Using the PSM method, with different matching rules, the average treatment effect (ATE), the average treatment effect in the treated (ATT) and the average treatment effect in the control (ATC) can be calculated. The majority of researchers report ATT in their studies, but due to the removal of observations because of the caliper and common support, only the average treatment effect in the remaining matched sample (ATM) can be calculated in the present case (Greifer, 2022). The ATM effect was modelled using g-computation with cluster-robust (subclass and id based) standard errors. As usual for causal analyses, a sensitivity test was carried out to estimate the risk from unmeasured confounders. For the test we used the `sensemakr`⁸ package.

Figure 3. Love plot of absolute standardized mean differences before and after matching.

2.7. Challenges and limitations

Our method to gather information for the pre-migration well-being is based on the respondent's retrospective perception and compares the respondent's values in 2024 with his/her well-being in the year/weeks before emigration. The advantage of this method is that it is time-saving, inexpensive and simple to measure in questionnaire surveys, and does not require, for example, longitudinal follow-up. However, it has the disadvantages of the embellishing effect of nostalgia, the bias due to justification of migration (lower values may be given for the period before migration) and the fact that, depending on individual characteristics, positive

⁸ <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sensemakr/index.html>

experiences in the past may be over-represented. For example, extroverts may remember more positive influences from the past (Barrett, 1997), while older respondents may describe earlier events in their lives more positively than they actually were (Comblain et al., 2005). The latter may be related to the general „rosy view” bias (Mitchell et al., 1997), which also calls for a more positive perception of past events. Conversely, negative experiences are more quickly forgotten and selective forgetting takes place (DePrince et al., 2012). A challenge to the reliability of retrospective data is the retrieval strategy used by the respondent to recall and judge past memories. Sometimes, even motivated respondents’ efforts do not allow for successful retrieval (Blair & Burton, 1987). In addition, the success of retrieval is also influenced by individual variables such as age or education (Berntsen & Rubin, 2002). However, the accuracy of retrieval in the case of migration is helped by the fact that this process can be considered as a kind of anchor point (Shmotkin, 2005), which occurs at a particularly significant stage in the life course. According to Oberauer and colleagues (2006), people remember events more accurately when they are rare, have serious consequences and are highly emotional and cognitively affective. Migration is certainly such an event. Further distortion may be caused by the fluctuation of subjective well-being prior to migration and the phenomenon that SWB typically declines in the year before emigration. Fredrickson (2000) and Kahnemann and colleagues (1993) also point out that people tend to judge certain past periods by their most intense point of discomfort or their end point. In this case, the retrospective assessment of subjective well-being before migration would be lower than the true one, since the respondent would judge only the last, most negative period. In summary, retrospective SWB assessment can be subject to both positive and negative biases and therefore the limitation of measurement error should be taken into account. Overall, however, retrospective evaluation, although often criticised in SWB studies, is a method frequently used in the absence of other data (e.g., Erlinghagen, 2021; Lundholm & Malmberg, 2006). Highlighting the importance of pre-migration experiences, Tosi and Impicciatore (2022) advocate the inclusion of retrospective questions in cross-sectional surveys. Although this method is far from being an accurate recollection of past experiences, it reflects these experiences well (Tov, 2012). Furthermore, the degree of happiness of an individual in the past and in the present is related. Bontan and Truglia (2011) were the first to describe this relationship, which they termed the „general habituation” channel. According to the model, a greater sense of happiness in the past increases the likelihood of a greater sense of happiness in the present.

In addition to the potential biases posed by retrospective measurement, two limitations should be noted that compromise the validity of the causal analysis on the total Hungarian population living in Austria. One is due to the fact that only those Hungarians in Austria who had lived in Austria for at least one year could be included in the survey. Since we restricted the sample to them in the analysis, the phenomenon of selection bias arises. Another potential bias is non-response bias due to the convenience sample. On the one hand, due to the snowball sampling method, we did not have the same chance of reaching each potential respondent. For example,

those with no Hungarian acquaintances were almost certainly left out. Furthermore, many did not agree to participate in the survey because they were distrustful of the research. As we know that social relationships and trust are also related to life satisfaction, censoring on those could lead to biased estimates.

3. Migration plans and experiences among Hungarians living in Hungary and Austria

3.1. Migration potential in Hungary

Migration potential measures the share of those with the intention to migrate in a society: an indicator of the share of those planning to leave their country for a shorter or longer period (Sik, 2003). It does not account for the actual act of migration but refers to plans, it cannot be used as a direct estimator for migration.

Migration can be considered as an outcome of a decision-making process and grasped through its graduality, starting with the formulation of the intention, through the concrete steps to the realization of migration. Migration intentions represent the early phases of this process where plans might change and only parts of intentions will be realized. Analysing the early phases of this process allows to grasp the main dimensions of selection: the socio-demographic characteristics of these population and their differences in terms of objective and subjective well-being that seem to be an important driver of both intentions and migration itself (Gödri-Feleky, 2017).

Studies linking migration intentions and the actual act of migration and looking at how much previous intentions were realized are scarce. Nevertheless, a previous study found that 17% of migration plans were fulfilled over a 3-year follow-up period (Gödri-Feleky, 2017), and that previous migration plans were statistically significant predictor of actual migration.

As such, the extent of migration potential is largely dependent on the way it is measured: whether plans, intentions, or actual actions taken are considered. Migration potential is measured in Hungary from the early 90s by TÁRKI with questions about planning to go abroad to work for a few weeks, for a few months/years or indeterminately. These results show that the migration potential of the Hungarian population in terms of short- and long-term employment increased during the 2000s compared to the 1990s, it peaked in 2012 (19% expressed any kind of intentions), and it came down to 13% by 2016 (Figure 4). As for who would like to migrate, results from previous research show that it is higher among younger people, with more material and social resources who are also less satisfied, pessimistic, and feel discriminated (Sik & Simonovits, 2002; Sik & Örkény, 2003).

Source: *TÁRKI* Monitor- and „Omnibus” survey, January 1993 – January 2016.

Figure 4. Migration potential in Hungary between 1993 and 2016 (%).

In our project we measured migration intentions in a somewhat different way, following, and aiming to be comparable with the results of the 2016 Hungarian Microcensus. This Microcensus measured migration potential through the question: “Do you plan to move abroad in the next 2 years for work, study or other reasons?” to which respondents could answer “no” (86,5%), “I don’t know” (5,7%) or “yes” (6,3%). In order to nuance and better grasp the graduality of intentions to move, in our study we asked additional questions about whether one has ever thought about moving or whether one would like to live abroad. The migration potential in Hungary in 2016 was 6,3%, if we narrow the population to 64 years or younger, taking out older generations less likely to migrate, 8,4% of the population are planning to move abroad. This indicator is very much in line with what was measured in our representative survey in 2023: 8,3% (Figure 5). Migration intentions in a wider sense, i.e. migration inclinations or positive attitudes towards migration concern 23-25% of the population.

In order to increase our sample size and be able to analyse people with migration intentions we relied on a boost sample as well complementing our representative sample. People recruited in this part of the survey have either ever thought about moving or expressed a like towards moving abroad. 62% of them plan to move within 2 years.

Figure 5. Migration intentions in Hungary in 2016 and 2023 (%). Source of data: Hungarian Microcensus 2016, MIGWELL surveys. Own figure.

As far as the sociodemographic characteristics of those who intend to migrate previous studies have already confirmed that migration potential is higher among more educated younger men from urban areas (e.g., Sik, 2018). Our results indeed confirmed these findings – a detailed overview will be presented in the upcoming chapters.

3.2. The attitudes toward emigrants

Attitudes towards immigrants has amply dealt with in previous research, however, attitudes towards emigrants or emigration in general might also be an indicator of the context, being supportive or hostile, and has an impact on plans to migrate. It has already by demonstrated that the support of the immediate relations of a person has an influence on migration plans, nevertheless, general attitudes of the overall population has not been considered so far, according to our knowledge.

When asked to rate the seriousness of different social problems, those planning to migrate and those not are in understanding in terms of the order of these problems: inflation, corruption, poverty, and the state of the health care system are considered as the most important problems Hungary faces, followed by the state of the education system, while emigration and integration of immigrants are viewed as being second order problems. Those planning to migrate themselves, however, consider these problems as being more important than their counterparts not willing to move (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Perception of the seriousness of different social problems (mean values on a 0-10 scale, where 0 means not at all serious and 10 means very serious). Source of data: MIGWELL surveys. Own figure.

Mirroring the research tradition that measures attitudes towards immigrants we formulated and tested a few statements regarding the perception of emigration and emigrants. Not surprisingly, those planning to migrate have a more positive attitude towards emigration, however, the general attitudes are rather positive as well. Nearly all with migration intentions agree (98-99%), at least to some extent, that every person has the right to choose the country where he or she gets to thrive, that the right to move freely within the EU is a good thing, and that a stay abroad offers many new opportunities for children. The majority of the general public was also positive about these statements (85-88%). People were slightly less sure about whether moving abroad bring money and experience back home, but still very positive in this respect 75% of the general population and 91% of those planning to migrate agreeing with the statement. Negative symbolic messages that one might encounter in the media such as people emigrating would let the country down was rejected by the majority, 71% of not planning to migrate and 99% of those with migration intentions disagreeing with the statement (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Attitudes towards emigrants, agreement with statements (%). Source of data: MIGWELL surveys. Own figure.

Nevertheless, more pragmatic implications of moving abroad, the idea that those who graduated in Hungary should pay back the cost of their degree if they move to work abroad, generated more polarized opinions. Whereas those planning to migrate clearly rejected the idea (82%), the general population remained divided on the matter with 42% of them agreeing and 57% rejecting the idea.

3.3. Migration plans in Hungary

In the followings plans and details of the planned migration are going to be presented among those having the intention to migrate (among those planning to migrate in the following 2

years). As already mentioned, intentions to move to another country do not necessarily mean that these intentions will be realized. Intentions might differ in terms of their seriousness and about the kind of migration one would like to realize. Indeed, in our survey, 41% of those with migration intents are still only considering the possibility, 45% of them are seriously considering the idea, whereas 9% have already made the decision and only 5% have already taken concrete steps to organize their move. These concrete steps primarily consist in gathering information through contacts (59% of those having taken concrete steps) and internet (40%), and engaging in actual job search (32%). The length of the planned stay is between 2 and 5 years for one third of those planning to migrate, whereas 28% of them would even consider never to return (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Migration plans and planned length of stay among those with migration intentions (%). Source of data: MIGWELL surveys (those planning to migrate in the following 2 years – representative and boost sample combined). Own figure.

In line with previous studies, the main destinations of Hungarians are Austria and Germany, 43-43% mentioned these countries among the three they would consider to move to, the third main destination is the UK with one quarter of those with migration aspiration mentioning it. Another 10% of them would go to the Netherlands, Switzerland and eventually the USA as the only destination outside Europe (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Destination countries among those with migration intentions (%). Source of data: MIGWELL surveys (those planning to migrate in the following 2 years – representative and boost sample combined). Own figure.

As for the purpose of the intended migration, 99% of the people would move to another country to work – 70% of them would accept to work even in a field other than their original profession and 56% would accept to work below their level of qualification. Besides of working (several answers were possible), 19% would like to learn a foreign language and another 7% would like to study abroad – 25% at a graduate level and 31% in a professional education (Figure 10).

Interestingly, only 27% speak the language of the country of their first choice at a level to be able to have a conversation, 43% have only basic language knowledge while 29% do not speak at all the language, but the lack of language skills does not seem to dissuade them.

Figure 10. Destination plans among those with migration intentions (%). Source of data: MIGWELL surveys (those planning to migrate in the following 2 years – representative and boost sample combined). Own figure.

Persons with the intention to move to another country could indicate 3 reasons or objectives for their migration intent. The primary reason to planning to migrate are financial ones, with the majority, 83%, mentioning it (Figure 11). Other important reasons seem to be a quest for a more predictable future abroad mentioned by 52%, and better work conditions mentioned by 45%. Another 29% mentioned that migration would financially secure their future in Hungary (e.g., starting a family, building a house, starting a business in Hungary). Migrating to join family members, friends etc., for professional reasons (to advance one’s career or to gain professional experiences abroad), or to have access to better public services was also mentioned by 7-13%, while public safety or political reasons were also mentioned by a few.

Figure 11. Reasons to migrate among those with migration intentions (%). Source of data: MIGWELL surveys (those planning to migrate in the following 2 years – representative and boost sample combined). Own figure.

More than one third of those planning to migrate (38%) would move alone, while half of them (53%) would migrate with their partner and 29% with their child (Figure 12). However, regardless of whether one would move alone or with others a great majority of them (93%) have the support of their immediate environment, family and friends, and about 43% feel strongly supported in their eventual decision to move which is an important factor in a successful migration. As shown in Chapter 3.2 the general perception of emigration in Hungary is not negative whereas one’s immediate micro-level environment is very positive towards such decisions.

Figure 12. With whom they are planning to migrate (%). Source of data: MIGWELL surveys (those planning to migrate in the following 2 years – representative and boost sample combined). Own figure.

3.4. The Hungarian-born population in Austria: an overview

The second deliverable of the MIGWELL project provided a detailed analysis of the international migration patterns in and between Hungary and Austria (Németh et al., 2022). In this subchapter we would like to summarize only the most important demographic features and spatial patterns of the Hungarian population stock in Austria

According to the official statistics altogether 94,717 Hungarian-born people lived in Austria on the 1st of January 2024. About 86% of them have Hungarian citizenship, however only three-fourth of the Hungarian nationals were born in Hungary. The human sex ratio is slightly biased toward the female sex with about 85 males per 100 females. Women outnumber men in all age groups above the age of 20. The age-sex pyramid of Austrian-born individuals exhibits an “urn” shape, whereas the age-sex pyramid of Hungarian-born individuals displays a “diamond” shape, a pattern also common among immigrant populations (Figure 13).

Figure 13. Population pyramid of the Austrian-born (left) and the Hungarian-born people (right) living in Austria, 2022. (The scales are different). Source: Statistics Austria. Own figure. Blue: males, Pink: females.

Over the past two decades, the spatial distribution of the Hungarian-born population in Austria has undergone significant changes. Although Vienna experienced the largest absolute increase – rising by 2,000 individuals between 2002 and 2011, and by nearly 11,000 more by 2024 – the capital now accounts for a smaller proportion of the Hungarian-born population compared to the early 2000s. In 2002, nearly three-fourths of Hungarian-born residents lived in Vienna, Lower Austria, and Burgenland. Today, only about half reside in these eastern provinces. This shift is largely attributable to the rapid growth of Hungarian populations in other federal provinces, particularly Upper Austria (from approximately 3,000 to 15,000), Styria (from around 3,000 to 11,000), Salzburg, and Tyrol (each increasing from about 1,000 to 7,000) between 2002 and 2024 (Figure 14-15).

Figure 14. The share of Hungarian citizens in the Austrian municipalities by 2011 and 2022. Source: Statistics Austria

Figure 15. The Hungarian-born population according to the regions of Austria, 2002-2024Source: Statistics Austria. Own figure.

3.5. Motivations of migration to Austria

The leading reason for migrating to Austria is related to material well-being, with 57.5% of respondents citing financial motives (Figure 16). The second most popular answer is a more predictable future (39.4%), while the third is better working conditions (37.4%). Reasons that also exceeded 10% include education (25.2%), social relationships (19.4%), and helping their future back in Hungary (planned return) (11.6%). Political reason was mentioned by 8.1% of respondents.

No statistically significant relationship at the $p < 0.1$ level can be shown between the six most common reasons for migration and gender. The largest differences appear for financial reasons (69.2% among men, 53.3% among women) and better working conditions (42.1% among men, 32.9% among women). However, an individual’s current level of education shows a relationship with financial reasons (χ^2 : 12.43, $p=0.006$), reasons related to education (Fisher’s exact test, $p < 0.001$), and reasons connected to helping their future back in Hungary (Fisher’s exact test, $p=0.014$). Financial motives are most common among those with vocational qualifications (72.5%), but also high among those with only primary education (68.8%) (compared to 57.9% for secondary school graduates and 47% for university degree holders). The same trend is characteristic of the motive of helping their future back in Hungary at a later stage. This reason is most common among those with primary education (25%) and vocational qualifications (18.8%). For education, however, the trend is reversed: higher values appear among secondary school graduates (35.5%) and university degree holders (28.2%).

The presence of financial motives also shows a relationship with age ($W = 9866$, $p = 0.017$), as do better working conditions ($W = 12878$, $p = 0.03$) and reasons related to education ($W = 3873$, $p < 0.001$). When financial motives are present, the median age is 40, compared to 37 when they are absent. Better working conditions are likewise more typical among older respondents (median 39 years vs. 37 years when absent), whereas education-related reasons are characteristic of younger individuals (median 25 years vs. 42 years when absent). The education-related reason ($W = 11494$, $p < 0.001$) also shows a relationship with the year of migration, as does the relationship-related reason ($W = 9337.5$, $p = 0.003$). When education-related motives are present, migration is more recent (median 2018 vs. 2014 when absent); in contrast, relationship-driven migration is more typical of Hungarians who moved abroad earlier (median 2010 vs. 2015 when absent).

Figure 16. Migration motivations of Hungarians residing in Austria. Source: Own figure.

4. The objective factors of well-being among Hungarians living in Hungary and Austria

This chapter presents the general demographic and socio-economic data of our target groups – the Hungarians living in Hungary and Austria – based on the MIGWELL survey conducted in 2024. For Austria, we also show the national averages of the EU-SILC 2022 and, for reference, the data of the native-born population and the immigrant arriving from the “new” EU countries. The aim of this chapter is to collect the most important objective factors that may have an impact on subjective well-being. These objective factors will be compared across different subsamples of the database. The comparative analysis will cover the brief description of the following relations (Figure 17):

- Differences between potential stayers and potential leavers in Hungary.
- Differences compared to the Hungarian average.
- Differences between Hungarians in Austria and Hungarians in Hungary.
- Differences between the Hungarians and the native-born population in Austria, supplemented by the Austrian national averages and the scores for immigrants from the new EU countries.

The in-depth analysis of Relation 1 was the main purpose of the previous MIGWELL Research Report (Németh et. al., 2023). About Relation 5 we will write in more details in Chapter 9.

Figure 17. Overview chart of the comparative analysis based on the logical structure presented in Figure 1. Source: Own figure.

It is important to emphasise that the results of the Hungarian MIGWELL survey are representative of the total adult population in Hungary. However, for potential migrants, an additional survey was needed to achieve an adequate sample size. Therefore, the subgroup of potential migrants is not a representative sample. In Austria, the nationally aggregated data from EU-SILC 2022 are representative of the total adult population. For methodological reasons, statistical representativeness cannot be ensured after the breakdown by country of birth. For more details, see chapter 2.5.

4.1. Demographic and spatial characteristics

In Hungary, the sex ratio of potential stayers is exactly the same as the national average (47% male, 53% female), but the opposite is true for potential emigrants, where 53.2% are male. Of all the subgroups studied, the highest proportion of men is found here.

Since the gender breakdown and the age structure of the Hungarian-born population was available in the database of Statistics Austria, we could take this information into consideration during the survey sampling. The 54% female surplus of Hungarians in Austria is smaller than for immigrants from the new EU countries, but higher than the Austrian average and also compared to the native-born population (51-51% in both cases) (Figure 18).

Figure 18. The share of people by gender in Hungary and Austria by analytical subgroups. Source of data: EU-SILC 2022, MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Based on our survey, Hungarians in Austria have a younger age composition in general than the other subgroups in the EU-SILC 2022 database (Figure 19). The average age of the respondents in the MIGWELL survey was 38 years, compared to the average age in Austria of 49 years. Figure 19 shows only one younger subgroup: those planning to emigrate from

Hungary are on average 35 years old, which is significantly lower than both those planning to stay (49 years) and the national average (48 years). This is not surprising given that international migration participants are typically young adults in their 20s and 30s (Fassmann et al., 2017; Tálas, 2020: 73).

Figure 19. Age distribution of people in Hungary and Austria by analytical subgroups. Source of data: EU-SILC 2022, MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

The MIGWELL survey in Hungary was representative of the geographical distribution too; however, spatial representativeness is not true in the case of potential migrants after the additional data collection phase. In Hungary the proportion of potential stayers is almost exactly the same as the national proportion. Respondents living in Pest County and the Southern Greater Plain region are slightly over-represented among the potential emigrants.

In Austria, the EU-SILC data are representative of the total adult in general but statistical representativeness cannot be ensured on subnational level, particularly after the breakdown by country of birth. In comparison with the spatial distribution of the Hungarian population in Austria (Chapter 3.4), Vienna and Styria are slightly overrepresented in the MIGWELL sample, while other regions are slightly underrepresented. (However, the difference is typically smaller than one percentage point) (Figure 20).

Figure 20. The share of people by NUTS2 regions in Hungary and Austria by analytical subgroups. Source of data: EU-SILC 2022, MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

In terms of the degree of urbanisation, there is a significant difference between potential migrants and those who intend to stay. 37% of those who plan to leave Hungary would migrate from low and 33% from high population density settlements, i.e., typically from villages or large cities. These proportions are only around 30% and 17% for those intending to stay. A fifth of Hungarians in Austria did not give a specific settlement name, so no data are available for this variable. However, it can still be concluded that they are basically urban dwellers, similar to immigrants from the new EU countries. While EU-SILC data show that 45% of the native-born population live in low-density settlements, only 19% of Hungarian respondents do (Figure 21). From the above we can also conclude that a significant proportion of Hungarian migrants not only cross an international border but also start a new life in a big city, coming from a rural environment. This change in lifestyle alone can have an impact on subjective well-being.

Figure 21. The share of people by the degree of urbanisation of their place of residence in Hungary and Austria by analytical subgroups. Source of data: EU-SILC 2022, MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

4.2. Financial situation

In order to outline the context, we need to draw attention to changes in the national averages of certain macro-level indicators.

According to the 2013 EU-SILC survey, the *personal incomes* in Austria were three times higher on average than in Hungary (ca. 27,300 EUR vs. 7,600 EUR). Regarding the median values, the difference was similar: ca. 22,000 EUR in Austria and 6,600 EUR in Hungary. This income gap has narrowed in the 2018 and 2022 EU-SILC wave; the mean and median values then displayed “only” a 2.3-fold difference between the two countries (ca. 27,600 and 22,800 EUR vs. 12,200 and 10,600 EUR) (Table 5). In terms of *equivalised disposable household income*, one can observe similar trends: the average and median values of the income level showed a 2.3-fold and 2.4-fold difference in favour of Austria, respectively.

	Austria			Hungary		
	2013	2018	2022	2013	2018	2022
Mean	27,326	28,603	27,599	7,627	9,827	12,216
Median	22,070	23,671	22,780	6,600	8,520	10,644

Table 5. Average total personal income in Austria and Hungary (yearly, gross, EUR/per capita), considering all types of incomes and benefits, adjusted for PPP and inflation, and standardized to 2022 local currency units using the corresponding official HICP indexes. Source of data: *Eurostat microdata*. Own table.

The at-risk-of-poverty rate is a relative measure indicating the proportion of individuals whose equivalised disposable income (after social transfers) falls below the at-risk-of-poverty threshold, defined as 60% of the national median equivalised disposable income after social transfers. This methodological approach explains why the proportion of people living below the at-risk-of-poverty threshold is similar in the two countries. In Austria, approximately 13% of the population falls into this category, compared to 12% in Hungary, with these rates remaining remarkably stable over time.

In 2013, the share of materially deprived individuals was relatively low in Austria, at just 4%, and dropped further to 2% by 2022. In contrast, over a quarter of Hungary’s population (26%) faced material deprivation in 2013. The subsequent decline to 9% highlights a significant improvement in living standards in Hungary.

Low work intensity, which measures the proportion of individuals aged 0–59 living in households where adults worked less than 20% of their total potential working time in the previous year, remained relatively stable in Austria at around 5%. In Hungary, this indicator fell significantly from approximately 9% in 2013 to 4% in 2018 but experienced a slight uptick by 2022.

Finally, we examined the proportion of individuals for whom debt repayment – excluding mortgage or main dwelling-related loans – constitutes a financial burden. In 2022, those without such debts represented around 79% of the population in Austria and 80% in Hungary. However, debt repayment challenges persist for about 3% of Austrians and 5% of Hungarians.

Based on the experience of the cognitive interviews, it has become clear to us that when asking about personal and household income, it can be problematic to get the specific amount. The sensitivity of the topic is only one of the main reasons. It is a difficult task for respondents to add up the income of different members of the household, especially if some members are paid in HUF and others in EUR. This took an unrealistically long time during the cognitive interviews and clearly increased the risk of non-response. We therefore decided to treat the data on income as a categorical variable in both countries. (For this reason, of course, we had to reclassify the EU-SILC variables too.) Even so, 17.5% and 35.1% of respondents in Hungary did not answer our questions on personal and household income respectively. For Hungarians in Austria, the refusal rates were much lower, at 8.7% and 4.8% respectively.

The income distributions of potential emigrants in Hungary are basically the same as the national average (Figure 22). However, the (non-representative) sample of potential emigrants shows some interesting differences. If we exclude those who refused to answer, the share of people with a net income of HUF 200,000 or less is much lower among potential emigrants (18.8%) than among those who want to stay (33.5%) and the Hungarian national average (34.9%). Medium income earners (201-500 thousand HUF) account for 70.3% of those planning to emigrate, compared to 58% for potential stayers and 55% for the national representative sample. At the same time, the share of high-income earners (above HUF 500,000) varies within a very small range (between 4.1% and 4.8%). In summary, it can be said that it is not the poorest and not the wealthiest who typically want to emigrate from Hungary, which is consistent with the general "migration hump" theory (Zelinsky, 1971).

Figure 22. Personal incomes in Hungary by analytical subgroups (monthly, net, HUF). Source of data: MIGWELL survey. Own figure.

Household data also show a similar pattern. While one in three households with no intention to migrate is low-income (33.6%, maximum 400,000 HUF), this proportion among potential migrants is only 16%. The proportion of households with an income above 1 million HUF is very low in both subgroups (3-5%). 4 out of 5 households planning to emigrate can be considered as medium income, i.e., between 400,000 and 1 million HUF (Figure 23).

Figure 23. Household incomes in Hungary by analytical subgroups (monthly, net, HUF). Source of data: MIGWELL survey. Own figure.

Hungarians in Austria are clearly under-represented among those with a monthly income above 3,500 EUR (Figure 24). Excluding those who refused to answer, only 6.8% of respondents belong to this group. This is closest to the 10.5% of immigrants from the new EU countries; and there is a remarkable gap compared to the native population (25.6%). At the same time, the low-income group, i.e., those with a monthly income of up to 1,600 EUR, is relatively low (26.1% - compared to the Austrian average of 31.6%). This is mainly due to the relatively low inactivity rate and high employment rate among Hungarians in Austria. (It is important to underline again that this indicator includes all types of income, e.g., pensions, social benefits, etc.) The above shows that the middle-income group (1,600 - 3,500 EUR) is strongly over-represented among Hungarians in Austria, with a share of 59%, compared to 37-39% for all other groups surveyed.

Figure 24. Personal incomes in Austria by analytical subgroups (monthly, net, EUR). Source of data: EU-SILC 2022, MIGWELL survey. Own figure.

The graph of household income for Hungarians in Austria is meaningless. Half of the respondents indicated that they currently have no household income at all. This is clearly not a true reflection of reality, as almost everyone had a personal income (see the previous graph), and everyone is a member of a household. There are two possible explanations of this phenomenon. On the one hand, as mentioned earlier, respondents may have had difficulty adding up the incomes of different household members. On the other hand, although the concept of household was explained in a separate paragraph in the questionnaire, it was clearly still a problem for many respondents to define the composition of the household in practice. Many are transnational migrants and may have been uncertain about whether or not to include family members living in Hungary in the household. (We specifically asked them about the income of the household in Austria, and in such a case they would have had to define themselves as a

single person household.) Therefore, about half of the respondents were more likely to avoid answering by choosing the "no income" option.

As the previous graphs show, the income distribution of the Hungarian households in Austria is probably similar to that of immigrants from the new EU countries. In their case, most households fall within the range of 2,200 – 3,500 EUR in terms of monthly income, while the native-born population has a much higher proportion of households with an income between 5,000 – 8,000 EUR.

Figure 25. Household incomes in Austria by analytical subgroups (monthly, net, EUR). Source of data: EU-SILC 2022, MIGWELL survey. Own figure.

„Severe material deprivation” is a Eurostat indicator that refers to the proportion of the population that cannot afford at least 4 out of 9 predefined material items considered by most people to be desirable to lead an adequate life. The list includes the inability “to pay unexpected expenses, afford a one-week annual holiday away from home, a meal involving meat, chicken or fish every second day, the adequate heating of a dwelling, durable goods like a washing machine, colour television, telephone or car, being confronted with payment arrears (mortgage or rent, utility bills, hire purchase instalments or other loan payments)”.⁹ In the MIGWELL

⁹ It was one of the components that defined the at-risk-of-poverty-or-social-exclusion rate (AROPE) according to the Europe 2020 strategy. Later the number of predefined deprivation items increased from 9 to 13 in the Europe 2030 strategy. The new items are the following: capacity to replacing worn-out furniture, replacing worn-out clothes by some new ones, having two pairs of properly fitting shoes (including a pair of all-weather shoes) and spending a small amount of money each week on him/herself. For the sake of data comparability, we refer to the older definition of material deprivation in this Report. See more details:

survey we asked the same standardised questions on household capabilities, and the results are shown in Figures 26 and 27.

It is a remarkable contradiction that, although the financial situation of potential migrants is objectively somewhat better than that of potential stayers (Figure 22), they feel they can only cover their everyday expenses with minor or major difficulties. This was the response of 73.5% of potential migrants, which is much higher number than both the response of potential stayers and the national average (55%). For the other variables, there are no significant differences between the analysed subgroups in Hungary. In fact, some statistics show a more favourable picture for potential emigrants: for example, a higher proportion of them can afford to buy quality food and more of them can keep their homes sufficiently warm.

Hungarians in Austria perceive their financial situation better in all aspects of the survey. The difference is significant for two variables in particular. Only 27% of the respondents in Austria said that they can cover usual expenses with some or major difficulties. Almost 90% of the Hungarians in Austria can afford at least one week's holiday a year, compared to 50-52% in the Hungarian subgroups (Figure 26c).

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Glossary:Material_deprivation and https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Living_conditions_in_Europe_-_material_deprivation_and_economic_strain.

a: cover usual expenses

b: face unexpected expenses (1,290 EUR in Austria, 120,000 HUF in Hungary)

c: afford paying for one week annual holiday away from home

d: being confronted with payment arrears (on mortgage or rental payments, utility bills, hire purchase instalments or other loan payments)

e: afford a meat, chicken, fish or vegetarian equivalent every second day

f: keep home adequately warm

Figure 26. Household capacity to... Source of data: EU-SILC 2022, MIGWELL survey. Own figure.

As far as household possessions are concerned, there are negligible differences between the analytical subgroups in Hungary. A slightly higher percentage of potential migrants have access to the internet and a car compared to the national average; these are important prerequisites for the planned intensification of spatial mobility. The penetration of ICT among Hungarians in

Austria is almost 100%. However, relatively fewer people have a car, a television and a washing machine than those surveyed in Hungary, but this is rarely because they cannot afford them. The MIGWELL survey specifically asked about electronic devices owned by households in Austria. Some of the Hungarians living a transnational life regularly "commute" between their household in Hungary and in Austria, so they do not always need, for example, a washing machine. And 60% of those without a car live in Vienna, where the advanced public transport makes expensive car maintenance unnecessary in everyday life.

Figure 27. Assets the households have for personal use by analytical subgroups. Source of data: EU-SILC 2022, MIGWELL survey. Own figure.

4.3. Economic status and job

Since the MIGWELL project aims to study the SWB – migration nexus from a micro-perspective, instead of using aggregated macro-data, we focus on the individual level. These objective, personal attributes are directly related to people’s satisfaction with their jobs, and they also affect people’s subjective well-being as a whole. However, according to the OECD How’s Life Report (2013: 29) there are very few reliable and internationally comparable databases on employment quality. Therefore, beside the available information from the EU-SILC dataset on people’s self-defined current economic status, occupation and highest level of education (Németh et al., 2023), in the MIGWELL surveys we had the opportunity to include further questions as well. Overqualification, the duration of employment contract and the opportunity to move up to a higher position or to have more autonomy at the workplace are indicators aiming to grasp employment quality better.

In the representative Hungarian MIGWELL survey the share of people with primary education is 23.6%, 55% with secondary education and 21.5% with tertiary education (Figure 28). Among the subgroups of potential stayers and potential migrants the secondary education level is more typical, for instance 4 out of 5 people planning to emigrate belong to this category. Only 5% of potential migrants have a primary education, while the share of people with tertiary education is close to the national average (17%).

According to 2022 EU-SILC data, Austria has a lower share of people with a primary education level (18%) and a higher share with a higher education (30%) than Hungary. This is true for native-born people and even more so for the immigrants from the new EU countries, including Hungarians.

According to the 2016 Microcensus, the share of Hungarians with a primary education among Hungarian employees residing permanently in Austria was 5% and the share of those with a tertiary education was 25% (17% for men and 32% for women; Horváth 2022, 118). This may be partly explained by the slight female overrepresentation in the sample, as they have a higher proportion of graduates, and may also be a consequence of snowball sampling, but it may indicate a real change compared to the estimation eight years ago. (It is worth noting, however, that the share of people with tertiary education among Hungarians living permanently in other foreign countries was already 33.6% in 2016 - Horváth 2022, 116.)

Figure 28. The share of people by the highest level of education by analytical subgroups. Source of data: EU-SILC 2022, MIGWELL surveys. Own figure.

In Hungary, the distribution of those planning to emigrate by economic status is radically different from the distribution of the representative national sample (Figure 29). 84.5% of potential emigrants are employees, compared to 54.9% in the national sample and 57.1% for potential stayers. There are very few retired people among them and the self-employed rate is also lower than the national average. In contrast, the proportion of unemployed persons and students is higher.

In Austria, the self-employed category is missing in the EU-SILC database. Nevertheless, it can be seen that the share of employed persons is roughly the same as in Hungary, but with a relatively higher share of students and pensioners. For immigrants from the new EU Member States, the size of the economically inactive population is much smaller than the Austrian average (27% and 35% respectively). In the non-representative Hungarian sample obtained by the Austrian MIGWELL survey, students were over-represented, accounting for 13% of the respondents compared to the national average of 6%. This is to some extent a consequence of snowball sampling. The high proportion of employees is not surprising, however, given the generally young age composition of Hungarians in Austria, many of whom are target earners (see the MIGWELL Research Report Nr. 2.1: Németh et al., 2022).

Figure 29. The share of people by current economic status by analytical subgroups. Source of data: EU-SILC 2022, MIGWELL surveys. Own figure.

There are no significant differences between the Hungarian subgroups compared to the national sample. However, the proportion of both the highest prestige occupations (managers, professionals, technicians and associate professionals: 16.7% in total compared to 19.6% in the national sample) and low prestige occupations requiring no qualifications (6% compared to 13.5% in the national sample) is slightly lower among those planning to emigrate. The other ISCO categories – with the exception of skilled agricultural, forestry and fishery workers – are over-represented among potential emigrants. In particular, clerical support workers and service and sales workers have a strong migration intention: they account for 43% of all potential emigrants.

The share of people having the highest-prestige occupations (managers, professionals, technicians and associate professionals) is the highest among the Austrian-born analytical subgroup (43.7% after excluding the non-respondents) (Figure 30). For immigrants from the new EU Member States and the Hungarians it is 26.6% and 31.5% after excluding the non-respondents. This is much higher than what Horváth found (2022: 120) on the basis of the 2016 Hungarian Microcensus (17%). By contrast, the MIGWELL survey slightly underestimated the categories of "craft and related trades workers" and "plant and machine operators, and assemblers" (15.4% compared to 23% in the Microcensus), and this is particularly true for elementary occupations (9% compared to 20% in the Microcensus). The largest group size is service and sales workers: about one third of respondents belong to this category, compared to only one in five nationally. This figure is consistent with Horváth's findings, who calculated that 31% of Hungarians in Austria could be classified in this category in 2016. In summary, the

non-representative MIGWELL survey in Austria presumably reached a higher proportion of higher-skilled Hungarians than lower-skilled ones.

Figure 30. The share of people by the International Standard Classification of Occupations (ISCO 08) by analytical subgroups. Source of data: EU-SILC 2022, MIGWELL surveys. Own figure.

A comparison of the distributions by educational attainment and current occupational structures reveals a significant presence of overeducated Hungarians in Austria – a phenomenon that is not new. Drawing on data from the 2016 Hungarian Microcensus, Horváth (2022, 118) found that approximately one-third of Hungarians in the Austrian labour market were employed in positions below their level of education. This issue was particularly acute among mothers with children left behind in Hungary, 85% of whom were working in roles that did not match their qualifications (Horváth 2022, 136–137). Similar findings emerged from the 2024 MIGWELL survey: excluding respondents who refused to answer, 30% of Hungarians in Austria identified themselves as overqualified for their jobs (Figure 31).

Figure 31. Overqualification. (“Compared to your level of education (primary, secondary or tertiary), what kind of work are you doing in Austria?”). Source of data: EU-SILC 2022, MIGWELL surveys. Own figure.

Figure 32. Number of working hours per week by analytical subgroups. Source of data: EU-SILC 2022, MIGWELL surveys. Own figure.

There is little difference between subgroups in terms of the duration of the employment contract (Figure 33). The proportion of Hungarian respondents in Austria with a fixed-term employment contract is slightly higher (14%) than in Hungary (7-8%). About 5% of respondents stated that they are currently working without an official work contract. In reality, this is probably higher, but on the one hand not everyone dares to admit this in survey, and on the other hand, as seen above, the MIGWELL survey could reach relatively few people with elementary occupations.

(According to the empirical experience, this situation is most common in agriculture or construction).

Figure 33. Duration of employment contract by analytical subgroups. Source of data: EU-SILC 2022, MIGWELL surveys. Own figure.

Excluding non-respondents, there is relatively little difference between sub-groups in Hungary regarding their perceived opportunities to achieve a higher position at work (Figure 34). Among potential migrants, 29.5% believe that advancing in their job is at least somewhat realistic, compared to 35% of potential stayers. In contrast, the figure is significantly higher among Hungarians in Austria, with 56.6% expressing a similar outlook.

Figure 34. Opportunity to move up to a higher position or to have more autonomy at the workplace by analytical subgroups. Source of data: EU-SILC 2022, MIGWELL surveys. Own figure.

4.4. Housing conditions

In the OECD How's Life framework, housing conditions were captured by three headline indicators: the number of rooms per person, housing costs, and the number of dwellings lacking basic facilities (OECD 2013). Since the lack of basic facilities does not pose a widespread problem in Hungarian and Austrian households, we focus on the reported housing problems which directly affect people's satisfaction with their housing situation.

As the previous MIGWELL Research Report pointed out (Németh et al., 2023: 40-41), respondents in Hungary more frequently reported different types of internal housing problems. According to the EU-SILC, leaking roof, rot in window frames and floor, damp walls/floors or foundation (22% vs. 10%), and dark rooms (8.5% vs. 5.5%) were almost twice as frequent in Hungary as in Austria. On the other hand, the external negative factors, such as noise from the streets, crime and vandalism in the area, pollution, filth, and other environmental problems seem to be stronger in Austria (Figure 35).

Considering the analytical subgroups of this Research Report, the housing problems are rated slightly worse by potential emigrants in all the aspects examined. In particular, there is a significant difference in the level of noise from neighbours and from the street. However, this can be explained by the fact that the non-representative sample of potential emigrants includes a higher proportion of people living in densely populated settlements (see Chapter 4.1) and are therefore more likely to encounter this problem.

It is also interesting to note that, compared to the Hungarian population, some problems are less frequent in the neighbourhoods where Hungarian households in Austria live (e.g., pollution, filth, or other environmental problems), while others are more frequent (e.g., dark rooms, noise from neighbours or from the street). Regarding crime, violence or vandalism, there are no differences between the perceptions of the analysed subgroups; only 4-5% reported that this is a problem in the area they live.

Leaking roof, damp walls/floors/foundation, or rot in window frames or floor:

Too dark, not enough light:

Noise from neighbours or from the street:

Pollution, filth, or other environmental problems:

Crime, violence or vandalism in the area:

Figure 35. Percentage of people living in accommodation with the following housing problem by analytical subgroups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys. Own figure.

Figure 36. Total number of rooms in the dwelling the household lives by analytical subgroups (With the living room but without the kitchen and bathroom. The half-room counts as a room, and the "American kitchen" - living room and kitchen function combined - also counts as a room). Source of data: EU-SILC 2022, MIGWELL surveys. Own figure.

While the representative sample in Hungary found that 86% of people live in own properties (or live with a close relative of the owner, i.e., partner, spouse or child), only 24% of Hungarians in Austria do so (Figure 37). This is not a surprising discrepancy, since, as the expert interviews showed, property prices are much higher in Austria and it is not a realistic objective for most immigrants to accumulate the necessary wealth.

Also not surprisingly, those who do not plan to leave Hungary are slightly more likely to be homeowners than potential emigrants (87% and 81% respectively). On the one hand, buying a house or flat is one of the main drivers for Hungarians wanting to work in Austria. On the other hand, in general, people who rent are characterised by greater flexibility and more active spatial mobility.

The relative majority of Hungarians in Austria rent the whole dwelling (42%), but one in five of those interviewed rent only part of the dwelling. People living in commercial accommodation are typically those who work in a hotel and receive accommodation in that building from their employer (2% in the sample).

Figure 37. Legal relationship to the property by analytical subgroups. (“I am the owner of the dwelling, or its spouse, partner or relative.”). Source of data: MIGWELL surveys. Own figure.

The previous three sub-chapters dealt with the material components of people's well-being. The figure below can in some ways be seen as a summary of these, but rather from the perspective of the respondents, as it was intended to operationalise their perceived social position. We asked the respondents to „imagine a ladder with the upper level representing the upper part of society and the lower level representing the lower part. Where would you currently place yourself on the ladder in Hungary / Austria"?

In Hungary, compared to the national average, the perceived social position of potential stayers was slightly higher (5.4) and that of potential emigrants slightly lower (4.8). This is interesting because the previous chapters have repeatedly shown that the objective financial position of those planning to emigrate is generally not worse than that of those who imagine their future in Hungary. In fact, for some income or housing indicators we even see better values for potential emigrants.

Hungarians in Austria placed themselves on average at 6.6 on this imaginary 0-10 social ladder (Figure 38). Here, we specifically asked them to think about their current position within the Austrian society. (Their previous perceived position before the move, on average, was 6.1 in Hungary). This high score is surprising, because based on the literature we expected that after migration a significant proportion of people would be in a lower social status in their new home country, and this would be reflected in their perceived position as well. Further research is needed to explore the reasons, but their transnational living situation may also have an impact. Many of the Hungarians in Austria are more or less transnational migrants who spend a lot of time in Hungary and very often maintain two addresses or households there. It is possible that this phenomenon obscures – and in a sense makes unnecessary – a realistic assessment of their position within the Austrian society, and that unconsciously people perceive and interpret their

improved living standards in the context of the Hungarian society they also belong to. (For more on migrant transnationalism, see chapter 4.10).

Figure 38. Perceived social position by analytical subgroups. (“Imagine a ladder with the upper level representing the upper part of society and the lower level representing the lower part. Where would you currently place yourself on the ladder in Hungary / Austria?”). Source of data: MIGWELL surveys. Own figure.

4.5. Household composition

The theory called “new economics and sociology of labour migration” (NELM) underlines that migration decisions are usually made by families and households, rather than by isolated individuals (Németh et al., 2023: 34-35).

It was important to ask survey respondents to provide information on the size and composition of their households. In the case of the Hungarian sample, this was done without any problems, but in Austria, there were several complicating factors. We have therefore included a brief clarification (see below) of what the household concept is in general and how it should be interpreted in practice.

„What is a household?

A household is made up of persons who live together in a dwelling or part of a dwelling and share at least part of the household's expenses (e.g. food, daily expenses). Dependent persons are also members of the household.

Many Hungarians living in Austria are members of two households: one in Hungary (often with other members of their family living there) and one in Austria. If this applies to you, please answer the question below accordingly!

Note: If you live with tenants and only pay rent together, this is a one-person household. It is also a one-person household if you live alone, and get accommodation from your employer e.g. in a hotel.”

We are well aware that according to statistical definitions, each individual is assigned to a single household based on their "usual residence," which is typically determined by where they spend the majority of their time.¹⁰ However, field experience has shown that this rigid statistical thinking is sometimes incompatible with the way people – especially transnational migrants – experience this situation in practice. What is more, it does not seem logically justified to separate, for example, a family member working in Austria from his/her household in Hungary just because this person spends most of his/her time as a one-person household in Austria. Since he/she brings a significant part of his/her income back to Hungary – and his/her “left-behind” family members use it to finance their daily expenses – without the person working abroad the income per capita indicator for the Hungarian household would be incorrect. We therefore concluded that in the Austrian MIGWELL survey we leave open the possibility for respondents to belong to two households if they consider this to be true in their own living situation. We asked the following questions about this topic:

- How many people are living in your household in Hungary, if you have any (including you)?
- How many people are living in your household in Austria (including you)?
- Who do you live together in a flat in Austria? You can tick more than one answer. Please also indicate the number of persons in each category! (E.g., how many children under 6 years of age live with you?)

Despite our best efforts, we were unable to construct a reliable profile of these “dual” households, as the provided numbers of persons living in the two households were sometimes mathematically controversial. Nevertheless, the parameters for the Austrian households are still accurate and the existence of a second household in Hungary can be also confirmed.

According to the representative MIGWELL survey, the average number of persons living in a household is 2.7 in Hungary (Figure 39). This value is slightly lower for households of potential stayers and slightly higher for that of potential migrants (2.6 and 2.9 respectively). According to the EU-SILC survey, the average household size in Austria was also 2.7 in 2022. Hungarian households in Austria are slightly smaller not only compared to the native-born population, but also compared to migrants from the new EU Member States (2.3 persons on average).

¹⁰ An example from a publication of the Hungarian Central Statistical Office illustrates this situation. “A husband works in a distant settlement, resides in a worker's accommodation, and spends only the weekends with his family. ... Consequently, the husband is not considered a member of the resident household at the dwelling where the census is conducted. Instead of being classified as a family consisting of a married couple and children, the *household* is recorded as a single-parent family (the wife's marital status is adjusted to "mother"). ... The husband is classified as a resident member of an institutional household as a single individual in the other municipality (KSH 2006: 29).

Figure 39. Household size by analytical subgroups. Source of data: EU-SILC 2022, MIGWELL surveys. Own figure.

21% of the Hungarian respondents in Austria wrote higher than 0 to the question about the household size in Hungary, and 63% answered yes to the question whether they have maintained a registered address in Hungary (either permanent or temporary) (Figure 40). These are clearly indicators of the existence of strong transnational ties, which will be discussed in more detail in Chapter 4.10.

Figure 40. Address in Hungary. Source of data: EU-SILC 2022, MIGWELL surveys. Own figure.

Finally, we asked with whom Hungarians in Austria live in an apartment (not necessarily in the same household). 28% of the respondents live alone, while 72% share an apartment with at least one other person. They most often live together with their partner (59%) and their children (31% in total), but colleagues and friends were mentioned on third place (7.4%) (Figure 41).

Figure 41. Living together in Austria. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys. Own figure.

4.6. Social connections

In our research framework, we take into account other, immaterial measures of quality of life in addition to the material components of well-being covered in the preceding chapters. Included are indicators like social connections and social capital, health condition, work-life balance, and other factors related to the perception of national situation and perspectives, and personal security. In the sections that follow, these aspects of well-being are addressed, presenting both objective and subjective measures.

As well-being and people’s aspirations are always shaped by the social contexts in which they are embedded, we also take into account the relational dimension in our research. This dimension refers to the social relationships that people must be able to enter into in order to meet human needs. It has objective as well as more subjective indicators. Micro-level objective indicators such living with a partner, household size, presence of small children has already been presented in the previous chapter.

In the followings other indicators of the reliability of social connections such as frequency of meeting with family and friends, having someone to discuss personal matters, or access to help (material, non-material) will be presented together with general trust in other people.

Looking at the number of persons with whom one can discuss intimate and personal matters based on our survey results we can see that people with migration intentions have the most connections: only 3% have no one at all, half of them have 3 persons or less while 43% have more than 3 persons to rely one to discuss personal matters (Table 6). In case of Hungarians living in Austria the question was asked separately for Hungary and Austria to grasp the complexity and transnational character of their personal connections. Their separate number of connections in Hungary and Austria follow somewhat similar trend, however, Austrian connections seem to be slightly more important in number: half of them have 1-3 persons in Hungary to rely on, while two third of them have similar number of connections in Austria. They are more to have no one (15%) in Hungary or no one in Austria (9%) seemingly being more isolated.

	General HU 2024	Pot. stayers Representative 2024	Pot. migrants Boost 2024	HU in AT 2024 (friends in Hungary)	HU in AT 2024 (friends in Austria)
No one at all	7.0	5.7	3.0	15.0	9.4
3 persons or less	67.0	67.4	53.6	54.8	65.8
More than 3 persons	23.0	23.8	43.4	23.0	19.7
NA	2.8	3.0	0.0	6.5	5.1

Table 6. Having people (not counting family members) with whom to discuss intimate and personal matters (%) Source of data: EU-SILC 2022, MIGWELL surveys. Own calculation.

Although about half (47.7%) of Hungarians living in Austria stated they have both Hungarians, Austrians and people from other background among their friends, 23.5% of them claimed to have rather Hungarians, and another 20.6% rather Austrians as friends.

Transnational personal connections are also more salient among those who are planning to migrate: while only about half of the Hungarian population have any member of her family or any of her friends and acquaintances living abroad, 83% of those planning to migrate reported such connections (Figure 42).

Figure 42. Percentage of people with any family member, friends or acquaintances living abroad. Source of data: EU-SILC 2022, MIGWELL surveys. Own figure.

Being able (having the time and money) to meet with friends is also an important aspect of social connections. In earlier EU-SILC measurements Austrian respondents seemed to be in a better situation, as nearly everyone (89-90%) said that they were able to get together with friends/family (relatives) for a drink/meal at least once a month. This proportion, although somewhat increasing from 2013 to 2018, was much lower in Hungary (63% in 2018). This difference is partly due to financial deprivation. These tendencies remained stable with 86.7% of Austrians and 62.7% of Hungarians being able to meet with friends in 2022 and 2024. Hungarians with migration intentions, however, started to catch up in this respect to the Austrian level with 70% of them doing so and only 3.7% not being able to afford it, while Hungarians living in Austria follow very similar tendencies (81.6% being able to meet up with friends monthly and only 2.6% not being able to afford it) as the native Austrians with (Figure 43).

Figure 43. Percentage of people meeting friends and family at least once a month. Source of data: EU-SILC 2022, MIGWELL surveys. Own figure.

In terms of trusting other people, there are notable differences (Figure 44). The level of trust is slightly lower in Hungary than in Austria (an average of 5.3 on a 0-10 scale versus 5.8). However, both those planning to migrate and those who have already migrated have a lower level of trust with an average of 4.7 among potential migrants and 5.1 among Hungarian migrants living in Austria. When it comes to trusting people living in one’s neighbourhood, the level of trust is higher than the generalized trust in Hungary (an average of 5.8 on a 0-10 scale), however, the level of trust is lower among potential migrants and Hungarians living in Austria (both 5.1) (Figure 45).

Figure 44. Distribution of trust in other people: on a 0-10 scale. Source of data: EU-SILC 2022, MIGWELL surveys. Own figure.

Figure 45. Distribution of trust in people in one's neighbourhood: on a 0-10 scale. Source of data: EU-SILC 2022, MIGWELL surveys. Own figure.

In line with having someone to discuss personal matters, despite the differences in the frequency of contact with friends and family, a similarly high proportion of respondents in Austria (84%) and Hungary (89%) report that they can ask for help from relatives, friends, or neighbours, which is even higher among potential migrants in Hungary (94%) and Hungarians living in Austria (91%) (Figure 46). Looking at material and non-material help separately it seems that asking for financial help is a more sensitive issue: a somewhat lower share of respondents would be able to ask for it. In the case of Hungarian migrants living in Austria, nevertheless, asking

for non-material help would be the issue as only 58% could ask such thing from relatives, friends, or neighbours (Table 7). It is indeed true for this population that they have their support network both in Hungary and in Austria, and this seems to pose a problem when in need of non-material help, probably necessitating the helper being present.

Figure 46. Percentage of people being able to ask for help from relatives, friends, or neighbours. Source of data: EU-SILC 2022, MIGWELL surveys. Own figure.

	General HU 2024	Pot. stayers Representative 2024	Pot. migrants Boost 2024	HU in AT 2024
Material help	78.8	79.5	87.1	84.5
Non-material help	85.7	86.6	92.3	58.1
Any kind of help	89.0	89.3	94.0	91.3

Table 7. Percentage of people being able to ask for material or non-material help from relatives, friends, or neighbours. Source of data: EU-SILC 2022, MIGWELL surveys. Own calculation.

Beyond people's personal connections, their eventual memberships in associations, creating some kind of embeddedness and network, also affects their quality of life and well-being. In this respect the share of respondents not being a member of any association is an interesting indicator: 75% of Hungarians do not have any kind of such membership, while this lack of engagement is even higher among those intending to migrate (82%), while it is lower among Hungarians living in Austria (68%) (Table 8).

	General HU 2024	Pot. stayers Representative 2024	Pot. migrants Boost 2024	HU in AT 2024
Social, charitable organization	3.3	3.1	0.9	
Church, religious organization	6.6	6.4	4.3	
Party, political organization	1.5	1.4	1.3	
Trade union, employee representation	8.9	9.4	9.0	
Sport, recreation or other cultural association	9.7	8.3	7.3	
Cultural organisation				4.8
Other voluntary organisation	0.8	0.6	0.4	24.8
No membership in any kind of organisation	75.4	76.9	82.0	68.1

Table 8. Membership in voluntary organisations (%). Source of data: EU-SILC 2022, MIGWELL surveys. Own calculation.

4.7. Health status

One of the most significant factors influencing well-being is health, which also has an impact on how well people are able to engage in daily activities that enhance their well-being. Here, we will rely on respondents' self-assessment of their health status and whether they feel that their activities are limited due to health issues in the absence of objective measures of their health condition (information about diseases and conditions causing poor health or disability). By its very nature, self-perceived health measurement is subjective. It is supposed to cover the various aspects of health, such as mental and physical, and focuses on the overall condition of health rather than the specific circumstance.

As already presented in the previous (WP2) report based on 2013 and 2018 EU-SILC data, perceived health is better in Austria than in Hungary. Around 70% of Austrians evaluated their health condition as very good or good, while only about 60% of Hungarians declared the same. Our more recent data confirm these tendencies with 62.6% of the Hungarian sample (in 2024) and 69.8% of the Austrian sample (in 2022) declaring to be in a very good or good health condition. Hungarians who are planning to migrate, however, perceive their health condition much better than the rest (90.6% in a very good or good shape) and 98.3% at least in a fair condition (Figure 47). This seems to be in line with previous empirical results that migrants, and those with migration plans are in better health condition than others also due to the fact that overall, they are younger, or, in a reversed causal logic, people with better health are those that are prone to migrate or consider it. Interestingly, however, this difference is slightly less notable in the case of Hungarian people who have already migrated to Austria. Nevertheless, their perception of their own health condition remains more positive (79.1%) than either the native

Austrian population (70.4%) or immigrants from the new EU Member States living in Austria (65.1%) as measured in the 2022 EU-SILC.

Figure 47. Perceived health. Source of data: EU-SILC 2022, MIGWELL surveys. Own figure.

According to previous, 2013 and 2018 EU-SILC data no notable difference existed between the two countries in terms of the share of people declaring a severe limitation in their activities due to their health condition (around 7-10%), while the share of people declaring to be somewhat limited was slightly less important in Hungary (18-19%) than in Austria (25%). More recent data confirm these tendencies with one third of Hungarians (33.3% in 2024) declaring to be strongly or otherwise restricted due to their health conditions and 28.8% of Austrians in 2022) (Figure 48). In line with previous results, the share of Hungarians with health restrictions among those planning to migrate is much lower, only 7.7%. On the other hand, those Hungarians that have migrated to Austria are rather similar in this respect (26,7% declaring to be severely or otherwise restricted) to either their Austrian counterparts or other immigrants from new EU Member States (28.5%) with slightly less of them being severely restricted (3.5%).

It has to be noted, however, that the differences in the perception of limitations due to health condition might be partly shaped by different cultural contexts, regulations, and institutional and policy approaches in the two countries to the diagnostics and formal acknowledgement of such conditions.

Figure 48. Percentage of people declaring to be strongly or otherwise limited in their everyday activities due to their health condition. Source of data: EU-SILC 2022, MIGWELL surveys. Own figure.

4.8. Work-life balance

Another aspect of the quality of life is work-life balance, in terms of the time one can devote to family life and leisure activities, and how much free time one has beyond working and commuting. In our research it is measured through the working hours, participation in leisure activities and being able to meet with friends.

The landscape of working hours changed somewhat since 2018 in Austria where part-time work became more widespread, while the main tendencies remained similar in Hungary with a dominance of full-time jobs. According to 2022 EU-SILC data the average working hours in Austria is 20.3 while it is 41.1 in Hungary in 2024 according to our survey with potential migrants working slightly more, 42 hours/ week on average. In Austria, indeed, Hungarians work less hours than their non-migrant counterparts, 35.2 hours, which, nevertheless, remain above the Austrian average, including other immigrants from new EU member states (20.1 hours) (Figure 49).

Beyond the differences in terms of working hours there is another, still persisting difference between the two countries in terms of the share of respondents regularly participating in a leisure activity (Figure 50). While 71,7% (in 2022) of respondents in Austria engage in such activities, only 37.6% of Hungarian respondents reported engaging in leisure activities (in 2024). As these activities, such as sport, cinema, or concerts, could entail certain costs (e.g., entrance fees and/or travel costs), this can be an obstacle for some: indeed, a higher share of Hungarian respondents does not participate in such activities because they cannot afford it (18% as opposed to 8% in Austria). Nevertheless, the share of those who do not have regular leisure

activities for other reasons remains significantly higher in Hungary (43.8%) than in Austria (20%). These results seem to be stable over time.

However, Hungarians with migration intention are also people who have more leisure activities: 50.6% of them regularly participate in leisure activities, while the share of those who are deprived because of cost issues are similar to the Hungarian population (17.6%). An even higher share of Hungarians living in Austria engage in such activities (65.5%) although their share remains below the native Austrians. This is especially due to the fact that they can now afford it: only 6.1% said that costs would prevent them to do so.

Figure 49. Total number of working hours per week. Source of data: EU-SILC 2022, MIGWELL surveys. Own figure.

Figure 50. Percentage of people regularly participating in a leisure activity. Source of data: EU-SILC 2022, MIGWELL surveys. Own figure.

4.9. External factors

The quality of the living, working and economic environment directly contributes to quality of life, and their subjective perception is related to subjective measures of well-being. In the following the perception of Hungary’s overall situation and economic context, expectations for the future and trust in institutions will be explored.

The perception of the economic situation in Hungary is by far the worst among those planning to migrate (Figure 51). Whereas 15.6% of the general population think the situation being very bad, 23.6% of potential migrants share the opinion, meaning that negative opinions are not just characterizing half of the population in question but two third of them. Future expectations regarding the country’s economic performance show similar tendencies, potential migrants are the least optimistic: only 5.2% of the latter think that the situation will slightly improve as opposed to 13% among the general population (Figure 52).

Figure 51. Perception of the current economic situation of Hungary (%). Source of data: EU-SILC 2022, MIGWELL surveys. Own figure.

Figure 52. Expectations for the future economic situation of Hungary (%). Source of data: EU-SILC 2022, MIGWELL surveys. Own figure.

The perception of the current situation in Hungary follows similar tendencies: when rated on a 0-10 scale, potential migrants are the least positive with an average of 2,6 as opposed to 3.9 among the general population (Figure 53).

Figure 53. Perception of the current overall situation of Hungary: values on a 0-10 scale. Source of data: EU-SILC 2022, MIGWELL surveys. Own figure.

Trust in institutions is another indicator of the perception of a country’s performance and the overall context. Overall, the most trusted institution in Hungary is the police followed by the legal system in general, the Government, the political system and the Parliament come next while the trust in the media is the lowest. Potential migrants follow similar tendencies, however, at a lower level of trust. The order of trust in Hungarian institutions among Hungarians living in Austria is somewhat different, although the level of distrust is similar to potential migrants. They mostly trust the legal system, while least trust the Government. Trust in Austrian institution, however, is significantly higher in all aspect with the legal system and the media being the mostly trusted (Table 9).

<i>Trust in the...</i>	General HU 2024	Pot. stayers Representative 2024	Pot. migrants Boost 2024	HU in AT 2024 (Hungarian institutions)	HU in AT 2024 (Austrian institutions)
... police?	5.5	5.7	4.5	3.6	6.1
... legal system?	4.9	5.1	4.2	5.2	7.6
... Government?	3.9	4.0	3.0	3.1	5.5
... political system?	3.8	3.9	3.1	3.5	6.4
... Parliament?	3.8	3.9	3.1		
... media?	3.6	3.7	3.1	4.6	7.6

Table 9. Trust in institutions: mean values on a 0-10 scale. Source of data: EU-SILC 2022, MIGWELL surveys. Own calculation.

Compared to the results of the 2016 Microcensus, where 69% of the respondents declared to feel fairly or very safe the situation has improved, according to our survey, 83.6% of Hungarians felt fairly or very (35.6%) safe when walking alone in their area after dark (Figure 54). The share of those feeling very safe (35.6%) is even higher among potential migrants (41.2%) and Hungarians living in Austria (42.3%). However, perception of personal security is more polarized among the latter: feeling a bit unsafe in Austria is at a similar level (10.3%) than among the general Hungarian population (13.6%), both higher than among those planning to migrate (3.9%).

Figure 54. Perceived personal safety. Source of data: EU-SILC 2022, MIGWELL surveys. Own figure.

4.10. Transnational activity

According to Kim and colleagues (2021), transnationalism can be broken down into several dimensions: social ties, transnational family status, cultural ties, economic ties, political ties, transnational attitude and identity, and finally transnational healthcare use. In the MIGWELL project, we mainly focused on social ties, transnational family status and economic ties (Figure 55). Although the EU regulations require the establishment of a residence in only one country at a time, 62.58% of the Hungarians in the sample a Hungarian address. They do so with only 20.65% of the respondents having a household in Hungary. 45.16% of the total sample can therefore be said to have retained their Hungarian address even without having a household in Hungary. It can also be seen that Hungarians in Austria have preserved their social contacts with those who have remained in the home country. Only 15.16% of the sample have no friends in Hungary (and 6.45% did not answer). For those who have no friends in Hungary, the median emigration year is 2010, and this increases with the number of friends (with at least 10 friends the median is 2019). The descriptive data also show some relationship between the number of friends and geographical distance, as only 38.29% of those with no friends live in the three provinces closest to the Hungarian border (Upper Austria, Vienna, Burgenland), while 80% of those with at least 10 friends live in these provinces. Most Hungarians in Austria have 2-4 friends in Hungary (35.48%). 66.77% of respondents can count on material support from Hungary, while 49.67% can rely on non-material support. In terms of visits to Hungary, 1-2 trips home per year are the most common (32.58%), but returning home two or three times a year and every month is also common (20.96% for both). The two extreme response options, returning home several times a month (11.93%) and not visiting home at all (12.9%), have almost the same proportion of answers.

46.77% of respondents send financial support home, while 32.25% do not. The proportion of no answers (20.96%) is particularly high for this variable. Our subsequent analyses have shown that those people have similar attributes to those who send money home, and therefore are likely to be reluctant to take up the truth about sending money home.

Figure 55. Transnational activity of the sample. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys. Own figure.

Those providing financial support to people who stayed in Hungary send home the 10% of their income, based on the median. No gender difference is observed in the percentage of their earnings that they send home (Figure 56). When looking at the respondents' own monthly income (this is a categorical variable, so we used the category midpoint to transform it to a scale variable) and the percentage of remittances sent home together, we find that on average, remitter

Hungarians in Austria send home on average ~€330. By gender, the average for men is €380 and €288 for women.

Figure 56. Percentage of remittance by gender. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys. Own figure.

22.58% of the total sample have a partner or child who is not currently living with him or her (Figure 57). They are identified as having left their child or partner at home in Hungary. Minor differences may exist, for example, if the partner lives in a third country (e.g., Germany) or in another Austrian household, or if the child living outside Austria is an adult (based on the respondents' year of birth, this may only arise in a few cases). Those who has a partner and at least one child and neither of them is living in the same Austrian household as the respondent account for 4.1% of the sample.

Figure 57. Living with partner/child in Austria or leaving them behind. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys. Own figure.

Some of the transnational variables were merged and recoded to binary. Five new variables were created, which are:

- Remittance (1 if he or she remits)
- Visit home (1 if once every 2 - 3 months or more frequent)
- Social ties (1 if the respondent can get material or non-material help from home, or if he or she has at least one Hungarian friend)
- Family ties (1 if he or she has a left-behind partner or child)
- Accommodation (1 if he or she has an address or a household in Hungary)

These variables were summed to form a 0-1-2-3-4-5 transnational activity measure. Most respondents (40.6%) showed transnational activity in three variables. The number of individuals who were transnational in all areas (4.19%) and those who did not show any transnationalism at all (0.9%) was low (Figure 58).

Figure 58. “Transnationalism scores”. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys. Own figure.

We can draw some conclusions about the political attitudes of Hungarians in Austria towards Hungary and their media consumption habits by comparing institutional trust (Figure 59). It can be seen that the vast majority of respondents trust the Austrian media (78.06%) and the Austrian government (77.41%) more than their Hungarian counterparts. A positive comparison in favour of the Hungarian government appears only for 8% of respondents.

Figure 59. Trust comparison between the Hungarian and the Austrian media and government. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys. Own figure.

5. Subjective well-being patterns among Hungarians living in Hungary and Austria

5.1. Overall life satisfaction

Overall life satisfaction is the most frequently used indicator for assessing subjective well-being in large-scale surveys. The question is simple, short, and it can be understood across different countries and populations because it is less dependent on cultural norms (Diener et al., 1985; Veenhoven 1993). Overall life satisfaction, measured on a 0-10 scale, has been always higher in Austria than in Hungary since it is measured. However, the gap has been slightly decreasing since the first round of EU-SILC. The national average was 6.1 in Hungary and 7.8 in Austria by 2013, and these scores increased to 6.9 and 7.9 respectively until 2022.

The representative MIGWELL survey shows an almost identical value (7.0) for the Hungarian population by 2024. The discrepancy between potential migrants and potential stayers is not particularly high; 6.9 for those who plan to leave Hungary and 7.2 for those who don't. In Austria overall life satisfaction reaches the highest score among native-born people (8.0), while immigrants from the new EU Member States are generally less satisfied (7.5). According to our survey, Hungarians in Austria tend to evaluate their lives similarly (7.4). This value is slightly higher than that of all subsamples in Hungary (Figure 60).

Figure 60. Overall life satisfaction by analytical subgroups. Source of data: EU-SILC 2022, MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

5.2. Domain satisfaction

Examining domain-specific factors enables researchers to pinpoint the areas of life that most strongly influence personal subjective well-being. It's crucial to recognize, however, that individuals prioritize different domains depending on their personal circumstances. For instance, work-life balance might play a more significant role in overall SWB for younger people, whereas older generations may place greater emphasis on health issues.

The general 2022 EU-SILC database contains three domain satisfaction variables: respondents' satisfaction with their household's financial situation, their social relationships and the available time for things they like to do (time use). Additionally, the satisfaction with personal income, housing situation and main occupation was also surveyed in Austria. (In the latter case we selected the economically active respondents to get comparable values.) The MIGWELL surveys covered not only these variables, but also people's satisfaction with external factors that were either part of earlier EU-SILC rounds (living environment, green areas) or were considered highly relevant during the narrative interviews (satisfaction with the quality and accessibility of public services).

The items listed in Table 10 can be classified into three main categories: satisfaction with material, non-material and external factors of well-being.

When looking at the primary data for Hungary, the pattern is fairly consistent: the domain satisfaction of potential stayers is slightly higher in most cases (+0.1 or +0.2 surpluses), and that of potential emigrants is lower by -0.2 to -0.9 compared to the national average. The exceptions are satisfaction with personal contacts and green areas, where the differences are negligible between the subgroups studied. For health the relationship is the reverse, with potential emigrants more satisfied with their health status. This is hardly surprising, given the fact that their average age is lower (see Chapter 4.1). In Hungary, the lowest satisfaction scores are related to personal and household income, and for external factors, respondents are clearly most dissatisfied with public services (Table 10).

The pattern of the data for Austria is also similar for each domain satisfaction. The satisfaction of native-born people tends to be slightly higher than the national average, while the satisfaction of immigrants from the new EU countries is lower or more or less lower than the national average.

The satisfaction of Hungarians in Austria with material goods is remarkably higher compared to both the Hungarian average and potential emigrants. There is one exception: satisfaction with housing conditions is slightly lower in Austria, and only compared to potential emigrants is there a minimal surplus. Satisfaction with social contacts and available leisure time, on the other hand, is clearly lower among Hungarians living in Austria. The largest difference among the aspects taken into account is in satisfaction with the quality and availability of public services: the gap is larger than 2 on a scale of 0-10 in favour of Austria.

To summarise, the main conclusions of Table 10 and Figures 61-70 is that the satisfaction of Hungarians in Austria with material goods is quite high, approaching and even exceeding the Austrian average in terms of satisfaction with personal income. (Here the only exception is the satisfaction with housing conditions). The relatively high SWB values are particularly striking when compared to the subsamples in Hungary. For the non-material factors, however, the relationship is reversed: both in terms of satisfaction with social contacts and available leisure time, the lowest average values were measured among Hungarians in Austria. These indicators are not only worse than in Hungary, but also compared to immigrants from the new EU countries.

Table 10. Average domain satisfaction scores by analytical subgroups.

	Avg. HU	Pot. stayers HU	Pot. migrants HU	Avg. AT (2022)	Native in AT (2022)	EU12 in AT (2022)	Hun in AT	Diff.: Hun in AT vs. Avg. HU	Diff.: Hun in AT vs. pot. migr.	Diff.: Hun in AT vs. Avg. AT
<i>Material factors</i>										
HH financial situation	6.2	6.4	6.0	7.3	7.6	6.7	7.1	+0.9	+1.1	-0.2
Personal income	5.9	6.1	5.3	6.9	7.1	5.9	7.1	+1.2	+1.8	+0.2
Job	6.8	7.0	6.4	7.5	7.6	6.9	7.1	+0.3	+0.7	-0.4
Accommodation	7.5	7.6	7.2	8.4	8.5	7.7	7.4	-0.1	+0.2	-1.0
<i>Non-material factors</i>										
Health	7.3	7.3	8.2	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	7.7	+0.4	-0.5	n.a.
Social relationships	7.7	7.8	7.8	8.6	8.7	8.3	7.5	-0.2	-0.3	-1.1
Time use	7.0	7.0	6.1	7.4	7.6	7.1	6.8	-0.2	+0.7	-0.6
<i>External factors</i>										
Living environment	7.4	7.5	7.2	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	7.4	0	+0.2	n.a.
Green areas	6.8	6.8	6.9	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	7.4	+0.6	+0.5	n.a.
Public services	5.4	5.5	5.0	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	7.5	+2.1	+2.5	n.a.

Source of data: EU-SILC 2022, MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own table.

Figure 61. Satisfaction with the financial situation of the household by analytical subgroups. Source of data: EU-SILC 2022, MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Figure 62. Satisfaction with personal income by analytical subgroups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Figure 63. Satisfaction with job by analytical subgroups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Figure 64. Satisfaction with accommodation by analytical subgroups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Figure 65. Satisfaction with health by analytical subgroups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Figure 66. Satisfaction with social relationships by analytical subgroups. Source of data: EU-SILC 2022, MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Figure 67. Satisfaction with time use by analytical subgroups. Source of data: EU-SILC 2022, MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Figure 68. Satisfaction with living environment by analytical subgroups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Figure 69. Satisfaction with green areas by analytical subgroups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Figure 70. Satisfaction with public services by analytical subgroups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

5.3. Affective well-being

Incorporating affective well-being metrics into surveys enables researchers to capture emotion-driven effects, offering a deeper understanding of how individuals truly feel in their daily lives and how various factors influence subjective well-being (SWB). This concept focuses on the frequency of positive and negative emotions, such as happiness, anxiety, or stress, shedding light on aspects of human behaviour that life satisfaction measures alone may overlook

The affective dimension of the SWB gap between the two countries is a long-standing phenomenon. In the previous Research Report, we summarised the changes in the national-level gap after 2013 (Németh et al., 2023: 59-61). This time, we focus on the analytical subgroups, as shown in the table and figures below.

Table 11 shows the percentage of respondents who have chosen the options "all of the time" or "most of the time" in the questionnaires of the EU-SILC or MIGWELL surveys. Perhaps the most striking conclusion is that the affective well-being scores of potential migrants are more favourable than that of those planning to stay, in all the aspects examined. This is an important part of the descriptive data analysis because it has become clear that affective well-being is not the main driver of emigration intentions.

In Austria, national averages are available for only two variables, as the 2022 SILC questionnaire focused solely on happiness and loneliness. Based on our non-representative sample, Hungarians in Austria scored lower in both categories. However, when compared to data from Hungary, a more nuanced pattern emerges. Hungarians in Austria experience both positive and negative emotional states more frequently. They are more likely to feel happy and

calm in Austria than in Hungary, yet also more prone to feelings of nervousness and depression. Notably, their average scores for loneliness and stress are worse, at 10.7% and 16.3% respectively, compared to the Hungarian averages of 8.7% and 9.9% (Table 11, Figure 71-77).

Table 11. Affective SWB scores by analytical subgroups. (Frequency: all of the time + most of the time answers, %, non-respondents are excluded)

	Avg. HU	Pot. stayers HU	Pot. migrants HU	Avg. AT (2022)	Native in AT (2022)	EU12 in AT (2022)	Hun in AT	Diff.: Hun in AT vs. Avg. HU	Diff.: Hun in AT vs. pot. migr.	Diff.: Hun in AT vs. Avg. AT
<i>Positive emotions</i>										
Happy	56.2	56.7	70.4	74.0	76.4	62.8	70.4	+14.2	0	-3.6
Calm, peaceful	52.3	52.2	61.0	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	69.3	+17.0	+8.3	n.a.
<i>Negative emotions</i>										
Nervous	7.7	6.9	5.2	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	8.1	+0.4	+2.9	n.a.
Downhearted,depressed	7.0	5.8	3.9	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	7.5	+0.5	+3.6	n.a.
Feeling down	6.4	5.5	2.1	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	4.6	-1.8	+2.5	n.a.
Lonely	8.7	7.4	2.6	4.3	3.4	6.9	10.7	+2.0	+8.1	+6.4
Stressed	9.9	9.0	8.6	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	16.3	+6.4	+7.7	n.a.

Source of data: EU-SILC 2022, MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own table.

Figure 71. Being happy: the share of respondents by analytical subgroups. Source of data: EU-SILC 2022, MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Figure 72. Feeling calm and peaceful: the share of respondents by analytical subgroups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Figure 73. Being nervous: the share of respondents by analytical subgroups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Figure 74. Feeling downhearted or depressed: the share of respondents by analytical subgroups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Figure 75. Feeling down in the dumps: the share of respondents by analytical subgroups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Figure 76. Feeling lonely: the share of respondents by analytical subgroups. Source of data: EU-SILC 2022, MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Figure 77. Feeling stressed: the share of respondents by analytical subgroups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

5.4. Eudaimonic well-being

Eudaimonic variables receive far less attention in international surveys compared to the cognitive and affective dimensions. However, incorporating measures of eudaimonia – which reflects a meaningful life and includes aspects such as autonomy, self-esteem, and self-actualization – could offer a more comprehensive understanding of SWB. This approach would

allow researchers and policymakers to account for psychological factors that play a crucial role in the perception of well-being.

An illustrative example is the EU-SILC survey, which last measured eudaimonic well-being in 2013. Recognizing the importance of this dimension, the MIGWELL project incorporated three comparative questions into both parallel surveys. In the representative Hungarian survey, respondents rated their agreement on a scale from 0 to 10. The average scores were 6.9 for the statement "the things I do in life are meaningful" and 7.0 for "I feel free to choose how to live my life." However, optimism scored somewhat lower, with an average of 6.3.

The pattern is similar to domain satisfactions. Potential stayers reported slightly higher average scores than the national representative sample (by 0.1 points), while potential emigrants scored considerably lower (by 0.4–0.5 points).

In contrast, Hungarians living in Austria reported higher average scores across all three variables (Figure 78-80). The smallest difference was observed for "feeling free to live life" (7.3, compared to 7.0 for the Hungarian average and 6.6 for potential migrants). The largest positive difference was seen in "general optimism about the future" (7.6, compared to 6.3 for the Hungarian average and 5.9 for potential migrants).

Figure 78. Feeling that things, they do are meaningful (0: not worthwhile at all, 10: completely worthwhile). Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Figure 79. Feeling that they are free to choose how to live life (0: not true at all, 10: completely true). Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Figure 80. Optimism about the future (0: completely without hope, 10: completely hopeful). Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

6. The variables associated with domain satisfaction among Hungarians living in Hungary and Austria

6.1. Satisfaction with job

6.1.1. Model for the whole sample

As some variables explaining job satisfaction were only asked for employed persons, the model findings are only valid for this economic activity group.

Based on the model, Hungarians living in Austria have the highest average estimate of work satisfaction (7.32; CI: 7.08-7.56), while potential migrants have the lowest (6.75; CI: 6.55-6.94). The average estimate of those intending to stay is close to that of those living in Austria (7.34; CI: 7.22-7.47) (Figure 81). When controlling for the other variables, it is observed that the fact of intending to stay is associated with higher job satisfaction than being a potential migrant. If all persons in the sample were intending to stay, compared to the situation if all were potential migrants, respondents' job satisfaction would be higher by 0.34 (CI: 0.004-0.68) on average. The association of living in Austria with job satisfaction is not significantly different compared to any other group.

Figure 81. Mean job satisfaction estimates by Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

The model suggests an inverted U-shaped relationship between job satisfaction and the age variable in the joint sample. The curve reaches its highest estimate of job satisfaction (7.25) between the ages of 45 and 50. Among the Hungarian groups, this inverted U-shape is strongest

for those intending to stay, with the curve differing between groups (steady slope for potential migrants, almost horizontal for Hungarians from Austria), but these differences are not significant.

By settlement category, the lowest average estimate is for those living in sparsely populated areas (6.86; CI: 6.67-7.04), while the highest is for those living in intermediate density areas (7.37; CI: 7.22-7.52). Compared with the sparsely populated settlement reference category, living in a densely populated settlement (0.29; CI: -0.009-0.6) and in an intermediate density settlement (0.36; CI: 0.08-0.62) were also associated with higher satisfaction. The average marginal effect for the group of potential migrants in the „intermediate density-sparsely populated settlement comparison” is close to 0 (0.02; CI: -0.51-0.56). Significant effects largely disappear in the subsample decomposition according to the Hungarian sub-sample.

In terms of education, the highest average estimates were obtained for those with tertiary education (7.71; CI: 7.5-7.92), followed by two groups of people with secondary education, those with a certificate (7.32; CI: 7.16-7.48) and those with a vocational education (6.87; CI: 6.7-7.04). However, the job satisfaction of these two groups is not significantly different from that of the low-educated (6.13; CI: 5.73-6.54) in the whole sample, after controlling for other variables. The model indicates that the association with job satisfaction in the „vocational-primary” comparison is strongest among those who intend to stay. This relationship is significant at the $p < 0.1$ significance level, with the average marginal effect in the „vocational-primary comparison” being 0.57 (CI: -0.02-1.18). Hungarians living in Austria are the only group where the average marginal effect is in the negative direction in all comparisons with the primary education reference group, suggesting a negative effect of over-education. However, the average marginal effects of the education category are not significant for this migrant group. The pairwise comparison of marginal effects indicates that the effect of education is moderated somewhat by the different Hungarian groups. Indeed, higher marginal effects are expected in the „tertiary-primary comparison” among those who want to stay than among Hungarians in Austria (Figure 82).

Figure 82. Average marginal effects of education by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Among the variables potentially closely related to work, neither the number of hours worked nor ISCO-08 categories show a relationship with job satisfaction (a slight managerial dissatisfaction is associated for potential migrants and a dissatisfaction among workers with unskilled occupations is observable for those living in Austria, but there is not enough statistical power to verify these claims). An interesting, unexpected relationship is observed for the type of employment contract. Individuals with a fixed-term contract of more than six months (6.25; 5.91-6.59) have the lowest average satisfaction estimate, while individuals with a fixed-term contract of less than six months (7.63; CI: 6.96-8.31) have the highest. A significant relationship is found between the type of employment contract and job satisfaction. Having a fixed-term contract of more than six months is associated with on average 1.01 lower job satisfaction than having a fixed-term contract of a reference short duration. Looking at the Hungarian groups, this relationship is entirely due to the group of those who intend to stay (average marginal effect close to -2), while in the other two groups the average marginal effect of job satisfaction for those with a longer fixed-term contract is in the positive direction. The relationship between length of fixed-term contract and job satisfaction is clearly moderated by the Hungarian group variable, with significant differences in marginal effects for those who intend to stay on the one hand, and for potential migrants and for those living in Austria on the other. Among those who want to stay, having a short-term fixed-term contract is associated with higher job satisfaction even compared to an open-ended contract (average marginal effect in the „open-ended contract-short-term fixed-term comparison” is -1.37) (Figure 83).

Figure 83. Average marginal effects of contract type by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Another important variable was the possibility of advancement and development at work. The possibility of advancement and development (7.62; CI: 7.47-7.77) was associated with higher job satisfaction estimates compared to a lack of it (6.88; 6.75-7.01). The marginal effect was 0.23 (CI: -0.01-0.48), which was significant at the $p < 0.1$ level. The breakdown by groups shows that the effect of this variable is also mainly observed in the group of those intending to stay (0.38), for those living in Austria it is not significant, while for potential migrants, who presumably do not want to advance locally in their current Hungarian job, the average marginal effect is only 0.05 (CI: -0.48-0.59).

Turning to the work-life variables, engaging in leisure activities (7.64; CI: 7.5-7.78) is also associated with higher job satisfaction estimates compared to those who cannot do so for reasons beyond their control (no money, no time) (6.16; CI: 5.9-6.43). The average marginal effect is 0.39 (0.13-0.64) in this case. This difference is significant only in the group of those who want to stay, but the sign is in the expected direction for the other groups as well. Those with a partner (7.31; CI: 7.19-7.42) have higher estimated job satisfaction than those without a partner (6.87; CI: 6.68-7.06). Having a partner is associated with higher job satisfaction by an average of 0.29 (CI: 0.02-0.56), significant at the $p < 0.05$ level. For this variable, in contrast to previous trends, the effect is not associated with satisfaction for those intending to stay, in fact this is the only group where the average marginal effect is negative (not significant). For those

living in Austria, having a partner is more important, with a marginal effect of 1.25 (CI: 0.54-1.96), while for potential migrants the value is 0.47 (-0.05-1). The former is significant at the $p < 0.01$ level, the latter at the $p < 0.1$ level. The relationship between partner and job satisfaction is also moderated by the Hungarian group subcategory. The marginal effect of having a partner is significantly different between those who live in Austria and those who want to stay (Figure 84).

Figure 84. Average marginal effects of having a partner by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Job satisfaction is related to the variable of how well an individual can cover his or her household expenses, as a proxy for salary. Compared to the reference „with major difficulties” category (5.22; CI: 4.53-5.92), all other variables show a significant positive marginal effect, except for "with difficulties" (mean marginal effect 0.87; CI: -0.13-1.87), at the $p < 0.001$ level. It can be observed that, apart from the category „with difficulties”, the average marginal effect increases in all other categories as the ease of payment rises. The average marginal effect in the „very easily-with major difficulties comparison” is a remarkable 3.59 (CI: 2.46-4.71). After breaking down the groups, it becomes clear that the most important issue among Hungarians in Austria is the secure coverage of expenses. This is already apparent in the „with some difficulties-with major difficulties comparison”, with the marginal effect being significantly larger for Hungarians in Austria than for the other two groups in Hungary (5.2; CI: 1.43-9 in comparison with those intending to stay, 4.21; CI: 0.32-8.1 in comparison with potential migrants). The reason for this large difference is that having major difficulty paying for

expenses is associated with markedly low job satisfaction among Hungarians in Austria. For Hungarians in Austria, the first step is the important one of achieving a level of „with some difficulties”. In comparison, even the average marginal effect of „easily-with major difficulties” is not significantly different from this „with some difficulties-with major difficulties step”. However, we can observe a significant jump at the „very easily-with major difficulties comparison”. This makes it clear that for Hungarians in Austria, „very easily” is the second important step up after the „with some difficulties” one (Figure 85).

Figure 85. Average marginal effects of the ease of covering the expenses by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

The last variable with which we found a link is being looked down because of work or financial situation. Those who feel that society looks down on them have lower mean estimates of job satisfaction (5.77; CI: 5.39-6.15) than those who do not experience this (7.47; CI: 7.35-7.58). Being looked down upon versus not being looked down upon is associated with lower job satisfaction by an average of 0.93 (CI: 0.47-1.39) (no significant difference in comparison with the "so-so" category). Being looked down upon is the most negative in Austria, with an average marginal effect of -1.62 (CI: -2.72-(-0.52)) among Hungarians living there, while being looked down upon is the least strongly associated with job satisfaction among those planning to stay in Hungary (-0.7; CI: -1.33-(-0.06)). Furthermore, for those living in Austria, even the „so-so being looked down-not being looked down comparison” is significant, indicating a disadvantage of even some degree of disdain (Figure 86).

Figure 86. Average marginal effects of being looked down upon by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

6.1.2. Extended model for Austria

Those who are overqualified for their current job have lower mean estimates (6.67; CI: 6.16-7.18) than those who have a suitable „education-job pairing” or were able to find a job requiring higher skills than they have based on their education (7.46; CI: 7.22-7.69). The mean marginal effect of overqualification is negative (-0.78; CI: -1.41-(-0.16)), with a significant association with job satisfaction. The negative association with overeducation is strongest for those who were maximally satisfied with their job in Hungary (-2.95; CI: -5.36-(-0.53)). This effect is not observed for those who were previously dissatisfied. The effect of overeducation is significantly different at the $p < 0.1$ level for those who were previously absolutely dissatisfied and those who were maximally satisfied, with a marginal effect difference of 4.65 (CI: -0.42-9.73).

Of the new variables included in the model, only the frequency of visits to Hungary showed a significant relationship with job satisfaction. Contrary to expectations, the mean estimates for those who visited home frequently were lower (6.96; CI: 6.63-7.3) than those who visited home infrequently (7.52; CI: 7.22-7.82). The mean marginal effect was -0.55 (CI: -1.08-(-0.03)) for frequent visits home. One could speculate that those who have no relatives in Hungary indicate a negative relationship with frequent home visits, while those with family members left behind are more satisfied with their job if they can travel home frequently. However, this is not the

case. In fact, the negative relationship of frequent home visits is even higher for those who have children or a partner in Hungary. However, the difference is not significant in this regard.

Differences between subjective and objective integration among Hungarians in Austria

This analysis is based on Karin Amit and Svetlana Chachasvili-Bolotin's article published in 2018 "Satisfied With Less? Mismatch Between Subjective and Objective Position of Immigrants and Native-Born Men and Women in the Labour Market". The authors introduced the idea that, in addition to the possible mismatch between skills required for a job and qualification, another mismatch may be present in the labour market. This arises when a person's labour market position based on objective data does not match the position occupied by subjective job satisfaction within a society. Previous research has shown that for women, job satisfaction is often higher than would be indicated by the conditions and prestige of their jobs. This discrepancy is often explained by the presence of low job-related expectations. In Israel, Amit and Chachasvili-Bolotin (2018) also showed that women have a higher proportion of this positive mismatch, yet men are more likely to have a negative mismatch (not satisfied with their otherwise good job and salary). In their study, this positive mismatch was also observed for some socioeconomically disadvantaged ethnic groups who were satisfied with their low material wealth. We did the same analysis for Hungarians in Austria, placing them in Austrian society.

Calculation procedure and limitations:

- First, we needed the subjective measure. In the cited article, this was the average of job satisfaction and income satisfaction. But since EU-SILC did not measure satisfaction with income, we replaced it with satisfaction with the household's financial situation. The wave that included both satisfaction with household income and satisfaction with work is 2018. The average of the two satisfaction levels was used as the subjective indicator, and then z-score standardization was used to produce the final score. For Hungarians in Austria, these are the 2024 satisfaction scores, so even this six-year difference could be a bias if there is a trend change.
- The easier, work-related part of the objective indicator is connected to the prestige of the job. If the person is working in ISCO08 1,2 or 3, then code 1, if not, then 0.
- In the objective financial part, since we have replaced satisfaction with the household's financial situation with satisfaction with income, we should also look at household income. However, our household income category data is either corrupted or the respondents not indicate the true category due to the personal nature of the question. Thus, for Hungarians, only the personal income response is meaningful. Then the Austrian 2018 EU-SILC personal income values were adjusted for inflation to 2023

levels. Then the Austrian values were classified according to the salary response categories of our own survey questionnaire. Later on, as in the study by Amit and Chachasvili-Bolotin (2018), the median value of the categories was converted from category to salary value (e.g., a category between €250 and €500 became €375). This figure was then converted to a z-value.

- The 0 or 1 and the z-value were added together, then another z-value conversion was performed.

If the difference between the objective indicator and the subjective indicator was greater than 0.5, we can talk about a negative mismatch, if less than -0.5, about a positive match, and if between the two, about a good match.

On average, the Hungarians are the second worst after the Turks on the subjective indicator. On the objective indicator, Hungarians are the third worst (ahead of Turks and Yugoslavs). Of all the country of birth groups, Hungarians have the best subjective and objective match. 49% of men and 36% of women belong to this correctly categorising group (Figure 87-88). Negative pairing is less common for women in all groups by country of birth, while positive pairing is more common for them. Negative pairing is true for 28% of Hungarian women, which is the third lowest. For Hungarian men it is 30%, the lowest of all country of birth groups. However, Hungarian women are more likely to be positively matched (35%) than Hungarian men (20%).

Positive incorrect pairing is more common than correct pairing: entrepreneurs, low educated, married, living in Vorarlberg. However, this is not the case for Hungarians, who are 11.6% less likely to belong to this group.

Negative incorrect pairing is more common than correct pairing: highly educated, native Austrians, Turks.

Figure 87. Negative and positive mismatch by gender and country of birth group. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Figure 88. Negative, correct, and positive mismatch in the country of birth groups by gender. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

6.2. Satisfaction with income

6.2.1. Model for the whole sample

Based on the model, Hungarians living in Austria have the highest average income satisfaction estimate (7.2; CI: 6.96-7.44), while potential migrants have the lowest (5.03; CI: 4.78-5.27) (Figure 89). Compared with the estimates for the job satisfaction variable, it is striking that the gap between Hungarians living in Austria and those intending to stay in Hungary has widened. The average estimate for those intending to stay is 5.94 (CI: 5.81-6.07). The model indicates that living in Austria is associated with an average 0.54 higher income satisfaction compared

to being a potential migrant and 0.49 higher income satisfaction compared to intending to stay in Hungary. However, these marginal effects are not significant.

Figure 89. Mean financial satisfaction estimates by Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

In terms of economic activity, entrepreneurs (7.28; CI: 6.89-7.67) and employed persons (6.27; CI: 6.15-6.4) have the highest average estimates, while the disabled (3.81; CI: 2.97-4.66) and the unemployed (2.57; CI: 1.93-3.21) have the lowest estimated income satisfaction. The average marginal effect compared to the employed reference category is significant for the disabled (-1.58, CI: -2.58-(-0.59)), student (-1.64; CI: -2.31-(-0.97)) and unemployed (-2.15; CI: -2.94-(-1.41)) groups in increasing order of magnitude. There are some interesting findings regarding the moderating effect of the Hungarian group. Being an entrepreneur in comparison with being employed is associated with significantly higher income satisfaction (0.62; CI: 0.1-1.15) among those who intend to stay, while this effect is negative but not significant in Austria. Also, the negative student financial satisfaction already presented is the lowest in Austria (-1.15; CI: -2.27-(-0.03)) (Figure 90).

Figure 90. Average marginal effects of economic status by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

There is a very slight U-shaped correlation between age and income satisfaction, but for Hungarians living in Austria, a stagnation is expected until the age of 40, and then a slight decrease is observed. The model estimates that men have a slightly higher average income satisfaction (6.11; CI: 5.97-6.26 compared to 5.93; CI: 5.79-6.07 for women). In the counterfactual analysis, women can expect to have a slightly lower income satisfaction, with the largest gender gap observed for those living in Austria. However, the average marginal effect in this case is only -0.27 and the 95% confidence interval covers both negative and positive values, so no gender difference is observed.

As expected, those with tertiary education have higher average estimates of income satisfaction (6.97; CI: 6.73-7.21) than those with a certificate (6.08; CI: 5.91-6.24) or a vocational qualification (5.89; CI: 5.72-6.07). Those with primary education have the lowest estimates (4.54, CI: 4.22-4.85). Looking at the marginal effects, there is a significant relationship between education and income satisfaction. Tertiary education is associated with higher satisfaction by an average of 0.62 (CI: 0.1-1.14) compared to the primary education category. The average marginal effect is also significant in the „vocational-primary education comparison”, with a value of 0.44. The Hungarian group has a moderating effect. For potential migrants, the effect is not significant in any of the comparisons. The mean marginal effect of „tertiary education-primary education” is largest for Hungarians living in Austria (1.53; CI: 0.09-2.97) (Figure 91).

Figure 91. Average marginal effects of education by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

By type of settlement, those living in densely (6.15; CI: 5.96-6.34) and intermediate (6.19; CI: 6.04-6.35) populated settlements have higher estimated average satisfaction than those living in sparsely (5.57; CI: 5.37-5.77) populated settlements. The counterfactual analysis does not support the positive returns to satisfaction of living in densely populated settlements. However, a positive (0.48; CI: 0.21-0.75) significant marginal effect is observed for living in intermediate densely versus sparsely populated settlements. This difference shows a positive significant association for those intending to stay, with an average marginal effect of 0.57 (CI: 0.24-0.89) (Figure 92).

Figure 92. Average marginal effects of settlement type by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

On the partnership variable, those with a partner have higher average estimates of satisfaction not only with work but also with income. In their case, the average estimate is 6.2 (CI: 6.08-6.33), while for singles it is 5.63 (CI: 5.45-5.81). Having a partner is found to be associated with an average increase in satisfaction of 0.16 (CI: -0.09-0.42), the relationship is not significant. However, the role of the partner is moderated by the Hungarian group variable, with a significant positive association only in the potential migrant group (0.74; CI: 0.08-1.4) (Figure 93).

Figure 93. Average marginal effects of having a partner by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Two indicators related to the objective measure of income, greater difficulty in meeting expenditure and deprivation, show a negative association with income satisfaction. The mean estimate of income satisfaction for those in deprivation is 4.83 (CI: 4.66-5.01), while for those unaffected by the condition it is almost two full points higher (6.66, CI: 6.53-6.79). Similarly, the mean estimate is lower for those who have major difficulty in covering their expenditure (2.68; CI: 2.17-3.19) than for those who can do so very easily (7.87; CI: 7.33-8.41). The average marginal effect for deprivation is -0.95 (CI: -1.32-(-0.58)), with an absolute value close to the average marginal effect for the comparison of the categories of covering expenditure „with difficulties-with major difficulties” (1.5; CI: 0.59-2.4) (Figure 95). The average marginal effect for the „very easily-with major difficulties comparison” is 3.98 (CI: 2.91-5.03). Suffering deprivation is associated with the smallest negative effect among those intending to stay (-0.65; CI: -0.94-(-0.35)), a stronger but not significant effect for those living in Austria (-1.44; CI: -3.02-0.13), while the strongest average negative effect of deprivation is observed for potential migrants (-1.53; CI: -2.16-(-0.9)). The moderating effect of each Hungarian group is also reflected in the relationship between the difficulty of meeting the expenditure and satisfaction. The positive effect of covering expenditure is more pronounced and stronger for those living in Austria. For example, the „with difficulties-with major difficulties comparison” for those living in Austria averages 4.56 (CI: 0.77-8.35), while for those intending to stay it is „only” 1.8 (CI: 1.1-2.5) (Figure 94).

Figure 94. Average marginal effects of the ease of covering the expenses by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Figure 95. Average marginal effects of deprivation by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Respondents' incomes are placed in relative positions compared to median wages in Hungary and Austria. Three categories have been developed: above the median wage in Hungary and Austria, above the median wage in Hungary but below the median wage in Austria, and finally the third category is that the respondent earns less than both the median wage in Hungary and Austria. Earnings higher than the median in both countries have a positive average marginal effect (1.02; CI: -0.22-2.27), while, if earnings are only higher than the Hungarian median, the effect is almost neutral (0.12; CI: -0.42-0.67). However, the confidence intervals show that the effects are not clear-cut. Among the Hungarian groups, relative earnings show a significant relationship with income satisfaction only for potential migrants, when their income is above both the Hungarian and the Austrian median (3.57; CI: 0.62-6.5) (Figure 96).

Figure 96. Average marginal effects of relative deprivation by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

In addition to objective indicators of financial situation, social perceptions of income are also linked to satisfaction with finances. Those who feel that they are looked down upon because of their job or salary have significantly lower estimates (5.03; CI: 4.67-5.39) than those who do not feel the same (6.19; CI: 6.07-6.3). Those who answer "so-so", fall between these two groups (5.74; CI: 5.5-5.99). The average marginal effect of being perceived as despised is -0.37 (CI: -0.79-0.05). Belonging to the any of the Hungarian group does not moderate the relationship between being looked down upon and income satisfaction.

6.2.2. Extended model for Austria

Based on the model of Hungarians in Austria, pre-migration financial satisfaction does not moderate the relationships shown so far. Although the moderating effect is not significant, it is worth pointing out that the slight gender gap already shown widens to its widest when both men and women were satisfied with their income before emigration. This may suggest that women find it more difficult to transfer their good income situation to Austria. While overqualification was previously associated with lower levels of job satisfaction, it shows no relationship with income satisfaction. Neither the frequency of returning home nor the existence of specific reasons for migration can be associated with differences in income satisfaction. In terms of remittances, the average estimates of remittances are the highest among those, who send money home (7.45; CI: 7.18-7.73). Compared to those who did not answer the question on remittances,

the average marginal effect of remittances is 0.63 (CI: -0.1-1.36), which is a significant difference at the $p < 0.1$ level.

6.3. Satisfaction with housing conditions

6.3.1. Model for the whole sample

In contrast to the two domains presented so far, the highest average estimated satisfaction with housing was found in the group of those intending to stay (7.67; CI: 7.57-7.77). The estimated satisfaction with housing of potential migrants is also high (7.07; CI: 6.89-7.25). In between these two groups are the Hungarians in Austria with an average estimated satisfaction of 7.29 (CI: 7.09-7.49). Counterfactual analysis revealed no significant average marginal effect between the Hungarian groups. Thus, when controlling for other variables, there is no extra housing satisfaction provided by living in Hungary (Figure 97).

Figure 97. Mean housing satisfaction estimates by Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

In terms of economic activity, for employed persons automatically high satisfaction with housing (7.48; CI: 7.38-7.58) is not inferred from the observed high satisfaction with income. In terms of average estimates, besides entrepreneurs (7.97; CI: 7.67-8.27), students (7.54; CI: 7.2-7.87) and other inactive persons (7.91; CI: 7.55-8.28) also have higher values. Disabled people have the lowest average estimated housing satisfaction (6.76, CI: 6.15-7.37). However, when looking at marginal effects, it can be concluded that the category of economic activity is

not significantly related to housing satisfaction. Looking at moderating effects, only one significant relationship is observed. For the group of those intending to stay, being in the other inactive group is associated with higher housing satisfaction than being employees (Figure 98).

Figure 98. Average marginal effects of economic status by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

The relationship between age and housing satisfaction is once again described by the well-known slightly U-shaped relationship, but for potential migrants the increase occurs earlier, already in their 40s. The model estimates show a small female advantage in housing satisfaction. The mean estimated value for women is 7.56 (CI: 7.45-7.67), just below that of men (7.42; CI: 7.3-7.53). The counterfactual analysis reveals an average marginal effect of 0.14 (CI: -0.02-0.31) in favour of women, significant at the $p < 0.1$ level. This positive difference is due to the groups in Hungary and mainly to potential migrants (0.35; CI: -0.03-0.73). Among Hungarians living in Austria, the average marginal effect is negative, i.e., men have higher housing satisfaction, but the effect is not significant in this group (Figure 99).

Figure 99. Average marginal effects of gender by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

The expected ranking by education is also reflected in housing satisfaction. As the level of education decreases from the tertiary educated (7.84; CI: 7.66-8.02) to those with a certificate (7.64; CI: 7.51-7.76) and those with a vocational school degree (7.35; CI: 7.21-7.49) to the low educated, the average estimated satisfaction with housing also decreases. In terms of average marginal effects, the „tertiary education-primary education comparison” (0.57; CI: 0.19-0.95) and the „certificate-primary education comparison” (0.57; CI: 0.23-0.9) show a nearly similar effect. Furthermore, the „vocational-primary education comparison” (0.46; CI: 0.13-0.79) also indicates a significant positive relationship. For Hungarians living in Austria, only the „tertiary education-primary education comparison” is significant at the $p < 0.05$ level. However, in this comparison the average marginal effect is high (1.2; CI: 0.17-2.35). In the other comparisons with the reference low-skilled group, the significant difference is found among those intending to stay (Figure 100).

Figure 100. Average marginal effects of education by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

In the settlement type variable, the surplus in income-related satisfaction disappears for densely populated settlements once housing satisfaction is considered. The model estimates that the highest estimated housing satisfaction is observed in intermediately dense settlements (7.63; CI: 7.51-7.75). They are followed by densely populated (7.44, CI: 7.29-7.59) and sparsely populated (7.3; CI: 7.15-7.45) settlements. Living in an intermediately dense municipality is associated with an increase in housing satisfaction compared to a sparsely populated municipality. The average marginal effect is 0.24 (CI: 0.04-0.45). When examining the moderating effect of the Hungarian groups, it can be stated that this effect is mainly due to those who has the intention to stay (0.31; CI: 0.06-0.56) (although the average marginal effect is also positive in the other two groups). For the intention to stay group, the „dense-thin settlement comparison” (0.45; CI: 0.15-0.76) is also significant in the expected dense settlement direction. However, for Hungarians living in Austria, the „dense-thin comparison” shows a significant negative mean margin (-1.06; CI: -1.66-(-0.45)), i.e., living in rural areas is associated with a satisfaction premium (Figure 101).

Figure 101. Average marginal effects of settlement type by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

In line with the usual trends, those with a partner also have a higher average estimate of satisfaction with housing. For those without a partner, the value is 7.19 (CI: 7.15-7.33), while for those with a partner it is 7.63 (CI: 7.53-7.72). The average marginal effect is also more favourable for those with a partner, with a higher estimate of housing satisfaction of 0.44 (CI: 0.24-0.64). The positive effect is evident in all Hungarian groups, the weakest for those intending to stay (0.38; CI: 0.14-0.62) and the strongest among Hungarians living in Austria (0.6; CI: 0.1-1.1) (Figure 102).

Figure 102. Average marginal effects of having a partner by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Previous research has shown that people who live in their own property report higher levels of housing satisfaction. Based on the mean estimates, this is also true for the sample of Hungarians, as those who live in their own property (7.64; CI: 7.55-7.73) have higher scores than those who do not own their home (7.05; CI: 6.89-7.21). The counterfactual model also suggests a significant negative relationship between not owning the property and housing satisfaction. The average marginal effect is -0.37 (CI: -0.61-(-0.13)). The negative effect is observed in all Hungarian groups, but is significant only in the two groups currently in Hungary. It is slightly stronger for potential migrants (-0.53; CI: -0.06-(-1)) than for those intending to stay (-0.32; CI: -0.01-(-0.63)) (Figure 103).

Figure 103. Average marginal effects of house/flat ownership by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

There is a negative relationship between the number of household members per room and housing satisfaction. Thus, the more household members per room, the more dissatisfied the respondent is. An increase in the ratio by one is associated with a decrease in satisfaction of 0.49 (CI: 0.22-0.76). The decrease is steepest for those intending to stay, and smallest for those living in Austria. Similarly, lower housing satisfaction is associated with more problems with the dwelling and its surroundings (leaking, darkness, noise, environmental problems, crime). A decrease in satisfaction of 0.26 (CI: 0.11-0.41) is observed when one more problem is present. The relationship is not moderated by Hungarian group variable.

Closely related to housing satisfaction is the financial situation of the respondent, which is still represented by the variable which measures the difficulty of covering expenses. The lowest estimated average satisfaction is for those who have major difficulties in financing their expenses (5.5; CI: 5.08-5.92), while the highest estimated satisfaction is for those who can cover their expenses very easily (8.91; CI: 8.49-9.33). Compared to the reference group, all other response categories (even the "I don't know") show a significant positive mean marginal effect. The strongest is of course in the „very easily-with major difficulties comparison” (3.14; CI: 2.42-3.86). While for the previous domains, covering expenses was a very important indicator in Austria, it was not a relevant variable for housing satisfaction for Hungarians in Austria. Compared to the major difficulties category, only the response „I do not know” shows a significant positive difference for this migrant group. The positive marginal effects are thus due to the two groups in Hungary, especially the potential migrants (Figure 104).

Figure 104. Average marginal effects of the ease of covering the expenses by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

6.3.2. Extended model for Austria

For Hungarians in Austria, pre-migration housing satisfaction moderates the already presented association in several ways. The non-significant male gender advantage is strongest when the level of satisfaction before migration was low. The model suggests that men in Austria who were dissatisfied with their housing before migration are more satisfied with their housing than women who were equally dissatisfied before migration (mean marginal effect is 1.8). Similarly, for the low level of dissatisfaction before migration, the most significant additional satisfaction is related to living in a sparsely populated settlement. As expected, the higher the pre-migration satisfaction, the lower the estimates for post-migration satisfaction (but the relationship is not significant). This is only not evident for those living intermediately dense settlements, where the slope is positive. Also, in terms of education, the satisfaction advantage associated with high education is highest when satisfaction before migration was low. For the low-educated and those with vocational education, low pre-migration satisfaction is associated with low post-migration satisfaction and high satisfaction with high satisfaction (positive slope). The slope for housing-related problems and the household to room ratio is described by the most negative slope when pre-migration satisfaction was high. Thus, if an individual was satisfied with their housing before migration, but afterwards experiences many problems with housing or lives in an overcrowded dwelling, they will have a low estimate of their housing satisfaction. Conversely, if they were dissatisfied before migration, these problems are less bothersome.

Those who send money home have higher average satisfaction with housing (7.34; CI: 7.06-7.63) than those who do not (7.2; CI: 6.84-7.94), but lower than those who did not answer to this question (7.46; CI: 6.98-7.94). The mean marginal effects are not significant, so we found no evidence that sending home causes individuals to spend so little on their housing that it is associated with dissatisfaction. In terms of reasons for migration, indicating the reasons of financial and helping one's future in Hungary (7.44 and 7.37) resulted in higher estimates than not indicating these reasons (7.07 and 6.08). For the reason of helping one's future in Hungary, the average marginal effect is 0.528 (CI: -0.05-1.11), which is significant at the $p < 0.1$ level. Thus, those who know they will return home are more satisfied with their current housing. There is a significant effect for year of emigration, the earlier the emigration, the higher the satisfaction with housing.

6.4. Satisfaction with social relationships

6.4.1. Model for the whole sample

Satisfaction with social relationships is the first domain for which Hungarians living in Austria have the lowest mean estimate (7.61; CI: 7.41-7.81), followed by potential migrants (7.69; CI: 7.52-7.86), while those intending to stay have the highest mean estimate (7.87; CI: 7.78-7.97). Although the mean marginal effect is less favourable for those living in Austria compared to those intending to stay (-0.27; CI: -0.81-0.26), the counterfactual analysis did not reveal any significant difference between Hungarians intending to stay and Hungarians living in Austria. Being a potential migrant is also associated with lower satisfaction compared to those intending to stay, although this relationship is neither significant (-0.26; CI: -0.61-0.08) (Figure 105).

Figure 105. Mean relationship satisfaction estimates by Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

In the economic activity categories, a high average estimate satisfaction appears among students (8.38; CI: 8.05-8.71). Also, high scores are found for the other inactive (8.16; CI: 7.8-8.51) and, again, estimates for the self-employed (8.01; CI: 7.72-8.29) are higher than those for the employed (7.86; CI: 7.77-7.96). The estimates for the retired (7.19; CI: 6.97-7.41), the unemployed (7.1; CI: 6.63-7.58) and the disabled (6.75; CI: 6.15-7.35) are well below these values. Average marginal effects compared to employed only for the disabled show a significant difference in satisfaction at the $p < 0.1$ level (-0.59; CI: -1.29-0.1). For entrepreneurs (0.02; CI: -0.28-0.34) and students (0.25; CI: -0.21-0.72) the model also indicates a positive average marginal effect compared to employed, but the difference is not significant. The Hungarian group significantly moderates the relationship between economic activity and relationship satisfaction in only one case. Those intending to stay show lower satisfaction among retired compared to employed (-0.53; CI: -0.93-0.14) (Figure 106).

Figure 106. Average marginal effects of economic status by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

The average estimated satisfaction of women (7.84; CI: 7.73-7.95) is slightly higher than that of men (7.75; CI: 7.64-7.86). The analysis does not show a general relationship between gender and satisfaction. After moderating effects are taken into account, the group intending to stay has the strongest female satisfaction surplus (0.16; CI: -0.03-0.35), while the average marginal effect among Hungarians living in Austria is negative (-0.27; CI: -0.71-0.17). Although the

moderating effect is not significant, it points to a slightly less favourable social relations of Hungarian women (including transnational mothers) living in Austria (Figure 107).

Figure 107. Average marginal effects of gender by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

For the education variable, the average estimates follow the usual ranking. The highest scores are for the highly educated (8.18; CI: 8.01-8.36), while the lowest are for the low educated (7; CI: 6.76-7.24). Belonging to any other category compared to the low-skilled was associated with significantly higher relationship satisfaction. The average marginal effect compared with the primary education category is 0.33 (CI: 0.00-0.66) in the case of vocational education; 0.38 (CI: 0.05-0.71) in the case of certificate; and 0.5 (CI: 0.12-0.87) in the case of tertiary education. The moderating effect appears in a way that those significant differences are only found among those who intend to stay and Hungarians living in Austria (in this group the average marginal effects are larger) (Figure 108).

Figure 108. Average marginal effects of education by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

People living in densely populated areas (8.01; CI: 7.86-8.16) and those living in intermediately dense areas (7.89; CI: 7.77-8) are more satisfied with their relationships based on the estimates, than those living in rural, thinly populated areas (7.44; CI: 7.3-7.59). The average marginal effects also show a clear positive relationship in favour of intermediate density (0.26; CI: 0.06-0.47) and high density (0.47; CI: 0.24-0.7) settlements. The advantage of these settlement types is most pronounced for those intending to stay (intermediate: 0.33; dense: 0.81), with a significant moderating effect. For Hungarians living in Austria, the effects are directed towards thinly populated settlements. In the „densely-thinly comparison”, the average marginal effect is -0.4 (CI: -1.08-0.27), but the relationship is not significant (Figure 109).

Figure 109. Average marginal effects of settlement type by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Satisfaction with relationships is also higher for those with larger households. An extra household member is expected to be connected with a 0.14 higher satisfaction value. This positive slope is pronounced for the two groups in Hungary, while the slope is much steeper for Hungarians in Austria. This may be due to the fact that in their case the household also includes people who have stayed in Hungary, so they may not live together. As expected, those with a partner (7.94; CI: 7.85-8.03) have a higher estimated average satisfaction with relationships than singles (7.49; CI: 7.35-7.63). The mean marginal effect is significant and directed towards those with a partner (0.42; CI: 0.23-0.62). The relationship is also positive in all of the Hungarian groups (not significant for potential migrants), but the role of the partner is more prominent for Hungarians in Austria. The average marginal effect in this group is 1.18 (CI: 0.63-1.73) (Figure 110).

Figure 110. Average marginal effects of having a partner by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

In terms of the number of friends, those with no friends have the lowest average satisfaction estimate (6.82; CI: 6.52-7.12). Compared to them, even those with one friend (7.49; CI: 7.29-7.7) have a much higher score. There is then a further jump for those with 2-4 friends (7.92; CI: 7.82-8.01). From here, however, the increase in the number of friends is no longer reflected in substantially higher and higher estimates. For 5-9 friends, the average estimate is 7.99 (CI: 7.79-8.18), while for 10 or more friends it is 8.04 (CI: 7.44-8.64). For all other categories, the average marginal effect is positive compared to the category with no friends. However, the effect is not significant for those with only one friend compared to those with no friends (0.29; CI: -0.17-0.75). The average marginal effect is nearly equal for 2-4 friends (0.61; CI: 0.18-1.04) and 5-9 friends (0.71; CI: 0.24-1.18), but the value nearly doubles for the „10 or more friends-no friend comparison” (1.24; CI: 0.09-2.38). Moderating effect analysis reveals that friends play the largest role in the satisfaction of potential migrants, with the average effect of 2-4 and 5-9 friends being significant and much higher than the values obtained for the full sample. For those intending to stay, the effect of 10 or more friends appears strong (1.59; CI: 0.05-3.13), while for Hungarians from Austria none of the comparisons show a significant relationship (Figure 111).

Figure 111. Average marginal effects of the number of friends by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Those who can count on financial or non-financial support have a higher mean satisfaction (7.87; CI: 7.79-7.96) than those who cannot (6.96; CI: 6.69-7.22). The mean marginal effect is almost identical to that observed for the partner variable (0.53; CI: 0.20-0.86). When including the moderating effect of the Hungarian group variable, the significant association with help is only found for potential migrants at the $p < 0.05$ level, but the average marginal effect is also positive for the other two groups (significant at the $p < 0.1$ level for Hungarians in Austria). For potential migrants, the effect is very strong (0.96; CI: 0.14-1.78). Thus, in addition to the number of friends, whether they can expect help from these many friends is also of paramount importance (Figure 112).

Figure 112. Average marginal effects of the potential of getting help by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

In addition to having friends, meeting them also shows higher average satisfaction estimates (8.11; CI: 8.02-8.21). However, there is no difference among those who do not meet their friends for financial or time constraints (7.06; CI: 6.81-7.3) or due to other reasons (7.12; CI: 6.95-7.28). The average marginal effect is higher in the „meeting-not meeting for other reasons comparison” (0.53; CI: 0.31-0.75) than for the „meeting-not meeting for financial or time constraints comparison” (0.15; CI: -0.18-0.5), and the latter is not significant. The moderating effect of the Hungarian group variable is appearing in a way, that for Hungarians in Austria, the mean marginal effect in the „meeting-not meeting for other reasons comparison” is weaker (0.22; CI: -0.55-1.05) than the overall sample effect and not significant. However, not meeting friends for financial or time constraints shows a positive effect compared to not meeting friends for other reasons (2.27; CI: 0.67-3.86) in this group. The same effect is found for those intending to stay (0.35; CI: 0.004-0.71). In the case of the potential migrants the average marginal effect in this comparison turns negative (-0.88; CI: -1.65-(-0.1)) (Figure 113).

Figure 113. Average marginal effects of meeting with friends by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Being a member of any civil society organisation (CSO) is also associated with higher mean satisfaction estimates (8.17; CI: 8.01-8.33 compared to 7.68 for non-members; CI: 7.6-7.77). The mean marginal effect is also positive, with membership associated with a 0.19 (CI: 0.004-0.39) satisfaction surplus (Figure 114). Membership does not show a significant relationship with satisfaction for those intending to stay (0.56; CI: -0.18-0.28), but there are clear positive relationships for potential migrants (0.46; CI: 0.01-0.92) and Hungarians living in Austria (0.47; CI: -0.02-0.97) (the latter significant at the $p < 0.1$ level).

Figure 114. Average marginal effects of being a member in a civil society organisation by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Substantial mean estimation differences are observed between the two ends of the social exclusion spectrum, between those who are totally excluded (6.57; CI: 5.95-7.18) and those who are absolutely not excluded (8.43; CI: 8.32-8.54). Compared to being totally excluded, only the absolute not excluded category reports a significant increase in satisfaction (1.14; CI: 0.41-1.86). The Hungarian group also moderates this relationship. Significant effects are only found among Hungarians in Austria. In this group, the mean marginal effect of "so-so" (2.19; CI: 0.74-3.64) and the mean marginal effect of "rather not" exclusion is also positive (3.67; CI: 1.58-4.56) (Figure 115).

Figure 115. Average marginal effects of social exclusion by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Trust in other members of society is associated with higher relationship satisfaction. The average marginal effect for the whole sample is 0.05 (0.01-0.09). The role of trust is most evident in the relationship satisfaction of potential migrants, with no significant relationship found in the group of Hungarians in Austria (-0.02; CI: -0.13-0.08).

6.4.2. Extended model for Austria

Satisfaction before migration shows a positive relationship with satisfaction now, the relationship is significant. The significant moderating effect of satisfaction with relationships before migration appears only in one case. This is the education variable, where the surplus of satisfaction associated with higher education is higher when satisfaction with relationships before migration was low. And for the partner variable, the surplus of satisfaction with the

provision of a partner is observed to be higher (but not significantly so) when satisfaction was higher before migration (average marginal effect at pre-migration satisfaction level 9 is 4.42; CI: 1.5-7.34). If one was less satisfied with one's relationships before migration, the presence of a current partner provides a slightly smaller advantage (3.06 at pre-migration satisfaction level 6; CI: 1.18-4.94).

The mean satisfaction estimates for those who frequently visit back to Hungary (7.5; CI: 7.19-7.81) are lower than those for infrequent visitors (7.72; CI: 7.42-8.02). The mean marginal effect is against frequent visitors (-0.58; CI: -1.24-(-0.08), the relationship is significant at the $p < 0.1$ level. In terms of reasons for migration, those who moved to help their future in Hungary have lower estimated values (6.72; CI: 6.16-7.29) than those who did not indicate this response (7.76; CI: 7.53-8). However, the average marginal effect is not significant (-0.14; CI: -1.05-0.77). The average estimate for those who moved out because of a relationship (7.88; CI: 7.36-8.41) is higher than those who did not indicate this reason (7.56; CI: 7.32-7.78), but the average marginal effect (-0.01; CI: -0.87-0.85) is not significant in this case either

Individuals who left their partner or child in Hungary (7.12; CI: 6.64-7.6) have lower estimated satisfaction than those who did not (8.09; CI: 7.8-8.38). While the average marginal effect indicates a negative effect associated with leaving a family member at home (-0.71; CI: -1.59-0.16), the relationship is not significant. However, the mean negative marginal effect of the family member staying at home is significant if relationship satisfaction was high before migration (-1.48 at pre-migration satisfaction value of 9; CI: -2.77-(-0.2)). When the variable family member staying at home are replaced by the variables partner staying at home and child staying at home, only the role of the child left behind is significant. Leaving a child behind has a mean marginal effect of -1.68 (CI: -2.98-(-0.39)). In the presence of a partner or a child staying at home, frequent visits already have a higher mean estimate (7.53 compared to 6.64 for infrequent visits). The mean marginal effect of frequent visits is still negative (-0.53; CI: -1.25-0.18), but is no longer significant.

Regarding the nationality of the partner, although respondents with Austrian partner have a higher average estimate (8.69; CI: 8.2-9.18) than those with a Hungarian one (7.76; CI: 7.44-8.07), the average marginal effect does not show a significant difference (-0.1 for the Austrian partner; CI: -0.91-0.69). However, in contrast to the Hungarian partner, the presence of a partner belonging to any other nationalities (non-Austrian and non-Hungarian) is associated with significantly lower relationship satisfaction at the $p < 0.1$ level (-1.66; CI: -3.43-0.09)). The close relationship between German language proficiency and relationship satisfaction is already evident from the mean estimates. Starting from not knowing German at all (5.5; CI: 3.34-7.66), there is a gradual increase in estimated satisfaction up to the level of native language proficiency (8.27; CI: 7.81-8.72). Compared to the category not knowing German at all, even basic proficiency is associated with a significant additional satisfaction (5.81; CI: 1.26-10.3), but the other categories indicating better language proficiency do not provide extra additional

satisfaction. No significant relationship appears when generalised trust is replaced by localised trust (trust in the residents of your neighbourhood) in the model.

6.5. Satisfaction with health

6.5.1. Model for the whole sample

The average estimates of health satisfaction are an excellent reflection of the healthy migrant phenomenon, i.e., that potential migrants enjoy excellent (subjective) health. The mean estimate for this group is 8.17 (CI: 7.99-8.34), which is well above that of those who want to stay (7.41; CI: 7.31-7.51). Hungarians living in Austria are in between the two groups, but closer to the potential migrants' score (7.9; CI: 7.7-8.11). After controlling for the other variables, there is no evidence of a surplus by being a potential migrant, but Hungarians living in Austria show a negative average marginal effect compared to the other two Hungarian groups, even if these differences are not significant at the $p < 0.05$ level (-0.48 in comparison with those intending to stay; CI: -1.03-0.06; $p = 0.08$) (Figure 116).

Figure 116. Mean health satisfaction estimates by Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Estimated differences in economic activity are also affected by age. The average estimate for students is the highest (8.57; CI: 8.22-8.92), while the average estimate for pensioners (5.72; CI: 5.49-5.95) and disabled (4.08; CI: 3.47-4.7) is the lowest. The mean estimate for employed persons is 7.92 (CI: 7.83-8.02). In contrast to employed persons, pensioners (-1.34; CI: -2.2-(-

0.49)) and disabled persons (-2.27; CI: -2.99-(-1.53)) show a negative mean marginal effect. A few moderating effects are worth highlighting. Other inactive persons enjoy a satisfaction surplus among those intending to stay (0.65; CI: 0.2-1.1) compared to employed persons, while among Hungarians in Austria this other inactive group have a negative average marginal effect (-1.64; CI: -3.2-(-0.07)). Potential migrants show an unemployment satisfaction surplus (1.55; CI: 0.6-2.5) (Figure 117).

Figure 117. Average marginal effects of economic status by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Most studies describe the relationship between age and health in terms of a U-shaped curve. This U-shape is most pronounced in the group of Hungarians in Austria. In contrast, for those who intend to stay, a slope is visible after the age of 40. This trend at the end of the life curve differs significantly between Hungarians intending to stay and Hungarians in Austria. The average estimate of health satisfaction for men is higher (7.75; CI: 7.64-7.86) than for women (7.53; CI: 7.42-7.64). The average marginal effect is also in favour of men (-0.131; CI: -0.3-0.03), but the difference is not significant. The average marginal effect between genders is closest to 0 in the group of Hungarians in Austria.

The ranking of educational attainment observed for the previous domains is also maintained in the average estimates of health satisfaction. The low-educated (6.59; CI: 6.35-6.84) are outperformed by those with a vocational degree (7.38; CI: 7.24-7.52), those with a certificate (7.84; CI: 7.71-7.97) and those with a tertiary education (8.2; CI: 8.02-8.38). The average marginal effects, while pointing in the expected direction towards higher education, are not

significant (0.31 in the „tertiary education-primary education comparison”; CI: -0.08-0.7). No significant relationship with the moderation of the Hungarian groups is found, with the only noteworthy difference being the larger „tertiary education-primary education” difference in the sample of Hungarians in Austria (Figure 118).

Figure 118. Average marginal effects of education by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

By type of settlement, the highest average satisfaction estimates are for those living in densely populated areas (7.73; CI: 7.58-7.89), followed by those living in intermediately dense areas (7.65; CI: 7.53-7.77) and thinly populated areas (7.52, CI: 7.37-7.67). The average marginal effects show an intermediate density superiority compared to living in sparsely populated areas (0.2; CI: -0.0009-0.4). This positive effect is observed in the two groups in Hungary. The „densely populated-thinly populated comparison” shows the opposite direction for Hungarians intending to stay and for Hungarians in Austria. In Austria, there is a perceived health advantage associated with living in rural areas (-0.97; CI: -1.6-(-0.32)), while in Hungary the effect is in the direction of densely populated settlements (0.33; CI: 0.03-0.64) (Figure 119).

Figure 119. Average marginal effects of settlement type by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

The average estimate for those living with a partner is higher (7.69; CI: 7.59-7.78) than for singles (7.53; CI: 7.39-7.67), but the average marginal effect (0.04; CI: -0.14-0.23) does not show a significant advantage of having a partner. The existence of peer relationships can have multiple effects on health. They may encourage joint exercise and health promotion activities, and may also protect mental health by reducing loneliness and depression. In the sample, those who can count on some help from friends and family (7.69; CI: 7.61-7.77) have higher mean satisfaction estimates than those who cannot (7.04; CI: 6.77-7.32). The average marginal effect is not significant in the total sample (0.17; CI: -0.16-0.52), but the moderating effect of the Hungarian groups is present and a significant positive effect is observed for Hungarians in Austria (1.4; CI: 0.12-2.69) (Figure 120).

Figure 120. Average marginal effects of the potential of getting help by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

The analysis also shows a positive relationship with the number of friends. Having just one friend is associated with a higher mean estimate (7.26; CI: 7.04-7.47) than having no friends (6.6; CI: 6.29-6.91). A further larger jump appears in the 2-4 friend category (7.75; CI: 7.64-7.85), and from there the differences level off (5-9 friends 7.96; 10 or more friends 7.82). The average marginal effect for the „2-4 friend-no friend comparison” (0.45; CI: 0.02-0.88) is significant at the $p < 0.05$ level and indicates a positive return for having friends. The moderating effect of the Hungarian groups does not appear. Those who do leisure activities have significantly higher mean estimate (8.26; CI: 8.14-8.38) than those who do not do so due to financial or time constraints (6.86; CI: 6.66-7.06) or other reasons (7.24; CI: 7.11-7.36). Recreational activity has an average marginal effect of 0.34 (CI: 0.04-0.64) compared to passivity due to limitation. The mean marginal effect of leisure activity is also positive against the mean marginal effect of not participating in leisure activities due to other reasons, but it is no longer significant (0.1; CI: -0.09-0.31). The absence of leisure activities due to limitation is the strongest in the sample of Hungarians in Austria. Even when compared to other reasons, dropping out due to lack of money or time has a significant negative (-1.33; CI: -2.5 (-0.41)) relationship with health-related satisfaction (Figure 121).

Figure 121. Average marginal effects of spending leisure time by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Significant differences in health satisfaction are found in the perception of social exclusion. The average estimate for those who experience total exclusion is 6.52 (5.89-7.15), while for those who absolutely do not experience exclusion it is 8.17 (CI: 8.05-8.28). The average marginal effect between these two categories is significant at the $p < 0.1$ level (0.63; CI: -0.1-1.38). After moderation, it is found that this relationship is strong for Hungarians in Austria. In their case, in contrast to total exclusion, even „rather not being excluded” is significantly associated with higher satisfaction at the $p < 0.1$ level (1.33; CI: -0.16-2.82) (Figure 122).

Figure 122. Average marginal effects of social exclusion by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Membership in CSOs is also a variable that can reflect health-conscious behaviour. Those who are members of a CSO have higher mean estimated satisfaction (7.75; CI: 7.59-7.92) compared to non-members (7.6; CI: 7.51-7.69). The average marginal effect is also positive, but not significant (0.16; CI: -0.04-0.36) for the total sample. This is because a negative effect (-0.02; CI: -0.28-0.22) is observed among those intending to stay, while the effect is positive as expected at $p < 0.05$ and $p < 0.1$ levels among potential migrants (0.53; CI: 0.04-1.02) and Hungarians in Austria (0.47; CI: -0.02-0.97) (Figure 123).

Figure 123. Average marginal effects of being a member in a civil society organisation by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

A one higher number of problems in the living environment is associated with lower health satisfaction for those intending to stay (-0.15; CI: -0.36-0.04, not significant) and potential migrants (-0.35; CI: -0.63-(-0.08)). Significant differences in satisfaction with health status are observed with respect to the financial situation of the respondent. Those who find it very difficult to meet expenses have a much lower mean estimated satisfaction (5.65; CI: 5.22-6.08) than those who find it very easy to cover expenses (9.1; CI: 8.68-9.52). Even the „with difficulties-with major difficulties comparison” is associated with higher satisfaction (0.59; CI: -0.01-1.2), which is significant at the $p < 0.1$ level. The average marginal effect for the „very easily-with major difficulties comparison” is 2.29 (CI: 1.55-3.03). The moderating effect indicates that the link between finances is especially closely associated with health-related satisfaction, among those who intend to stay in Hungary (Figure 124).

Figure 124. Average marginal effects of the ease of covering the expenses by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

There is a large difference in mean estimated satisfaction between those who experienced a long-term negative health effect from COVID (6.38; CI: 6.12-6.63) and those who did not (7.77; CI: 7.68-7.85). The mean marginal effect is 0.53 (CI: 0.21-0.86), with no long-term COVID effect associated with significantly higher health satisfaction. The effect is positive in all Hungarian subsamples, but is significant only for those intending to stay (0.51; CI: 0.15-0.88).

6.5.2. Extended model for Austria

The level of satisfaction with health before migration shows a significant positive relationship with current satisfaction. For the group of Hungarians in Austria, the moderating effect of pre-migration health status is reflected in the urbanity, gender and long COVID variables. For those who were dissatisfied with their health before migration, densely populated settlements are associated with higher health satisfaction (2.77 for pre-migration satisfaction score of 2; CI: 0.38-5.15). Conversely, those who were fully satisfied show a positive association with living in thinly populated settlements. Similarly, in the case of pre-migration satisfaction, women (pre-migration satisfaction score of 2: 1.9; CI: 0.24-3.56) show higher current satisfaction. For pre-migration satisfaction the relationship is not clear. The long-term health effects of COVID are most severe for those who were satisfied with their health before migration.

The mean estimated satisfaction of frequent visitors to Hungary (7.82; CI: 7.6-8.04) is lower than that of infrequent visitors (7.99; CI: 7.78-8.21), and the mean marginal effect is also against

frequent visitors (-0.29; CI: -0.76-0.18), but not significant. In addition to the possible tensions associated with frequent home visits, the possible purpose of home visits to seek medical care in Hungary may also point towards lower satisfaction. The positive impact of home visits is reflected in the emotional charge provided by the family. Those who send money home have a lower average satisfaction (7.82; CI: 7.61-8.03) than those who do not (8.03; CI: 7.75-8.31). However, the average marginal effect is not significant, pointing minimally against sending money home (-0.14; CI: -1.15-0.02). The analysis therefore does not suggest that sending money home takes significant resources away from spending on maintaining health or treating illness. There is evidence of lower satisfaction with health among those emigrating to establish a future in Hungary. The mean estimate for this group is 7.55 (CI: 7.15-7.95), while for those migrating for other reasons it is 7.97 (CI: 7.81-8.14). The relationship is significant at the $p < 0.1$ level (-0.55; CI: -1.14-0.02). This may suggest the role of overwork related to the need to meet goals as soon as possible.

6.6. Satisfaction with work-life balance

6.6.1. Model for the whole sample

Looking at the mean estimates of satisfaction with the use of time, the group of potential migrants shows a considerable lag (6.17; CI: 6.96-6.39) compared to Hungarians in Austria (6.8; CI: 6.56-7.04) and those intending to stay in Hungary (6.97; CI: 6.85-7.09). The difference between potential migrants and those intending to stay is significant, with the average marginal effect (-0.58; CI: -1.01-(-0.16)) showing lower satisfaction among potential migrants (Figure 125).

Figure 125. Mean time use satisfaction estimates by Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

In terms of economic activity, the average estimates for this domain do not show an employment advantage. The average estimated satisfaction with time use of employed persons is relatively low compared to the other groups (6.6; CI: 6.49-6.72). Only students have a lower value than this (6.53; CI: 6.12-6.94). Unsurprisingly, the average estimated satisfaction of retired people (7.58; CI: 7.31-7.86), other inactive people (7.29; CI: 6.85-7.72) and unemployed people (7.08; CI: 6.48-7.67) is also higher than that of employed or self-employed people (6.86; CI: 6.5-7.21). However, when comparing the mean effects with those of being employed, only the disadvantage of being a student (-0.79; CI: -1.4-(-0.18)) and the advantage of being unemployed (1.57; CI: 0.73-2.41) are significant after controlling for other variables. Student dissatisfaction is strongest among Hungarians in Austria (-1.074; CI: -2.01-(-0.13)). In contrast, the unemployment advantage is clearly due to the two groups in Hungary (1.46 for those intending to stay and 1.1 for potential migrants). The group of those intending to stay also shows a significant advantage of other inactive (0.56; CI: 0.006-1.15) and retired (0.56; CI: 0.06-1.05) in comparison with employed at the $p < 0.05$ level. In contrast, Hungarians in Austria show a more favourable entrepreneurial situation (1.07; CI: -0.05-2.2) (Figure 126).

Figure 126. Average marginal effects of economic activity by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

There is also a U-shaped relationship between satisfaction with the use of time and age. The upward trend for potential migrants in the 30-50 age range is lower than the upward trend for those who intend to stay.

The average estimated satisfaction is slightly higher for men (6.81; CI: 6.67-6.95) than for women (6.76; CI: 6.63-6.89). Although the average marginal effect is pointing towards men (0.02; CI: -0.17-0.23), no significant gender effect can be detected. The largest difference in this effect is found for potential migrants, while among Hungarians in Austria it is more favourable towards women. However, the differences are once again not significant (Figure 127).

Figure 127. Average marginal effects of gender by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

In terms of education, the differences are smaller compared to the domains presented so far. Moreover, the lowest mean estimates are not for the low-skilled (6.69; CI: 6.39-6.99), but for those with a vocational education (6.66; CI: 6.49-6.83). Highly qualified have a value of 7.15 (CI: 6.93-7.36). The average marginal effects are not significant in the whole sample, but a moderating effect of the Hungarian groups is present. Among Hungarians in Austria, the „tertiary education-primary education comparison” is associated with higher satisfaction (1.99; CI: 0.4-3.58) (Figure 128).

Figure 128. Average marginal effects of education by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

People living in densely populated (7.02; CI: 6.84-7.21) and intermediately densely populated (6.92; CI: 6.77-7.06) settlements have almost the same average estimated satisfaction, but those living in thinly populated settlements have a substantially lower average (6.32; CI: 6.14-6.51). This difference is also reflected in the average marginal effects. The average marginal effect of living in a densely populated settlement is 0.56 (CI: 0.27-0.86), while the value for living in an intermediately dense settlement is 0.39 (CI: 0.13-0.64) in comparison with the thinly dense reference group. These positive effects are the strongest among the group of those intending to stay. In contrast to living in a sparsely populated settlement, for potential migrants living in a densely populated settlement (0.54; CI: -0.04-0.12) and for Hungarians in Austria living in an intermediately dense settlement (0.63; CI: -0.11-1.38) show a positive relationship at the $p < 0.1$ level (Figure 129).

Figure 129. Average marginal effects of settlement type by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

For the partner variable, this is the first domain where the average estimate is higher when there is no partner (6.88; CI: 6.71-7.05) than when there is a partner (6.74; CI: 6.62-6.86). The average marginal effect is also negative (-0.17; CI: -0.41-0.07), but its relationship with satisfaction is not significant. In the group of Hungarians in Austria, the average marginal effect is the only one pointing towards the existence of a partner (0.12; CI: -0.53-0.78), but this relationship is not significant either. Although the mean estimated satisfaction of the group with no friends (6.41; CI: 6.03-6.79) is lower than the group with at least 10 friends (7.68; CI: 6.95-8.41), no significant mean marginal effects are found for the number of friends. Differences at the $p < 0.1$ level appear when introducing the moderating effect. Compared to those without friends, having only one friend for those intending to stay, 5-9 friends for potential migrants and 10 or more friends for Hungarians from Austria show a positive relationship with higher satisfaction (Figure 130).

Figure 130. Average marginal effects of the number of friends by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

In addition to the number of friends, meeting friends does not show a significant relationship with satisfaction with time use. Higher mean estimated satisfaction is found for those who spend time doing leisure activities (7.13; CI: 6.99-7.28) than for those who do not do so for some limitation (6.09; CI: 5.85-6.33) or other reason (6.66; CI: 6.5-6.81). The average marginal effects are positively significant in favour of leisure in all comparisons (0.83 in comparison with passivity due to limitation and 0.55 in comparison with not participating in leisure activities for other reasons). There is no significant difference between the „no leisure activity” categories. The relationships shown are due to the two groups in Hungary. For Hungarians in Austria, none of the effects are significant, with leisure time expenditure showing a negative effect compared to passivity for other reasons (-0.31; CI: -1.01-0.39) (Figure 131).

Figure 131. Average marginal effects of spending leisure time by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Compared to the previous domains, the differences in social exclusion are smaller between those who are totally excluded (6.52; CI: 5.76-7.29) and those who perceive no exclusion at all (7.09; CI: 6.95-7.22). The average marginal effects are not significant for the whole sample. However, in the group of Hungarians in Austria, even the response "so-so" was associated with significantly higher satisfaction compared to total exclusion (1.87; CI: 0.01-3.73) (Figure 132).

Figure 132. Average marginal effects of social exclusion by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Those who are members of a CSO are slightly more satisfied with their time (6.87; CI: 6.67-6.87) than those who are not (6.76; CI: 6.65-6.87). The mean marginal effect is significant but points to a disadvantage for those who are more likely to be involved in civic life (-0.28; CI: -0.05-(-0.3)). This effect is significant at the $p < 0.05$ level for those who intend to stay (-0.34; CI: -0.6-(-0.05)). For the group of Hungarians in Austria, the effect is not significant, but it is pointing towards the benefit civic participation (0.34; CI: -0.26-0.95) (Figure 133).

Figure 133. Average marginal effects of being a member in a civil society organisation by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

The more favourable financial situation implies higher average estimates. Those who find it very difficult to meet expenses (5.86; CI: 5.34-6.38) have lower values than those who find it very easy to cover the finances (7.52; CI: 7.22-7.81). The average marginal effects also point to a positive relationship between financial satisfaction and time use. In contrast to the „with major difficulties” answer, even the „with difficulties” option is associated with significantly higher satisfaction (1.06; CI: 0.37-1.76). The relationship is stronger in the two groups in Hungary. For Hungarians in Austria, the average marginal effects point towards the easier coverage of expenses, but the confidence interval extends slightly below zero. The association between respondent's health status and satisfaction with time use is significant only for potential migrants. In contrast to poor health, even fair health is associated with a surplus in satisfaction (2.57; CI: 0.81-4.33) (Figure 134).

Figure 134. Average marginal effects of the ease of covering the expenses by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

6.6.2. Extended model for Austria

Satisfaction with the pre-migration period does not appear as a moderator. No significant marginal effects are found for reasons for migration. The largest difference is found in the category of helping to establish a future in Hungary, where the average estimate for those who selected this response (6.31; CI: 5.72-6.9) is lower than for those who migrated for other reasons (6.87; CI: 6.63-7.11). The average marginal effect is -0.42 (CI: -1.28-0.42). The mean estimated satisfaction of those who rarely move home is slightly higher (6.8; CI: 6.49-7.12) than that of those who move home frequently (6.77; CI: 6.45-7.1). The non-significant relationship (-0.46; CI: -1.17-0.24) provides no evidence of a potential time burden associated with moving home. There is also a negative association between family member staying at home and satisfaction, but this effect is not significant (-0.58; CI: -1.34-0.16).

6.7. Satisfaction with public services

6.7.1. Model for the whole sample

The satisfaction advantage of Hungarians in Austria is greatly reflected in their satisfaction with public services. The average estimated satisfaction of Hungarians in Austria is 7.42 (CI: 7.16-7.68), of those who want to stay 5.51 (5.39-5.64), while that of those who want to leave Hungary is only 5.02 (4.79-5.24). The average marginal effect is significant for those living in Austria compared to both groups in Hungary. In comparison with those who want to stay, the average marginal effect is 1.6 (CI: 0.9-2.38), and in relation to potential migrants it is even higher at

2.04 (CI: 1.2-2.8). Potential migrants also suffer a satisfaction disadvantage compared to those who want to stay, with an average marginal effect of -0.39 (CI: -0.84-0.05), significant at the $p < 0.1$ level (Figure 135).

Figure 135. Mean public service satisfaction estimates by Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

In terms of economic activity, disabled people have the lowest mean estimate (4.92; CI: 4.12-5.72), while entrepreneurs have the highest (6.11; CI: 5.72-6.49). The mean marginal effects show no significant relationship between economic activity and satisfaction with public services. However, with the introduction of the moderating effect, a satisfaction surplus associated with the other inactives appear compared to those who are employed, among those who intend to stay (0.77; CI: 0.19-1.35). The average estimated satisfaction is highest in young adulthood, then falls sharply and starts to rise again with a modest slope around age 70. For Hungarians living in Austria, however, there is no such collapse in their 30s and 40s. Around age 40, for example, the satisfaction surplus of Hungarians living in Austria is 2.15 (CI: 0.87-3.44) compared to those who want to stay (Figure 136).

Figure 136. Average marginal effects of economic status by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

The average estimated satisfaction is higher for men (5.74; CI: 5.6-5.89) than for women (5.67; CI: 5.53-5.81). The average marginal effect also confirms the association with the gender variable, with women being less satisfied (-0.22; CI: -0.48-(-0.005)). The effect is mainly due to the two groups in Hungary, with the average marginal effect for Hungarians in Austria being only -0.02. Turning to the education variable, although the satisfaction of highly educated people is higher (6.16; CI: 5.93-6.39) than that of those with a certificate (5.67; CI: 5.5-5.83), those with a vocational school degree (5.61; CI: 5.42-5.79) or those with low qualifications (5.27; CI: 4.95-5.59), no significant relationship between education and satisfaction with public services can be found. There is no moderating effect of Hungarian group variable.

Satisfaction once again reflects the disadvantaged role of being at the bottom of the settlement hierarchy. Those living in sparsely populated settlements (5.49; CI: 5.3-5.69) have the lowest average estimate, followed by those living in densely populated settlements (5.74; CI: 5.54-5.93) and then those living in intermediately populated settlements (5.81; CI: 5.66-5.97). The average marginal effect in the „intermediate-thin comparison” is significant (0.24; CI: -0.02-0.5) at the $p < 0.1$ level. This difference is due to the group of those intending to stay, for whom the effect is 0.35 (CI: 0.04-0.67). In the „dense-thin comparison”, the potential migrant group is the only one where the average marginal effect is in the direction of dense settlements (0.83; CI: 0.19-1.47), furthermore this relationship is significant (Figure 137).

Figure 137. Average marginal effects of settlement type by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Again, the presence of a partner was associated with a higher mean satisfaction estimate (5.78; CI: 5.66-5.91) than its absence (5.35-5.71). However, there is no significant relationship between this variable and satisfaction with public services (0.09; CI: -0.16-0.34). In terms of social exclusion, the average estimates do not show a clear trend, with those who are totally excluded (5.48; CI: 4.66-6.29) being higher than those who are rather excluded (4.82; CI: 4.41-5.22). As well as those indicating a feeling of rather not being excluded have higher mean estimates (6.01; CI: 5.82-6.21) than those who experience absolutely no exclusion (5.59; CI: 5.44-5.74). The mean marginal effects do not show a significant relationship. However, the moderating effect of the Hungarian groups appears and for Hungarians in Austria, a relationship appears to exist between feelings of exclusion and satisfaction with public services. For this group, even uncertainty ("so-so") is associated with significantly higher satisfaction (2.62; CI: 0.64-4.6) compared to total exclusion. Compared to this effect, the „absolutely not excluded-totally excluded comparison” provides only a slightly higher average marginal effect (2.98; CI: 0.93-5.03) (Figure 138).

Figure 138. Average marginal effects of social exclusion by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Average estimates of satisfaction with public services increase as an individual's financial situation improves. The lowest score is for those who find it a major difficulty to meet their expenses (3.4; CI 2.92-4.02), while the highest score is for those who find it easy to meet their expenses (6.42; CI: 6.1-6.74). Even in the „with difficulties-with major difficulties comparison” (1.16; CI: 0.38-1.92), a significant relationship between better financial situation and higher satisfaction is already evident. The average marginal effect is even larger in the „very easily-with major difficulties comparison”, 2.12 (CI: 1.17-3.07). The relationship is the strongest for those intending to stay, and for potential migrants it is significant in only one comparison (with difficulties-with major difficulties) (Figure 139).

Figure 139. Average marginal effects of the ease of covering the expenses by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Based on health status, the mean estimates for those in bad health are lower (5.08; CI: 4.68-5.48) than those in very good health (5.84; CI: 5.69-5.99). However, the mean marginal effects do not show a significant relationship. In fact, for those who want to stay, a relationship appears where those in very good health are more dissatisfied with public services than those in poor health (-0.76; CI: -1.4(-0.12)).

There is also a strong positive association between the level of institutional trust and satisfaction with public services (0.18; CI: 0.13-0.23). The association is slightly stronger for those intending to stay (0.23; CI: 0.18-0.28) than for potential migrants (0.14; CI: 0.04-0.24). In contrast, the association is not significant for Hungarians in Austria (0.02; CI: -0.16-0.21).

6.7.2. Extended model for Austria

In general, there is a slight downward slope in the relationship between satisfaction before migration and current satisfaction. Low satisfaction before migration is associated with high satisfaction now. And satisfaction before migration is associated with current dissatisfaction. This relationship is very strong for the low skilled, with a much steeper slope than for the other groups.

6.8. Satisfaction with green areas

6.8.1. Model for the whole sample

Hungarians in Austria were the most satisfied with green spaces (7.16; CI: 6.9-7.42), based on average estimates. Potential migrants (6.84; CI: 6.6-7.07) and those intending to stay (6.9; CI: 6.76-7.03) have almost the same values. The mean marginal effects do not indicate a significant relationship between the Hungarian groups and satisfaction (Figure 140).

Figure 140. Mean green area satisfaction estimates by Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Differences in economic activity and gender variables are not significantly associated with satisfaction. In terms of moderating effects, among those intending to stay, students are associated with significantly lower satisfaction than employed at the $p < 0.1$ level (-0.87; CI: -1.7-0.03). Among the categories of education, the highest mean estimate is for highly educated (7.4; CI: 7.17-7.64), while the lowest is for low-educated (5.99; CI: 5.65-6.32). Having a certificate (0.45; CI: 0.003-0.9) and being highly qualified (0.63; CI: 0.12-1.14) are associated with significantly higher satisfaction in comparison with primary education. The difference in the „vocational-primary qualified comparison” (0.38; CI: -0.06-0.83) is significant at the $p < 0.1$ level. These effects are pointing towards the more highly educated categories in all Hungarian groups, but are significant only for the potential migrant group (Figure 141).

Figure 141. Average marginal effects of education by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

On average, those living in densely populated settlements (7.27; CI: 7.07-7.47) are the most satisfied with green spaces, followed by those living in intermediately dense settlements (7.16; CI: 7.01-7.32) and then by those living in sparsely populated settlements (6.19; CI: 5.99-6.39). Living in an intermediately (0.91; CI: 0.64-1.19), and in a densely (1.15; CI: 0.83-1.47) populated settlement is associated with a significant satisfaction surplus compared to living in a thinly populated settlement. These effects are strongest for those who want to stay in Hungary. For Hungarians in Austria, there is no significant relationship, and the mean marginal effect in the „densely-thinly comparison” is negative (-0.35; CI: -1.17-0.45).

As the burden of financial expenditure decreases, higher average estimates of satisfaction with green spaces can be expected. The value for the „with major difficulties” category is 5.18 (CI: 4.62-5.73), while the value for the „very easily” group is 7.73 (CI: 7.18-8.28). The average estimated satisfaction is the highest for the „easily” option (7.74; CI: 7.42-8.07). Based on the average marginal effects, a significant relationship is found between easier coverage of financial burdens and higher satisfaction with green spaces. Already in the „with difficulties-with major difficulties comparison” a significant satisfaction surplus is found for the „with difficulties” group (1.12; CI: 0.33-1.91). In the „easily-with major difficulties comparison” this value rises to 2.16 (CI: 1.36-2.96). The effect is due to the two groups in Hungary. For Hungarians in Austria, there is no significant relationship between financial situation and satisfaction with green spaces. However, a significant mean marginal effect appears in the „I

do not know-with major difficulties comparison” for Hungarians who want to stay (3.03; CI: 1.34-4.73) and Hungarians in Austria (3.03; CI: 1.34-4.73).

In relation to health, a relationship emerges among potential migrants in terms of self-reported better health being associated with less satisfaction with green spaces. The average marginal effect in „very good health-bad health comparison” is (-1.88; CI: -3.71-(-0.05)) (Figure 142).

Figure 142. Average marginal effects of perceived health by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

The average estimate for those with a partner is slightly higher (6.96; CI: 6.83-7.09) than for those without a partner (6.85; CI: 6.67-7.04). The average marginal effect is not significant for the whole sample (0.09; CI: -0.16-0.35), driven by the opposite trends between those who want to stay (-0.23; CI: -0.54-0.08) on the one hand and potential migrants (0.74; CI: 0.12-1.35) and Hungarians in Austria (0.57; CI: -0.09-1.2) on the other. The positive effect is significant at the $p < 0.1$ level for Hungarians in Austria, and at the $p < 0.05$ level for potential migrants. The presence of a child is significantly ($p < 0.1$) associated with higher green space satisfaction (0.61; CI: -0.02-1.26) only in the sample of Hungarians in Austria. A relationship between feelings of safety and green space satisfaction is also found. Those who think that the neighbourhood is very unsafe (6.09; CI: 5.4-6.78) have a lower mean estimated satisfaction value, while the highest estimate is observed in the group of those who gave the very safe answer (7.25; CI: 7.08-7.42). According to the average marginal effects, the „fairly safe-very unsafe comparison” (0.72; CI: -0.04-1.5) is significant at the $p < 0.1$ level, while the „very safe-very unsafe comparison” (1.08; CI: 0.3-1.8) is significant at the $p < 0.05$ level. These effects are observed

for those intending to stay, with no association between safety and green space satisfaction for Hungarians in Austria. Also, in the two groups in Hungary, the model shows that noise pollution in the neighbourhood is associated with lower green space satisfaction (-0.892; CI: -1.26(-0.52)). The average marginal effect for Hungarians in Austria also points in the same direction (-0.51; CI: -1.23-0.19), but the relationship is not significant.

6.8.2. Extended model for Austria

The impact of noise pollution is more closely related to satisfaction with green space in cases where satisfaction was higher before migration. The average estimated satisfaction of those who emigrated to Austria to help establishing a future back in Hungary is lower (6.31; CI: 6.78-6.85) than those who did not (7.35; CI: 7.13-7.57). The relationship is significant, with a mean marginal effect of -0.88 (CI: -1.61(-0.15)). This effect is particularly strong for those who were satisfied with green spaces in Hungary. The opposite trend is observed for those who moved out because of a relationship. When this response is marked, the average marginal effect is positive, but not significant (0.57; CI: -0.13-1.28).

6.9. Summary of findings

6.9.1. Satisfaction with job

The desire to stay is associated with higher satisfaction compared to the potential migrant status. An important link can be found with the coverage of financial expenditure. Those who can pay their expenses more easily are more satisfied with their job. Even getting to a salary level where the respondent can cover the expenses with some difficulty is very important for Hungarians in Austria (this group has a stronger finance-job satisfaction relationship). This level provides the necessary satisfaction floor, the next jump in satisfaction comes only at the „very easily able to cover” level for Hungarians in Austria. Having a contract shorter than six months is preferable to a longer one. This is particularly noticeable for those who want to stay in Hungary. Contempt is detrimental to job satisfaction, and for Hungarians in Austria being looked down upon is even more detrimental than for the groups in Hungary. If the job limits the individual's leisure time, job satisfaction is lower, especially for potential migrants. The opportunity for promotion at work is also related to satisfaction, important for those who want to stay but not for potential migrants. Having a partner is associated with higher satisfaction, and this is particularly important for job satisfaction among Hungarians in Austria. In the case of overqualification, lower job satisfaction can be expected, especially if the individual was satisfied with his/her job before migration. Those who are more dissatisfied with their job in Austria are more likely to visit home than those who are satisfied.

6.9.2. Satisfaction with income

Compared to the employed, students, the disabled and the unemployed have lower levels of satisfaction. However, among those who intend to stay in Hungary, satisfaction is higher in the case of self-employed than that of the employed. Higher education is associated with higher income satisfaction, the association is strongest for Hungarians in Austria and weakest for potential migrants. By settlement type, there is a higher satisfaction of living in intermediately dense settlements compared to thinly populated ones. Having a partner also has a positive link with higher income satisfaction. Suffering deprivation and difficulty in meeting expenses is associated with lower satisfaction. Ease of meeting expenses is particularly important for Hungarians living in Austria, while the association with deprivation is stronger in Hungary. Being looked down upon because of one's financial situation also appears to be detrimental. For Hungarians in Austria, the existence of remittances is associated with higher satisfaction as opposed to a refusal to answer the question on remittances.

6.9.3. Satisfaction with housing conditions

Women are more satisfied with their housing, especially in Hungary. Satisfaction is higher in the case of higher education, but in the group of Hungarians in Austria, a significant relationship is found only in the high education-low education comparison. In Hungary, higher satisfaction is found for living in densely and intermediately populated settlements, while in Austria it is found in thinly populated municipalities. Satisfaction is also higher in this domain when a partner is present. Owning a house/apartment is particularly important, but only in Hungary. Overcrowding and a higher number of problems related to housing and living environment are associated with lower levels of satisfaction. Those who can easily cover their expenses are more satisfied with their housing. Contrary to the previous trend of this variable, this relationship is stronger in the two groups in Hungary, while the relationship is not significant for Hungarians in Austria. For Hungarians in Austria, higher satisfaction is found among men who were dissatisfied with their accommodation before migration and among formerly dissatisfied persons in this domain who now live in thinly populated settlements. However, for high levels of satisfaction with housing before migration, the negative association between overcrowding and environmental problems is stronger. Higher levels of satisfaction are observed for people who have emigrated earlier and for those who have emigrated to help their future back in Hungary.

6.9.4. Satisfaction with social relationships

Among those who intend to stay, retired people are more dissatisfied than employed people. Higher education is associated with higher satisfaction, with average marginal effects being stronger in the Austrian sample. Living in a more densely populated settlement is associated with higher satisfaction, but only in Hungary. Larger household size and having a partner are associated with higher satisfaction. For Hungarians in Austria, there is no significant relationship with the number of people in the household, but the presence of a partner is particularly important. The number of friends and the possibility to ask for help are also associated with higher satisfaction, with the strongest connection in the potential migrant group. Meeting friends is also favourable in the overall sample, with Hungarians living in Austria showing a disadvantage of not meeting friends for other reasons, i.e., not due to financial or time constraints.

Membership in a CSO is associated with higher satisfaction, especially among potential migrants and Hungarians living in Austria. For the group in Austria, the role of social exclusion is particularly detrimental. There is also a significant association with generalised trust, but only in Hungary. For higher relationship satisfaction before migration, current satisfaction is also higher. Frequent visits home is associated with lower satisfaction than infrequent visits home. Having a partner or child at home is associated with lower levels of satisfaction, of which having a relationship with a child is significant. There is no difference between Hungarian and Austrian partner in terms of nationality, but partners from other countries show lower satisfaction compared to having a Hungarian partner. A strong relationship is observed between higher German language skills and higher satisfaction.

6.9.5. Satisfaction with health

Living in Austria can be associated with a lack of satisfaction compared with those who want to stay in Hungary. The satisfaction of disabled and retired people is lower than that of employed people. In terms of settlement types, the trend observed so far remains relevant, with a significant advantage of living in intermediately, and especially living in densely populated settlements in Hungary. In Austria, living in a thinly populated municipality is linked to higher satisfaction. For Hungarians in Austria, the possibility of seeking financial or non-material help is associated with higher health satisfaction. Having more friends and being active in leisure activities also show a positive association. Lower satisfaction is observed among Hungarians in Austria who do not engage in leisure activities due to financial or time constraints. In Austria, social exclusion is also associated with lower satisfaction. Higher satisfaction is found for those with a membership in a civil society organisation. The association with health problems in the neighbourhood and financial opportunities (negative for the former and positive for the latter) is found in Hungary. Lower satisfaction is found if the individual has had a COVID infection with long-lasting effects.

There is a positive link between satisfaction before migration and satisfaction now. The negative relationship between COVID and satisfaction is stronger when satisfaction was higher before migration. People with low satisfaction before migration are currently more satisfied living in thinly populated settlements. The problem of stress due to overwork may arise for those who moved to Austria to establish their future in Hungary, as they are expected to have significantly lower health satisfaction

6.9.6. Satisfaction with work-life balance

Intention to stay in Hungary is associated with higher satisfaction than potential migrant status. Students are more dissatisfied (especially in Austria) than employed people. However, compared to employed people, the unemployed are generally more satisfied, and in some groups “other inactive” status and being self-employed are also associated with higher satisfaction. Higher satisfaction associated with higher education is only found among Hungarians in Austria. Compared to thinly populated settlements, living in a densely populated settlement is associated with higher satisfaction. This is mainly the case in the two groups in Hungary, for the Hungarians in Austria the advantage of intermediate density can be observed. In the absence of friends, satisfaction is lower, but the significant relationship differs by friend number categories in each Hungarian groups. In Hungary, there is a stronger relationship between leisure activity and satisfaction than in the group of Hungarians in Austria. In Hungary, membership in a civic organisation, bad health status and difficulty covering the expenses are associated with lower satisfaction, whereas in Austria social exclusion is linked to disadvantage.

6.9.7. Satisfaction with public services

The satisfaction advantage of Hungarians in Austria is evident compared to groups in Hungary. Even the intention to stay in Hungary is associated with higher satisfaction than being a potential migrant. The advantage of Hungarians in Austria is particularly significant for middle-aged people. A satisfaction disadvantage is observed for women. Compared to living in a thinly populated settlement, living in an intermediately populated settlement (among those intending to stay) and living in a densely populated settlement (among potential migrants) is also associated with higher satisfaction. The negative association with social exclusion reappears in Austria. For those intending to stay, easier coverage of financial expenses is associated with higher satisfaction. The relationship between institutional trust and satisfaction is only found in Hungary. Low satisfaction before migration is associated with high satisfaction now. And satisfaction before migration is associated with current dissatisfaction.

6.9.8. Satisfaction with green areas

A significant positive association with education is found only for potential migrants. The groups in Hungary again show a higher satisfaction with living in more densely populated settlements. In the whole sample, a relationship is found between easier coverage of financial expenditure and higher satisfaction with green space. In the two groups in Hungary, feelings of safety and lack of noise problems also show a positive relationship with satisfaction with green spaces. Hungarians in Austria have higher satisfaction when having a partner and a child. Those moving to Hungary to establish their future back in Hungary are less satisfied with green spaces.

6.10. Satisfaction inequalities

In addition to satisfaction averages and estimated averages, it is also worth looking at the inequalities in satisfaction. To identify the inequalities, we have used the standard deviation method used in the literature. Inequalities in each domain were examined separately by the Hungarian groups and by gender, education and economic status.

Figure 143. Inequalities by dimensions among the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

In general, the largest inequalities are found in the job satisfaction domain (Figure 143). In this domain, the lowest inequality is found among Hungarians in Austria. Inequality is particularly low for low-skilled Hungarians abroad, and inequality is also lower for men than for women in Austria. Inequality increases towards those with certificate and the highly qualified. Those intending to stay have higher inequality than the potential migrants. Outstanding inequality characterises the low-skilled group. Inequality in income satisfaction is lowest for Hungarians in Austria and highest for potential migrants. For Hungarians in Austria, a lower inequality for men compared to women is also observed in this domain, which is not observed in the two groups in Hungary. In Hungary, greater inequality is observed for the low-skilled, other inactive and student groups. Austria also shows a jump in student income satisfaction inequality. Inequalities in housing satisfaction are among the lowest overall. Within the low-educated group in Hungary, greater inequality is observed, while in Austria this group has almost the same level of satisfaction. In Austria, greater inequality is also found for the housing domain

among the student group. Satisfaction with social relations is very evenly balanced in Hungary, but there is greater inequality among Hungarians in Austria. Especially among the highly educated, there is a degree of inequality that is not present in this educational group in Hungary. In terms of health, satisfaction inequality is much lower among the potential migrant group than among Hungarians in Austria or those who want to stay. Among Hungarians in Austria, women and a group of low-skilled are exposed to inequality. For those who want to stay, it is also the low-skilled, but here it is men who are at risk. And for potential migrants, inequalities are high among the inactive. In general, health inequalities decrease with higher educational attainment. In terms of satisfaction with time use, the sample is rather homogeneous, especially the sub-sample of Hungarians in Austria. In the groups in Hungary, greater inequality is observed among the low educated.

In terms of the inequality between domains, the group of Hungarians in Austria can be characterised by almost the same average estimates in all domains based on the models (Figure 144). Only satisfaction with health, social relationships and public services jump out slightly, while satisfaction with time use deviates in the negative direction. In the two groups in Hungary, we find much greater inequalities. Both potential migrants and those who want to stay have the lowest levels of satisfaction with income and public services. On the upside, satisfaction with health jumps out for the group of potential migrants, while satisfaction with housing is slightly higher for those intending to stay. The largest differences between Hungarians in Austria and those intending to stay are in the average estimates of satisfaction with public services (1.9 difference in favour of Austria), income (1.26 difference in favour of Austria) and health (0.49 difference), while satisfaction with work (0.02 difference in favour of those intending to stay) is the most similar between the two groups. The highest similarity between those who want to stay and potential migrants is found in satisfaction with green areas (0.05 difference in favour of those who want to stay) and with social relations (0.18 difference in favour of those who want to stay). In the other domains, however, the difference between the two groups is above 0.45. The main difference is in satisfaction with income (0.91 for those who want to stay).

Figure 144. Mean estimates for different satisfaction dimensions by Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

6.11. Correlations between domains

In the following, we examine the correlation between the domains¹¹ in the three Hungarian groups. For those intending to stay, the strongest relationship is found between income and finances (Figure 145). Job satisfaction also shows a correlation with these variables above 0.5. The second strongest relationship in the matrix is found between satisfaction with housing and satisfaction with social relationships. Higher social satisfaction is also associated with higher satisfaction with health. Compared to preliminary expectations, the relationships between work-time use and income-health are weakly correlated at less than 0.4. A moderate relationship is observed between green spaces and housing, which is maintained in the other groups, presented in the following sections.

Figure 145. Correlation between satisfaction domains among those, who intend to stay in Hungary. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

¹¹ Since job satisfaction is also included in the matrix, these matrices are restricted to the employed group. Removing job satisfaction and income satisfaction, we also ran correlations for the full sample (students, retired), these did not differ significantly from the trends for employed presented.

The correlation values are generally higher for those who intend to leave Hungary (Figure 146). A stronger relationship is observed for „time use-public services” and „time-use-financial situation” pairs compared to those intending to stay.

Figure 146. Correlation between satisfaction domains among those, who intend to leave Hungary. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

For Hungarians in Austria, the correlation between the domains can be described as moderate in most cases (Figure 147). This correlation matrix is similar to that for those who want to stay. It is observed that the relationships with the public services domain are stronger in this group. A slightly stronger correlation is found between work and housing and between health and time use compared to those intending to stay.

Figure 147. Correlation between satisfaction domains among the Hungarians living in Austria. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

The correlation matrix of pre-migration satisfaction scores of Hungarians currently living in Austria is similar to that of potential migrants (Figure 148). Compared to the post-migration graph, typically weaker correlations are observed. The correlation between housing and satisfaction with work and housing and income is much weaker than after migration. However, the correlation between financial situation and income is the strongest in this figure.

Figure 148. Correlation between the pre-migration satisfaction domains among the Hungarians living in Austria. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

6.12. Correlation with overall satisfaction with life

Satisfaction with life in general is most closely related to financial situation and housing satisfaction (Figure 149). These domains are followed by job and social relationships. There is a stronger relationship between life satisfaction and the other domains among those living in Austria and those who want to stay. The relationship with health is stronger for those intending to stay, while for Hungarians in Austria the correlation is higher for satisfaction with time use and public services. For potential migrants, financial situation and housing are more closely related to life satisfaction, while the relationship with health is weaker than for other groups. The overall satisfaction with life before migration of Hungarians in Austria was also most strongly correlated with material goods, with the strongest correlation with the individual's own income in this column.

Figure 149. Correlation between the satisfaction domains and overall life satisfaction by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

7. The variables associated with life satisfaction among Hungarians living in Hungary and Austria

7.1.1. Model for the whole sample

The average estimates of life satisfaction reflect the surplus of satisfaction found in the majority of domains that is characteristic of Hungarians in Austria. The mean estimate for this group is 7.44 (CI: 7.26-7.63), with only a small difference for those who want to stay in Hungary (7.26; CI: 7.18-7.35), but a much larger difference in comparison with potential migrants (6.87; CI: 6.72-7.03). After controlling for other variables, being a Hungarian in Austria does not show a significant association with higher life satisfaction. In itself, therefore, living in Austria does not make a person more satisfied. Potential migrants, however, show a significant lag compared to those who want to stay (-0.35; CI: -0.71-(-0.004)) (Figure 150). There is therefore a link between the intention to migrate to Hungary and overall satisfaction with life.

Figure 150. Mean overall life satisfaction estimates by Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

In terms of economic activity, students have the highest mean estimate (8.04; CI: 7.73-8.36). Entrepreneurs (7.71; CI: 7.45-7.97) differ from employed (7.29; CI: 7.2-7.37) by almost 0.4. The lowest average estimates were for the unemployed (5.81; CI: 5.36-6.25) and the disabled (5.63; CI: 5.08-6.17). A significant student satisfaction surplus (0.5; CI: 0.05-0.95) and an unemployed (-0.71; CI: -1.33-(-0.108)) deficit are observed compared to the employed reference group. The student advantage is significant only for those who want to stay (0.71; CI:

0.1-1.32). However, the unemployment deficit is not significant in this group. A much stronger negative relationship between unemployment and satisfaction is observed for Hungarians in Austria (-4.39; CI: -7.14-(-1.38)) than for potential migrants (-0.82; CI: -1.7-0.05)) (Figure 151).

Figure 151. Average marginal effects of economic status by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

The relationship between age and satisfaction is described by a slight U-shape. The surplus of satisfaction of Hungarians in Austria compared to those who want to stay is mainly observed in young and old age, but the differences are not significant. In the gender variable there is little difference in the mean estimates. The value for women is 7.22 (CI: 7.12-7.32), while for men it is 7.2 (CI: 7.1-7.3). The average marginal effect is not significant (0.007; CI: -0.14-0.16) and there is no moderating effect by the Hungarian group variable. The average marginal effect points towards women for those intending to stay (0.06 CI: -0.12-0.25), while for men the effect is the largest among potential migrants (-0.1; CI: -0.45-0.24).

In terms of educational attainment, the average estimate for the low-skilled (6.29; CI: 6.07-6.51) lags behind that of those with a vocational school degree (7.05; CI: 6.93-7.17) and those with a certificate (7.32; CI: 7.21-7.44). There is then another jump in the estimates towards the high-skilled (7.72; CI: 7.57-7.88). The model indicates a significant relationship at the $p < 0.05$ level only in the „vocational-primary education comparison”. The average marginal effect is slightly weaker for those with tertiary education (0.31; CI: -0.05-0.67) than for those with vocational education (0.33; CI: 0.01-0.64). However, the significant relationship in the

„vocational-primary education comparison” is only found in the group of those intending to stay (0.5; CI: 0.19-0.81). For Hungarians in Austria, some comparisons show a negative or near-zero mean marginal effect (Figure 152).

Figure 152. Average marginal effects of education by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

In terms of settlement type, the average estimates do not show a large difference between sparsely populated (7.04; CI: 6.91-7.18), intermediately dense (7.29; CI: 7.19-7.4) and densely populated (7.24; CI: 7.1-7.37) settlements. There is no significant relationship between settlement type and satisfaction, either for the whole sample or for the Hungarian groups. The average estimate for those with a partner is higher (7.42; CI: 7.33-7.5) than for single respondents (6.75; CI: 6.63-6.68). The average marginal effect is 0.5 (CI: 0.32-0.68), indicating a significant relationship between having a partner and life satisfaction. However, this relationship is not significant for Hungarians in Austria (0.11; CI: -0.38-0.61). For potential migrants (0.92; CI: 0.51-1.33), the average marginal effect is almost double that of those who want to stay (0.45; CI: 0.23-0.67) (Figure 153).

Figure 153. Average marginal effects of having a partner by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

There is a large difference between the average estimates of the two extreme categories of the expenditure coverage variable. The value for „with major difficulties” is 5.15 (CI: 4.76-5.53), while the value for „very easily” is 8.84 (CI: 8.47-9.21). The average marginal effect of the „with difficulties-with major difficulties” is not significant, but for the categories indicating further easier coverage, a relationship with satisfaction is already apparent. For the „with some difficulties-with major difficulties comparison”, the average marginal effect is 0.7 (CI: 0.2-1.21), while for the „very easily-with major difficulties comparison” it is 1.9 (CI: 1.25-2.6). The moderating effect highlights that the relationship is stronger in the two groups in Hungary. In the group of Hungarians in Austria, the average marginal effects are also in the positive direction, except for the „with difficulties-with major difficulties comparison”, but the associations are not significant (Figure 154).

Figure 154. Average marginal effects of the ease of covering the expenses by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Dissatisfaction related to the lack of own house/home is strongest in the group of potential migrants (-0.34; CI: -0.77-0.09), but no significant relationship is found even in this subsample. Mean estimates increase with improvements in perceptions of health in the order of bad (5.93; CI: 5.66-6.21), fair (6.82; CI: 6.67-6.96), good (7.29; CI: 7.19-7.4) and very good (7.72; CI: 7.58-7.86). In the full sample, the relationship is not significant, with the expected positive correlation among the Hungarian groups only appearing in the group of those who want to stay in Hungary. For Hungarians in Austria, the effect is in the direction of bad health, but the confidence interval extends well above 0, and the relationship is not significant (Figure 155).

Figure 155. Average marginal effects of perceived health by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Abundance of peer relationships shows a less clear relationship with overall satisfaction with life than with satisfaction with relations. The presence of the possibility to ask for help is significant at the $p < 0.1$ level (1; CI: -0.16-2.17) only in the subsample of Hungarians in Austria (Figure 156).

Figure 156. Average marginal effects of the potential of getting help by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

The relationship with the number of friends is generally not significant. Two interesting relationships emerge after the moderation by the Hungarian groups. For those who want to stay in Hungary, having one friend is associated with lower satisfaction compared to having no friend (-0.5; CI: -0.9-(-0.11)). For potential migrants, a satisfaction excess associated with having 5-9 friends is found (0.94; CI: -0.05-1.94), which is significant at the $p < 0.1$ level (Figure 157).

Figure 157. Average marginal effects of the number of friends by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Unlike the raw number of friends, meeting with them is more important for satisfaction. The average estimate for those who answered yes to meeting friends is 7.5 (CI: 7.42-7.59), while the estimate for those who do not meet friends due to financial or time constraints is only 6.16 (CI: 5.93-6.38). In this comparison, the average marginal effect is 0.073 (CI: -0.31-0.46), not significant. However, in the „yes, meeting friend-not meeting friends for other reasons comparison” there is a significant positive relationship at the $p < 0.1$ level (0.22, CI: -0.0001-0.44). The relationships are in the positive direction for all Hungarian groups, with the strongest link found for potential migrants. For potential migrants, a further disadvantage of not spending time with friends due to a restriction in the comparison with „meeting friends” also appears significant at the $p < 0.05$ level (-0.94; CI: -2.59-(-1.09)) (Figure 158).

Figure 158. Average marginal effects of meeting with friends by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

As with meeting people, the opportunity to spend leisure time was also found to be important for life satisfaction. Leisure passivity due to financial or time constraints seems particularly damaging. The average marginal effect for the „yes, spending leisure time-no, cannot afford it comparison” is 0.74 (CI: 0.42-0.15), for the „yes, spending leisure time-no, for other reasons comparison” it is 0.23 (CI: 0.03-0.43), and for „no, cannot afford it-no, for other reasons comparison” it is 0.5 (-0.81-(-0.19)). All are significant. These trends appear in all of the three Hungarian groups. For Hungarians in Austria, only the „yes, spending leisure time-no, cannot afford it comparison” (1.07; CI: -0.18-2.34) is significant at the $p < 0.1$ level (Figure 159).

Figure 159. Average marginal effects of spending leisure time by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

In terms of social exclusion, a significant relationship with satisfaction at the $p < 0.1$ level was found only in the „absolutely not excluded-totally excluded comparison” (0.63; CI: -0.03-1.29). However, this relationship is only significant and strong in the group of Hungarians in Austria (2.16; CI: 0.71-3.63). In this group, even the „so-so-totally excluded comparison” indicates a positive relationship with life satisfaction (1.44; CI: 0.03-2.85) (Figure 160).

Figure 160. Average marginal effects of social exclusion by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Potential migrants show a satisfaction deficit related to CSO membership (-0.51; CI: -0.95-(-0.07)). However, the average marginal effect of trust in other members of society is strongest for this group (0.1; CI: 0.02-0.19). The relationship between generalized trust and satisfaction is also significant for those who want to stay in Hungary (0.06; CI: 0.01-0.1), but not for Hungarians in Austria (-0.007; CI: -0.11-0.1). The relationship with institutional trust is not significant for potential migrants (0.02; CI: -0.04-0.1). The positive association with that variable is slightly stronger for Hungarians in Austria (0.13; CI: -0.008-0.27, $p=0.06$) than for those intending to stay in Hungary (0.05; CI: 0.02-0.09). Problems related to housing and living environment are associated with lower satisfaction (-0.17; CI: -0.27-(-0.06)). The average marginal effect for potential migrants (-0.29; CI: -0.48-(-0.11)) is almost double that for those intending to stay (-0.14; CI: -0.28-(-0.01)). No significant relationship was found in the group of Hungarians from Austria (-0.07; CI: -0.29-0.14). Regarding the safety of the living environment, a significant relationship towards a higher satisfaction with a less safe place is found for those intending to stay at the $p<0.1$ level. In the two other Hungarian groups, the average marginal effects all point towards a safer place (Figure 161).

Figure 161. Average marginal effects of the feeling of safety by the Hungarian groups. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

7.1.2. Extended model for Austria

Higher life satisfaction before migration is somewhat transmitted to after migration, with an average marginal effect of 0.08 (CI: -0.06-0.22), but the relationship is not significant. The moderating effect of pre-migration satisfaction appears in the variables type of settlement and request for help. Those who were satisfied before migration experience higher satisfaction after migration in an intermediately dense municipality, while those who were dissatisfied before migration experience higher satisfaction in a sparsely populated municipality. The increase in satisfaction associated with the possibility to ask for help is higher for those who were dissatisfied before migration. The average marginal effect for the variable „visits to Hungary” indicates a potential negative relationship between frequent visits home and satisfaction (-0.23; CI: -0.63-0.15), but the relationship is not significant. However, the moderating effect of satisfaction before migration is also present in this variable. For those who were more satisfied with their lives before migration, frequent return home shows a satisfaction gain compared to those who were previously dissatisfied. In terms of reasons for migration, a negative but non-significant relationship (-0.37; CI: -0.86-0.12) with satisfaction is found for those who moved to Austria to establish a future back in Hungary.

8. The drivers of emigration intentions in Hungary

In order to better understand emigration intentions, in the following the results of a series of logistic regression models will be presented where those expressing the intention to migrate within the following two years are compared to those who do not have such plans.

8.1. Microcensus vs the MIGWELL survey

First, similar models based on similar survey questions were built and run on the 2016 Microcensus data and the 2023 MIGWELL representative survey data to check the validity of our results and to put forward eventual changes in time.

Despite the important differences in sample size of the two models, which affects the level of significance of the different parameters, the overall direction of the effects of the different variables remains quite stable. The most important drivers of migration intentions are friends or relatives already living abroad and previous experiences with migration, alongside the level of urbanization of the place one lives – people from more urbanized areas are more willing to move abroad (Table 12).

In terms of socio-demographic characteristics, in line with previous research (e.g., Sik, 2018), beside urbanized areas, migration intentions are also more likely among a younger population. The model indeed confirms that 18–25-year-olds are more willing to migrate than people of 46 years of age or older. It is also more likely among people living in Budapest, especially compared to the Great Plain and North of Hungary.

The effect of other variables, although with similar direction as in the Microcensus model, remain non-significant. This is the case for the overall life satisfaction: its parameter is very similar in the MIGWELL survey to the Microcensus, a higher level of satisfaction with life decreasing the intentions to migrate, nevertheless, probably due to the smaller sample size, it remains statistically non-significant.

Table 12. Drivers of emigration intentions in Hungary in 2016 and 2023 (logistic regression models).

Logistic regression model: plan to move abroad in the upcoming 2 years vs not	Microcensus 2016		MIGWELL representative survey	
(Intercept)	0.534***	(0.071)	0.516	(0.437)
26-35 vs below 26	0.648***	(0.052)	0.410+	(0.188)
36-45	0.443***	(0.037)	0.591	(0.348)
46-55	0.236***	(0.023)	0.159**	(0.109)
56-65	0.118***	(0.015)	0.077**	(0.074)
66-75	0.085***	(0.019)	0.134*	(0.134)
75+	0.061***	(0.019)	0.000***	(0.000)
Female vs Male	0.777***	(0.038)	0.995	(0.294)
Self-employed vs Employed	1.011	(0.090)	0.452	(0.294)
Unemployed	1.440***	(0.152)	2.463	(1.804)
Student	1.140	(0.115)	0.450	(0.290)
Retired	0.515***	(0.097)	0.508	(0.497)
Disabled	0.293***	(0.085)	0.000***	(0.000)
Other inactive	1.206+	(0.136)	0.409	(0.319)
Secondary	1.322***	(0.093)	0.402	(0.243)
Tertiary	1.513***	(0.135)	0.482	(0.318)
Married	0.617***	(0.037)	0.605	(0.234)
Children under 6	0.881	(0.095)	1.889	(1.056)
Children under 18	0.974	(0.035)	0.747	(0.156)
Great Plain and North	0.799***	(0.052)	0.350+	(0.195)
Transdanubia	0.782***	(0.051)	0.647	(0.318)
Urbanisation: Intermediate vs Thin	1.054	(0.062)	2.304*	(0.975)
Dense	1.364***	(0.093)	2.882*	(1.396)
Previous migration	2.029***	(0.180)	3.915**	(1.825)
Friends/ relatives abroad	2.904***	(0.249)	5.885***	(2.499)
Overall satisfaction	0.852***	(0.010)	0.874	(0.077)
Num.Obs.	47782		807	
R ²	0.154		0.291	
R ² Adj.	0.154		0.268	
AIC	20102.0		401.6	
BIC	20383.0		569.2	
Log.Lik.	-10046.052		-194.242	
F	66.370		137.929	
RMSE	0.22		0.25	

+ p < 0.1, * p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, *** p < 0.001

Source of data: Hungarian Microcensus 2016, MIGWELL representative survey. Odds ratios. Own calculation.

8.2. The role of economic, cultural and political factors, the assessment of the situation in the country, and social connectedness

Two models were run to measure the effect of economic variables and the effect of social connectedness controlling for the variables already mentioned in the previous part, among joint samples of the MIGWELL surveys including the representative sample and the boost sample (Table 13). Besides the effect of the control variables, as presented in the previous part, in these models people with children under 6 are more likely to plan to move as opposed to people with older children who are rather less eager in this respect.

Subjective perception of economic factors seems to matter. The likelihood of migration intention increases if someone is worried about unemployment. Perceived prospects, i.e., whether one can advance in their position plays a significant role as well: if there is no perceived possibility to attain a higher position, likelihood of intentions to move abroad is higher. Furthermore, those with a stable job (i.e., who are employed) are more likely to be willing to move than self-employed. Economic factors affect intention also when it comes to the perception of the country's economic situation. Those who think the country's economy is in a bad shape are more likely to have migration intentions.

Social connectedness is an important predictor of migration intentions. Those who have more friends in general are more likely to express such intentions. Nevertheless, in terms of social self-categorization or identification (people could choose up to 3 categories that matter most to them), those more willing to migrate are also those who are more defined by their family or their friends and chose other categories instead, but they also trust other people less.

Interestingly, when economic factors are taken into account (job prospects, perception of the country's economy, fear of unemployment), the effect of the level of overall satisfaction with life is neutralized. When considering different measures of social connectedness, lower level of satisfaction is a significant predictor of migration intentions.

Table 13. Economic, cultural and social drivers of emigration intentions (logistic regression models).

Logistic regression model: plan to move abroad in the upcoming 2 years vs not/DK	Model: Economic factors		Model: Social connectedness	
(Intercept)	0.202	(0.198)	4.417+	(3.655)
26-35 vs below 26	0.838	(0.329)	0.733	(0.208)
36-45	0.539	(0.245)	0.641	(0.211)
46-55	0.328*	(0.143)	0.306***	(0.099)
56-65	0.170**	(0.097)	0.093***	(0.044)
66-75	0.000	(0.000)	0.198+	(0.166)
Female vs Male	0.812	(0.186)	0.803	(0.140)
Secondary vs Primary	1.747	(0.980)	1.624	(0.606)
Tertiary	2.260	(1.453)	1.417	(0.612)
Married	1.026	(0.291)	0.759	(0.165)
Children under 6	3.097**	(1.191)	2.658**	(0.808)
Children under 18	0.779	(0.138)	0.726*	(0.095)
Great Plain and North vs Budapest	0.411**	(0.137)	0.851	(0.214)
Transdanubia	0.670	(0.228)	0.935	(0.231)
Urbanisation: Intermediate vs Thin	0.636	(0.179)	0.665*	(0.138)
Dense	1.092	(0.351)	1.091	(0.280)
Previous migration	3.025**	(1.196)	2.092*	(0.600)
Friends/ relatives abroad	2.486***	(0.616)	3.621***	(0.729)
Overall satisfaction	1.048	(0.085)	0.822***	(0.048)
Worried about unemployment	1.461***	(0.164)		
Higher position: Rather no vs no	0.599+	(0.176)		
Higher position: Rather yes.	0.447*	(0.155)		
Higher position: Yes, absolutely	0.747	(0.340)		
Country economy: neither good nor bad vs bad	0.462*	(0.161)		
Country economy: good	0.350*	(0.175)		
Self-employed vs employed			0.449*	(0.163)
Unemployed			1.581	(0.752)
Student			0.874	(0.361)
Retired			0.187+	(0.176)
Other inactive			0.196*	(0.127)
Nb of friends			1.192***	(0.055)
Identification: position in family (No vs marked)			0.693+	(0.130)
Identification: friends (No vs marked)			0.675+	(0.150)
Trust others			0.859***	(0.032)
Num.Obs.	527		1089	
AIC	560.2		959.5	
BIC	684.0		1134.2	
Log.Lik.	-251.107		-444.743	
RMSE	0.40		0.36	

+ p < 0.1, * p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, *** p < 0.001

Source of data: MIGWELL surveys (representative+boost sample). Odds ratios. Own calculation.

8.3. The differential effect of subjective well-being

It is also worth examining whether the degree of satisfaction affects different groups differently. A good example of this is the research by Brzozowski and Coniglio (2021), which showed the effect of SWB on migration only in the case of women and employed people. To analyse whether such differential effect exist, a series of interaction effects were added one-by one to the baseline model, and tested. The interaction models were based on the MIGWELL model presented in chapter 8.1. including the representative survey and the boost sample. The following graphs concern interaction with statistically significant effects and show the percentage chance of emigration (y-axis) given by the model when the two variables involved in the interaction (x-axis and subcategories according to line colours) take on different values.

Overall satisfaction had a differential effect depending on one’s economic status. As shown in the graph (Figure 162), dissatisfied unemployed people and dissatisfied students, who maybe have less administrative attachments and obligations, are more likely to be willing to emigrate than dissatisfied employed people, retirees, etc.

Figure 162. Interaction effect of economic activity and overall life satisfaction on migration intentions (predicted probabilities). Source of data: MIGWELL surveys (representative+boost sample). Own calculation.

The effect of satisfaction with one’s accommodation on migration intentions also depends on the urbanization of the settlement where one lives. Among those dissatisfied with their housing situation, people living in densely populated areas are by far the most likely to emigrate (Figure 163).

Figure 163. Interaction effect of urbanization level and satisfaction with accommodation on migration intentions (predicted probabilities). Source of data: MIGWELL surveys (representative+boost sample). Own calculation.

8.4. Choosing Austria as destination

When dealing with migration intentions it was also interesting to look at what the drivers are of choosing Austria as opposed to other destinations. In the following model those who included Austria in their top three destination countries received a value of 0, while those who did not include it received a value of 1. Results of the model show that self-employed people would favour other destinations and people choosing Austria are less likely from Budapest. In terms of overall life satisfaction, Austria is chosen by those less satisfied (Table 14).

Table 14. Drivers of choosing Austria as destination country among those planning to migrate in the following 2 years (logistic regression models).

Destination: other countries (1) vs Austria (0) - logistic regression model		
(Intercept)	0.231	(2.440000e-01)
26-35 vs below 26	1.620	(6.770000e-01)
36-45	1.196	(6.170000e-01)
46-55	1.043	(5.660000e-01)
56-65	0.386	(3.620000e-01)
66-75	1.390	(2.133000e+00)
Female vs Male	1.000	(2.820000e-01)
Self-employed vs Employed	4.448+	(3.684000e+00)
Unemployed	0.838	(5.590000e-01)
Student	2.611	(1.666000e+00)

Retired	0.447	(7.250000e-01)
Other inactive	0.000	(0.000000e+00)
Secondary vs Primary	1.211	(7.880000e-01)
Tertiary	1.862	(1.391000e+00)
Married	0.759	(2.810000e-01)
Children under 6	1.668	(8.290000e-01)
Children under 18	1.377	(3.410000e-01)
Great Plain and North vs Budapest	0.384*	(1.490000e-01)
Transdanubia	0.366**	(1.400000e-01)
Urbanisation: Intermediate vs Thin	0.859	(3.010000e-01)
Dense	0.620	(2.360000e-01)
Previous migration	0.968	(3.960000e-01)
Friends/ relatives abroad	0.806	(3.110000e-01)
Overall satisfaction	1.353**	(1.310000e-01)
<hr/>		
Num.Obs.	282	
AIC	377.3	
BIC	468.4	
Log.Lik.	-163.659	
RMSE	0.45	

+ p < 0.1, * p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, *** p < 0.001

Source of data: MIGWELL surveys (representative+boost sample). Odds ratios. Own calculation.

9. How does migration affect subjective well-being in Austria?

9.1. Changes by subjective well-being dimensions

Compared to the pre-migration period, satisfaction with life increased for 70.3% of respondents and decreased for only 11.9%, with only two domains showing a larger percentage increase, public services (76.6%) and income (72.9%). However, only 39% and 26.1% experienced an increase in satisfaction with social relations and health respectively. A high proportion reported stagnation in satisfaction in the health domain (38.3%), while 31.9% reported a decrease in satisfaction in the social relations domain. Also relatively high was the proportion experiencing a decrease (26.7%) and relatively low was the proportion experiencing an increase (50.9%) in the domain of leisure (Figure 164).

Figure 164. Changes in satisfaction dimensions. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

The sample was then filtered out to contain only those respondents, for whose, we could calculate satisfaction differences across all domains and also in the overall life satisfaction. Only 2.7% of this sub-sample experienced no increase in any one domain. In contrast, 10.3% found that emigrating to Austria was worthwhile in every area of life we examined. The highest proportion of respondents (17.9%) reported a positive change in 6 and 7 areas (Figure 165).

Figure 165. Distribution of the aggregate number of domains with an increase by respondents. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Although respondents experienced almost similar rates of increase in satisfaction with public services and income, the average change in satisfaction with public services is higher (2.57 compared to 2.4 for income). The average change in satisfaction with life is 1.5. There is only one domain where the average change is negative, and that is satisfaction with health (-0.06) (Figure 166).

Figure 166. Boxplot of changes in satisfaction dimensions. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

In the following, we examined how satisfaction with life in general and in each domain varied by socio-economic variables, transnational activity, migration reason and year of emigration. In general, two groups are compared, with the difference between the mean of the two in parentheses. Across all domains, we found a larger average increase for men than for women. The largest difference between the means of the two genders is measured for satisfaction with public services (2.59), while the smallest difference is measured for satisfaction with health (0.22) (Figure 167). Men's satisfaction with their income also improved substantially more (2.53 difference compared to women). In terms of educational attainment, there were more positive trends (it could mean a smaller decrease as well) for the highly educated than for the lower educated in most domains. Again, the largest difference in this comparison is for public services (1.12), but there is also a large difference in the change in the health domain (0.42). However, for the highly qualified, there was a smaller average increase in satisfaction with life (-0.48 difference), and in satisfaction with social relations (-0.51) and green spaces (-0.52). For the type of settlement variable, the majority of domains tended towards sparsely populated versus densely populated. However, those living in densely populated settlements show larger average increases in the domains of satisfaction with life (0.23), public services (0.42) and income (0.05). Living in a densely populated settlement shows a smaller increase in satisfaction with housing (-1.16), green spaces (-0.97) and work (-0.64). On average, those with a partner experienced more positive changes than those without a partner. The only exception is satisfaction with health, where satisfaction decreased more for those with a partner (-0.04 difference). However, those with a partner experienced larger increases in satisfaction with social relationships (0.63), green spaces (0.7) and housing (0.94).

Figure 167. Mean difference in the change of satisfaction dimensions by socio-economic variables. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

A comparison by transnational activities shows that there is typically a smaller increase in satisfaction when these activities are pursued (Figure 168). The only variable where there is a higher increase in several domains when this activity is present than when this activity is absent is the remitting behaviour. The largest positive differences by remittance are found in the domains of income (0.35) and health (0.21) and in overall satisfaction with life (0.15). While there were smaller increases in the domains of social relationships (-0.23) and time use (-0.4) when the respondent remitted. In the domains of time use (-0.99 difference) and social relations (-0.87), there were also more negative trends for frequent home visits (on average, satisfaction with social relations decreased in this group) than for infrequent home visits. However, frequent travellers experienced a larger increase in satisfaction with public services (0.88). Those leaving their child or partner at home also experienced substantially less favourable changes in the domains of public services (-1.1), time use (-1.02), and housing (-0.82) than those moving out with the whole family. Also, in this potentially lonely group, satisfaction with health has decreased by an average of 0.38 compared to the situation before migration. Individuals who were overqualified for their job experienced a more negative change in all domains except satisfaction with public services. On average, their satisfaction even decreased in the domains of social relationships (-0.31), health (-0.16) and time use (-0.02) compared to situation before migration. Although the overqualified increased their job satisfaction by 0.86 on average, this was 1.38 lower than the average for the non-overqualified. The other domain where the overqualified fall remarkably behind is housing (-1.39 difference).

Figure 168. Mean difference in the change of satisfaction dimensions by transnational variables. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

For all domains, the average change in satisfaction for those who indicated a reason for financial migration was more favourable than for those who did not (Figure 169). There was also a large difference in satisfaction with life (0.85), with even greater differences in the domains of income (0.86) and housing (1.15). The smallest difference is in satisfaction with health (0.35). The group that wants to establish its future in Hungary shows more negative trends. Of course, there is still a satisfaction increase everywhere except for the health domain, but to a lesser extent than for those who did not indicate this reason. Only in the domain of social relations (0.07) is there a minimal positive difference in favour of this migration reason. In the domains of satisfaction with life (-0.38) and especially in the domains of public services (-0.68 difference), green spaces (-0.7) and housing (-0.85), a smaller increase is observed in the presence of this migration reason. In the presence of migration due to relationship reason only in the domains of time use (0.04) and housing (0.22) are there a larger increase than in the absence of this reason. Even in the area of satisfaction with social relationships, the increase is smaller (-0.14 difference), but this is probably due to the fact that, having had a partner before migration, the individual's satisfaction was also high at that time. Substantially smaller increases were found in the domains of overall satisfaction with life (-0.79) and public services (-0.88).

Figure 169. Mean difference in the change of satisfaction dimensions by migration reason variables. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

In the case of life satisfaction, the two categories indicating older out-migration show a higher increase for migrants, and then a decrease can be observed towards the newer waves of out-migration (Figure 170). This may be due to the rapid increase in satisfaction in Hungary (satisfaction cannot increase as much after migration) in the 2010s and the low levels of early movers at that time. A similar temporal trend can be observed in the change in satisfaction with social relationships, where new movers experienced a smaller increase than older movers. Unlike the other groups, those moving out after COVID are characterised by a low change in housing satisfaction. However, it is in this group that the increase in satisfaction with public services is the highest. For earlier out-migrants, satisfaction with health has declined compared to pre-migration satisfaction, which may be influenced by problems associated with ageing. A higher increase in income satisfaction for those who moved between 2004 and 2011 also jumps out from the pattern.

Figure 170. Mean difference in the change of satisfaction dimensions by the era of migration. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

According to 70% of those taking part in the survey, the move to Austria has fulfilled their previous plans and hopes. However, the proportion of respondents who said they were completely satisfied (26.1%) was lower than those who said they were largely satisfied (43.9%), 23.2% gave a mixed response and only 4.5% were disappointed with the migration (Figure 171).

Figure 171. Opinion on whether the migration to Austria has lived up to the hopes. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Post-migration changes in life satisfaction and in each domain were also examined in terms of subjective perceptions of migration. The change in subjective well-being is not closely related to the perception of migration. The association of higher change associated with better perceptions and lower change or possible decrease associated with worse perceptions is most evident in satisfaction with social relationships and overall satisfaction with life (Figure 172). For the domains of job and income, for example, the difference in median change is minimal. The lower change and negative median for those reporting unsuccessful migration is found in the domains of housing, time use, health (where the median for the other categories is also close to zero) and public services, in addition to social relations.

Figure 172. Changes in satisfaction dimensions by the assessment of migration success. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

9.2. Changes in affective and eudaimonic variables

There are also typically positive trends in affective variables (Figure 173). The proportion of respondents not experiencing any negative emotions at all in the weeks prior to responding increased, especially for nervousness and feeling downhearted. There was also an increase in the proportion of „a little of the time” responses, while the proportion of the „most of the time” answers which was noticeable in the pre-migration period, decreased. The charts also show that not only did respondents moved to a better category from the „most of the time” option, but typically the same proportion selected a category which corresponds to a one-step increase (most of the time -> some of the time) and a two-step increase (most of the time -> a little of the time). In the case of depression, the response pair „most of the time pre-migration and none at all post-migration” is also common (29% of those who marked „most of the time” before migration). Loneliness is the negative emotion where the post-migration rates are most similar to the pre-migration rates. From those who were „none of the time” lonely before migration 28% of people became lonely „a little of the time”, 18% „some of the time” and 10% „most of the time” after migration. However, there is also a positive change, for example 29% of people who were „most of the time” lonely before moving to Austria, were not lonely at all in the weeks before the survey. There is also an improvement in positive emotions after migration. For happiness and calmness, more than half of Hungarians in Austria answered „all of the time” or „most of the time”. In the survey, 57% of those who were „some of the time” happy before migration already indicated that they are „most of the time” happy now.

Feel down

Feel downhearted

Feel stressed

Feel calm

Feel lonely

Being nervous

Being happy

Figure 173. Changes in affective variables. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

There is some evidence of a link between the feeling of loneliness and having a partner or child left behind in Hungary (Figure 174). Among those with a family member staying at home, the proportion of „none at all” lonely people decreased after migration. 65% of those who were „none at all lonely” before migration have become lonelier since migration (20% moved to the „most of the time” category). In contrast among those, 60% of those who had the whole family in their household in Austria and were „none at all” lonely before migration answered never lonely after migration as well.

Figure 174. Changes in loneliness by having a leftover partner or child(ren). Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

We have examined the relationship between income and happiness, and the association between the change of these two variables (Figure 175). If we look separately at the pre-migration and post-migration period, there is no evidence that low income is associated with low levels of happiness. 48% of those in the lowest income category before migration indicated that they

were happy „most of the time” or „all of the time”. After migration, 70% of those in the lowest income category were at least happy „most of the time”. In the highest payment category after migration, 83% responded with „most of the time” or „all of the time”. The largest proportion of people, who are happy „all the time” belong to the highest income category.

Figure 175. Changes in happiness and income. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

The relationship between the perception of success of migration and the increase in happiness is illustrated in the figure below (Figure 176). Of those whose expectations were largely lived up, 86% are happy „most of the time” or „all of the time”. For those with a mixed assessment of migration, the percentage of those who were happy „most of the time” or „all of the time” was only 58.64%. However, it should also be noted that those who had a positive assessment of migration had a slight happiness surplus before migration. 53.65% of those who considered migration successful and are „most of the time” happy after migration were less happy before migration. Compare this value to the 79.4% of those with „most of the time” happiness level before migration and mixed perceptions of migration. Putting these together it means, that a

larger proportion of people increased their happiness level in the mixed assessment category. So there is no clear link between increased happiness and better perceptions of migration.

Being happy
Largely lived up

Being happy
Mixed

Figure 176. Changes in happiness by the assessment of migration success. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

There is also a positive shift in the variables of eudaimonic well-being compared to pre-migration times (Figure 177). Optimism has increased in 59% of respondents, the perception of meaningfulness of life has increased in 60%, while the perception of freedom to live has improved in 61.2%. The percentage reporting a decrease is highest for the variable „free life” at 20%.

Figure 177. Changes in eudaimonic variables. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

The interquartile range is between 0 and 2 for each variable, while the median is 1. It can be seen that the variation in these variables is very similar, with no differentiation towards one or the other eudaimonic indicator (Figure 178).

Figure 178. Boxplot of changes in eudaimonic variables. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Men and the highly educated show higher average improvements than women or the low educated for all eudaimonic indicators (Figure 179). For the highly educated, the improvement in free living (1.51 increase; 1.45 difference compared to the low educated) is particularly substantial. However, for those living in densely populated settlements, the averages of changes are lower than in thinly populated areas. The difference is -0.9 for the optimism variable and -0.92 for the free life variable. The opposite trends are observed for the partner variable, with the average improvement for those with a partner higher for the meaning of life and free life variables, but lower for the optimism indicator.

Figure 179. Mean difference in the change of eudaimonic variables by socio-economic variables. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

Transnational activities tend to be associated with lower average growth than not engaging in these activities (Figure 180). Only in the remittance variable has the presence of the activity higher average growth than those who do not remit. The difference is 0.44 for the free life variable and 0.49 for the optimism variable. The lower increase for frequent visits home is most pronounced for the optimism (-0.74) and meaning of life (-0.62) variables. For the child or partner left behind, lower increases are observed in the optimism (-0.79) and free life (-0.63) variables, while for the presence of overeducation, lower increases are observed in the meaning of life (-0.88) and free life (-0.86) variables (but still all variables show positive changes).

Figure 180. Mean difference in the change of eudaimonic variables by transnational variables. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

In terms of reasons for migration, higher increases are found for the financial and establishing a future in Hungary motivations, while lower increases are found for the reason of having a relationship (Figure 181). For those who migrate for financial reasons, the variables of optimism (0.62 difference compared to those who do not) and free life (0.58) show higher growth, while for those who migrate for helping their future in Hungary, the variable of free life (0.35) should be highlighted.

Figure 181. Mean difference in the change of eudaimonic variables by migration reason variables. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

The indicators of optimism and free life show higher increases for the two later waves of migration, while the meaning of life variable shows the largest increase for the earliest movers (Figure 182).

Figure 182. Mean difference in the change of eudaimonic variables by the era of migration. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

The positive relationship between the increase in eudaimonic variables and the improved perception of migration is most striking for the indicator „free life”, especially when comparing „no” and „yes, completely lived up” responses. Those who think migration has not met their expectations also show smaller median increases in the indicators of optimism and meaning of life than the other groups (Figure 183).

Figure 183. Change in eudaimonic dimensions by the assessment of migration success. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

9.3. Causal model

After reducing selection bias and restricting the analysis to the most recent emigrants (2018–2022), the causal model shows no statistically significant migration effect for the sense of meaningful life variable, although the average treatment effect on the matched sample points in a positive direction. For life satisfaction and happiness, however, the results clearly indicate positive migration effects (Table 15). When control variables and their interactions with the treatment variable were included in the model, the ATM for life satisfaction was estimated at 0.57, with an average predicted value of 7.27 for migrants. The model therefore attributes an increase of nearly 8.8% in life satisfaction to migration. This finding remains robust even after the sensitivity test. Unobserved confounders (orthogonal to the covariates) that account for more than 3.62% of the residual variance in both the treatment and the outcome would be sufficient to shift the estimate into a range where it is no longer statistically distinguishable from zero (representing a bias equal to 100% of the original estimate), at a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$. For example, if satisfaction with income were omitted from the model as a confounding variable, its effect alone would not reach this threshold; in fact, a confounder at least six times stronger would be required to do so.

In the case of happiness, migration is associated with a reduced probability of reporting „little or none of the time” or „some of the time”, and with an increased probability of reporting „most of the time,” for which the ATM is 0.24. According to the average predictions, the likelihood of „most of the time” happiness is 64% among migrants, compared to only 40.3% in the absence of migration (i.e., in the control condition).

Table 15. Modelling change in SWB using causal models.

SWB variable	Level	ATM
Life satisfaction		0.57** [0.2 - 0.94]
Happiness	Little or none of the time	-0.09*** [-0.12 -- 0.04]
	Some of the time	-0.14*** [-0.21 -- 0.06]
	Most of the time	0.24*** [0.12 - 0.36]
	All of the time	-0.01 [-0.04 – 0.005]
Meaning of life		0.26 [-0.05 - 0.58]

Note: ATM and 95% confidence interval values. *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$, + $p < 0.1$

Most moderating effects were not statistically significant; at the $p < 0.05$ level, significant results were found only for satisfaction with income and satisfaction with social relationships. In the case of income, even among those with median satisfaction (within the „Hungarian stayers” subsample), migration is associated with a greater gain in life satisfaction due to migration compared to those who are maximally satisfied with their income (1.32 [0.16 – 2.50]),

where the ATM is negative. However, compared to the median, the minimum value of income satisfaction does not yield a statistically significant additional gain.

A similar pattern emerges for satisfaction with social relationships: median satisfaction is associated with an advantage over the maximum, or, the latter appears to carry a disadvantage. For „most of the time” happiness, the ATM difference is 0.20 (0.005 – 0.39), while for life satisfaction it is 0.56 (–0.03 – 1.16), the latter being significant at the $p < 0.1$ level. For life satisfaction, a disadvantage of median satisfaction compared to the minimum is also observed at the $p < 0.1$ level.

Happiness also shows an additional gain for those with median satisfaction with their health status compared to those maximally satisfied. The positive male effect on life satisfaction is also evident in our model: the ATM for men is 0.96 (0.43 – 1.48), whereas for women it is only 0.24 (–0.26 – 0.75). The moderating effect of gender is statistically significant at the $p < 0.1$ level.

10. Return migration potential

9.4% of Hungarians in Austria plan to move back to Hungary in the next three years, while another 11% do not know or did not want to answer. 30.85% of those planning to return home are still considering the possibility, 27.66% are seriously considering the idea, 27.66% have already made a decision and 13.83% have already taken concrete steps. In addition to those planning to return to Hungary, 6.8% of the sample plan to move in the next two years, not to Hungary but to a third country. Overall, 80.2% of the total sample said that they definitely do not plan to leave Austria in the short term.

By far the most frequently cited reason for returning home was related to social relations (75.86% of those planning to return home). Aiming to achieve the goal set at the beginning of migration was cited by 20.68%, while other reasons were mentioned by 17.24%. None of the other response options was selected by at least five respondents. The problem of getting used to Austria was not mentioned by any of the respondents (Figure 184).

Figure 184. Reasons for the potential return. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

The main reason given for staying in Austria was financial (67.2%), but many also cited a more predictable future (52.63%) and better working conditions (40.48%), while 20.2% also mentioned social contacts as a factor (Figure 185).

Figure 185. Reasons for staying in Austria. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

The highest proportion of potential returnees (19.44%) is found among those who have a mixed perception of migration. Even the majority (71.42%) of those who think that migration has not fulfilled their previous expectations would not return to Hungary. And 87.65% of those who are completely satisfied with migration would definitely not return home (Figure 186).

Figure 186. Return migration intention by the assessment of the migration success. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

In both the life satisfaction variable and the satisfaction domains, we typically see higher median increases for those planning to stay in Austria than for potential returnees. For overall life satisfaction, the median value is 2 for the group planning to stay and 1 for the group planning to return. Moreover, a negative change is also observed for potential returnees, with a median change in satisfaction with social relationships of -1 (Figure 187).

Figure 187. Changes in satisfaction dimensions by return migration intention. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

The pre-migration happiness indicators of those planning to stay in Austria and those planning to return were almost similar, but the current happiness of those planning to return is lower than that of those planning to stay (Figure 188).

Figure 188. Changes in happiness levels by return migration intention. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

In terms of change in eudaimonic indicators, the largest (1) median increase difference between those planning to stay and those planning to return is found in the variable meaning of life. In contrast, the median increase in the free life indicator is the same. For all three variables, the median is zero among those who are uncertain about returning home or did not answer the question (Figure 189).

Figure 189. Changes in eudaimonic variables by return migration intention. Source of data: MIGWELL surveys 2024. Own figure.

11. Literature

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12. Appendix

Model formulas

- Satisfaction with job

- Whole sample:

$stf_job \sim hun_group * (hours + isco08_1 + educ_triconsult + contract + higherpos + gender + age + I(age^2) + hhsiz e + urban + covid_job + help_material + partner + expenses + looked_down_combined + health + leisure2)$

- Hungarians in Austria:

$stf_job \sim stf_job_pre * (children_partner + overqualified + selfeconstat_3 + educ_triconsult + higherpos + urban + gender + age + I(age^2) + hhsiz e + yimmig + covid_job + help_material + partner + visit_hu + expenses + remittance + looked_down_combined + migration_why_financial + migration_why_relations + migration_why_future_hungary)$

- Satisfaction with income

- Whole sample:

$hun_group * (selfeconstat_3 + educ_triconsult + gender + age + I(age^2) + hhsiz e + urban + covid_inc + relative_income + help_material + partner + expenses + deprived + looked_down_combined)$

- Hungarians in Austria:

$stf_income_pre * (selfeconstat_3 + educ_triconsult + gender + age + I(age^2) + hhsiz e + urban + covid_inc + relative_income + help_material + partner + expenses + deprived + looked_down_combined + overqualified + children_partner + remittance + visit_hu + migration_why_financial + migration_why_relations + migration_why_future_hungary + yimmig)$

- Satisfaction with housing conditions

- Whole sample:

$hun_group * (selfeconstat_3 + educ_triconsult + gender + age + I(age^2) + urban + owner + hh_room_ratio + problems + partner + expenses)$

- Hungarians in Austria:

$stf_accommodation \sim stf_accommodation_pre * (selfeconstat_3 + educ_triconsult + gender + age + I(age^2) + urban + owner + hh_room_ratio + problems + partner + expenses)$

nses+yimmig+remittance+migration_why_financial+migration_why_relations+migration_why_future_hungary)

- Satisfaction with social relationships

- Whole sample:

hun_group*(selfeconstat_3+educ_triconsult+gender+age+I(age^2)+urban+partner+hhsiz+children+help2+meet_friends2+social_ex_alternative+friends_total_cat+civic_part+trust_others)

- Hungarians in Austria:

stf_relation_pre*(selfeconstat_3+educ_triconsult+gender+age+I(age^2)+urban+hhsiz+children+help2+partner+meet_friends2+social_ex_alternative+friends_total_cat+civic_part+trust_others+yimmig+remittance+visit_hu+migration_why_financial+migration_why_relations+migration_why_future_hungary+children_partner+partner_nat+german)

- Satisfaction with health

- Whole sample:

hun_group*(selfeconstat_3+educ_triconsult+gender+age+I(age^2)+urban+partner+problems+leisure2+help2+expenses+social_ex_alternative+friends_total_cat+civic_part+covid_health)

- Hungarians in Austria:

stf_health_pre*(selfeconstat_3+educ_triconsult+gender+age+I(age^2)+urban+partner+problems+leisure2+help2+expenses+social_ex_alternative+friends_total_cat+civic_part+covid_health+yimmig+remittance+visit_hu+migration_why_financial+migration_why_relations+migration_why_future_hungary+children_partner)

- Satisfaction with work-life balance

- Whole sample:

hun_group*(selfeconstat_3+educ_triconsult+gender+age+I(age^2)+urban+partner+hhsiz+children+leisure2+meet_friends2+health+expenses+social_ex_alternative+friends_total_cat+civic_part)

- Hungarians in Austria:

stf_timeuse_pre*(selfeconstat_3+educ_triconsult+gender+age+I(age^2)+urban+partner+hhsiz+children+leisure2+meet_friends2+health+expenses+social_ex_alternative+friends_total_cat+civic_part+yimmig+visit_hu+migration_why_f

inancial+migration_why_relations+migration_why_future_hungary+children_partner+german)

- Satisfaction with public services

- Whole sample:

hun_group*(selfeconstat_3+educ_triconsult+gender+age+I(age^2)+urban+partner+children+health+expenses+socialex_alternative+trust_institute+feelsafe)

- Hungarians in Austria:

stf_public_pre*(selfeconstat_3+educ_triconsult+gender+age+I(age^2)+urban+partner+children+health+expenses+socialex_alternative+trust_institute+feelsafe+remittance+yimmig+visit_hu+migration_why_financial+migration_why_relations+migration_why_future_hungary+german)

- Satisfaction with green areas

- Whole sample:

hun_group*(selfeconstat_3+educ_triconsult+gender+age+I(age^2)+urban+partner+children+health+expenses+feelsafe+env_problem+noise)

- Hungarians in Austria:

stf_greenarea_pre*(selfeconstat_3+educ_triconsult+gender+age+I(age^2)+urban+partner+children+health+expenses+feelsafe+env_problem+noise+yimmig+visit_hu+migration_why_financial+migration_why_relations+migration_why_future_hungary+children_partner)

- Satisfaction with life overall

- Whole sample:

hun_group*(selfeconstat_3+educ_triconsult+gender+age+I(age^2)+urban+partner+expenses+help2+meet_friends2+leisure2+socialex_alternative+friends_total_cat+civic_part+trust_others+trust_institute+health+feelsafe+owner+hh_room_ratio+problems)

- Hungarians in Austria:

stf_overall_pre*(selfeconstat_3+educ_triconsult+gender+age+I(age^2)+urban+partner+expenses+help2+socialex_alternative+trust_institute+hh_room_ratio+yimmig+remittance+visit_hu+migration_why_financial+migration_why_relations+migration_why_future_hungary+children_partner+german)

Model's degree of fit (Adjusted R²)

Satisfaction with...	Whole sample	Hungarians in Austria
Job	0.29	0.64
Income	0.4	0.51
Housing conditions	0.25	0.39
Social relationships	0.29	0.42
Health	0.39	0.62
Work-life balance	0.19	0.28
Public services	0.24	0.34
Green areas	0.15	0.24
Life overall	0.38	0.58